

SUGAR - Surgical sUturing GrAdeR

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Abstract

Suturing is a fundamental surgical skill and surgical trainees' skills are meticulously evaluated by surgical educators. However, evaluation methods are primarily direct observation and manual video review using subjective rating scales that often lack precision and reproducibility. Manual evaluation is time-consuming, resource-intensive and expensive. The demand for objective assessment methods has motivated the development of technology-based approaches and the consequent need to define precise metrics for best surgical practices.

The work performed in this Master's Thesis aims to deliver a Proof-of-Concept for an objective, reproducible, and cost-effective method to evaluate surgical suturing skills, using a robust combination of traditional and advanced Computer Vision (CV) techniques. The novel Surgical sUturing GrAdeR (SUGAR) tool applies Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) object detection algorithms, such as YOLOv10 and YOLOv11, to detect and track surgical needles, the surgeon's hands and suturing tools. The surgical suturing skills are assessed using relevant metrics that are hard-coded following traditional CV techniques, bringing high explainability to the model. Several datasets, namely *AIsture*, *Instance2* and *Surgical needle* from *Roboflow*, are used to train the models and a dedicated dataset is purposely created with the collaboration of the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI) to validate and evaluate the SUGAR tool, based on high-definition videos of *ex-vivo* surgical suturing.

After comparing several models, results demonstrate that the most promising CV YOLOv11 models achieve a precision of 92.0% and a recall factor of 87.3% for the videos' suturing tools detection and segmentation, and a precision of 95.6% and a recall factor of 90.3% for the images' key suture components detection and segmentation. Based on these results, these models are therefore selected to validate the performance of the SUGAR tool, applying thirteen suture quality metrics, based on three of the four surgical skills assessment scales used by the RCSI grading system.

The Master's Thesis produces a Proof-of-Concept for a novel CV-based tool capable

of delivering objective and cost-effective suture skills assessments, by automatically evaluating key suture quality parameters with a precision of 85.68% and a recall factor of 61.75%. This Thesis's results exhibit a promising potential for the SUGAR system's use as an educational tool that will allow students to further develop basic suturing proficiency using self-directed learning.

Authorship Declaration

I wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this work and there has been no financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

I confirm that Generative Artificial Intelligence tools were not used in this Thesis.

I confirm that the Thesis has been read and approved by her named author and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for authorship but are not listed.

I confirm that I have given due consideration to the protection of intellectual property associated with this Thesis and there are no impediments to publication, including the timing of publication, with respect to intellectual property. In so doing, I confirm that I have knowledge of the regulations of my institution concerning intellectual property.

24/08/2025

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Contents

Abstract	i
Authorship Declaration	iii
Acknowledgments	iv
Acronyms	xv
Nomenclature	xvii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 Problem Statement	2
1.3 Potential Impact	3
1.4 Thesis Outline	3
2 Technical and Related Background	5
2.1 Defining the Problem	5
2.2 Suture Quality Assessment	6
2.3 Surgical Simulators for Training Purposes	8
2.4 CV Techniques for Surgical Training Purposes	9
2.5 CV Techniques for Suturing Skills Assessment	13

3	Methodology	16
3.1	Overview of the Thesis’s Methodological Design	16
3.2	Key Aspects of the Research Methodological Approach	18
3.2.1	Video Capture Setup	21
3.2.2	CV Model Training and Validation	23
3.2.3	Suture Quality Assessment Metrics	24
3.3	Ethical Considerations	26
3.3.1	Human Participation	26
3.3.2	Data Protection	27
3.3.3	AI Explainability	27
3.3.4	Ethical Approvals/Opinions	28
4	Implementation	30
4.1	SUGAR Lite: A First Step Towards CV-based Suturing Skill Assessment	30
4.1.1	Data Collection and Assembly	31
4.1.2	Suture Quality Metrics	32
4.1.3	CV Software Application and Model Training and Validation .	33
4.1.4	Suture Quality Analysis Through Metrics	34
4.1.5	System Validation	37
4.2	SUGAR: The Novel Automated Surgical sUturing GrAdeR Proof-of- Concept	40
4.2.1	Data Capture	40
4.2.2	Suture Quality Metrics	43
4.2.3	Video Reviews by Surgical Experts	49
4.2.4	Data Collection and Assembly	51
4.2.5	Dataset Creation	53

4.2.6	CV Model Training and Validation	54
4.2.7	Software Development Using Traditional CV Techniques	64
5	Experimental Results	88
5.1	Suture Quality Analysis Through Metrics	88
5.1.1	Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Human-based Input	89
5.1.2	Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suturing Videos	91
5.1.3	Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suture End-Product Images	103
5.2	System Validation	112
5.2.1	Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Human-based Input	113
5.2.2	Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suturing Videos	113
5.2.3	Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suture End-Product Images	123
5.2.4	The Value of Inter-Rater Reliability	131
5.2.5	Overall SUGAR System Validation	133
6	Discussion and Impact	138
7	Conclusions and Future Work	149
A	Ethics-Related Documentation	153
B	SUGAR CV Models Training and Validation	214
C	Poster SUGAR Master’s Thesis	221

List of Figures

3.1	The RCSI's Suturing Station Disassembled	21
3.2	The RCSI's Suturing Station	22
3.3	The RCSI's Suturing Station Recording Setup	23
4.1	SUGAR Lite Grading a Novice's Suture Quality	38
4.2	SUGAR Lite Grading an Expert's Suture Quality	38
4.3	Consent Forms for the Participants in the Suturing Task	41
4.4	Deployment of Suturing Stations at RCSI for the Suturing Task	42
4.5	Research Participant Performing the Suturing Task	43
4.6	Correct Placement of Needle Within the Needle Holder	45
4.7	The Surgeons' Knot (source: RCSI)	47
4.8	Sutures Displaying Incorrect Levels of Tension	48
4.9	SUGAR Video Expert Review Website	49
4.10	SUGAR Video Expert Review Form	50
4.11	Example of Manual Labelling Work Results	54
4.12	YOLOv10 Models Training Results	55
4.13	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 6	56
4.14	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 8	56
4.15	Validation Images Obtained from Trained Models	57
4.16	YOLOv11 Models Training Results	58

4.17 Example of Image of the <i>Instance2</i> Dataset Showcasing Surgical Tools Annotations	59
4.18 Examples of Object Detection by Trained Model 12	59
4.19 Another Example of Object Detection by Trained Model 12	60
4.20 Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 14	63
4.21 Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 16	63
4.22 Validation Image Obtained from the Trained Model 14	63
4.23 Validation Image Obtained from the Trained Model 16	64
4.24 <i>Correct placement of needle within the needle holder</i> Metric by the SUGAR Tool	68
4.25 The Needle Holder's Right and Left Edges And Associated Linear Regression Lines	68
4.26 Representation of the Middle of the Needle Holder	69
4.27 Graphic of the <i>Correct placement of needle within the needle holder</i> Metric by the SUGAR Tool	70
4.28 Graphic of the <i>Insertion of needle at the right angle to skin</i> Metric by the SUGAR Tool	71
4.29 <i>Insertion and exit of needle approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges</i> Metric by the SUGAR Tool	75
4.30 Graphic of the <i>Insertion and exit of needle approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges</i> Metric	75
4.31 Demonstrated Locking of Suture When Performing the Surgeons Knot	78
4.32 Demonstrated Handling of Needle With Fingers	79
4.33 Suture End-Product and its Representation by the SUGAR Tool	81
4.34 <i>All sutures parallel to each other</i> Metric by the SUGAR Tool	82
4.35 <i>All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound</i> Metric by the SUGAR Tool	83
4.36 <i>Suture tension appropriate</i> Metric for Excessive Tension Analysis by the SUGAR Tool	86

4.37	<i>Suture tension appropriate</i> Metric for Insufficient Tension Analysis by the SUGAR Tool	87
5.1	Validation Results of the SUGAR Tool	134
6.1	False Positives Example for the <i>All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound</i> Metric in Image 208773 by the SUGAR Tool	144
6.2	False Negatives Example for the <i>Distance between sutures appropriate</i> and <i>Distance between sutures equal</i> Metrics in Image 210072 by the SUGAR Tool	145
6.3	False Positives Example for the <i>Suture tension appropriate</i> Metric in Image 248992 by the SUGAR Tool	145
6.4	False Negatives Example for the <i>Suture tension appropriate</i> Metric in Image 263779 by the SUGAR Tool	146
B.1	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 1	214
B.2	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 2	215
B.3	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 3	215
B.4	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 4	215
B.5	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 5	216
B.6	Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 7	216
B.7	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 1	216
B.8	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 2	217
B.9	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 5	217
B.10	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 6	217
B.11	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 7	218
B.12	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 8	218
B.13	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 9	218
B.14	Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 10	219

B.15 Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 11	219
B.16 Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 12	219
B.17 Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 13	219
B.18 Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 15	220

List of Tables

4.1	The Five Datasets Used in SUGAR Lite	32
4.2	Model Training and Validation of SUGAR Lite	34
4.3	The Six Publicly Available Datasets Used in SUGAR	53
4.4	Parameters and Results Obtained in YOLOv10 Models Training . . .	55
4.5	Parameters and Results Obtained in YOLOv11 Models Training . . .	58
4.6	Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM14 with YOLOv11 Models with Bounding Boxes	61
4.7	Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM14 with YOLOv11 Models with Masks.	61
4.8	Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM16 with YOLOv11 Models with Bounding Boxes	62
4.9	Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM16 with YOLOv11 Models with Masks	62
5.1	Results Obtained for the <i>Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure)</i> Metric	89
5.2	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Correct placement of needle within the needle holder</i> Metric	91
5.3	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Insertion of needle at right angle to the skin</i> Metric	93
5.4	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Needle inserted and removed using supination</i> Metric	94

5.5	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges</i> Metric	96
5.6	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>One pass of needle per suture insertion</i> Metric	98
5.7	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeons knot</i> Metric	100
5.8	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Handled needle with forceps, not fingers</i> Metric	101
5.9	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>All sutures parallel to each other</i> Metric	103
5.10	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>All suture placement equidistant from the edge of the wound</i> Metric	105
5.11	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Distance between sutures appropriate</i> Metric	107
5.12	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Distance between sutures equal</i> Metric	109
5.13	Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the <i>Suture tension appropriate</i> Metric	111
5.14	Validation Results for the <i>Correct placement of needle within the needle holder</i> Metric	113
5.15	Validation Results for the <i>Insertion of needle at right angle to the skin</i> Metric	115
5.16	Validation Results for the <i>Needle inserted and removed using supination</i> Metric	116
5.17	Validation Results for the <i>Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges</i> Metric	118
5.18	Validation Results for the <i>One pass of needle per suture insertion</i> Metric	119
5.19	Validation Results for the <i>Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeons knot</i> Metric	120
5.20	Validation Results for the <i>Handled needle with forceps, not fingers</i> Metric	122

5.21	Validation Results for the <i>All sutures parallel to each other</i> Metric . . .	123
5.22	Validation Results for the <i>All suture placement equidistant from the edge of the wound</i> Metric	125
5.23	Validation Results for the <i>Distance between sutures appropriate</i> Metric	127
5.24	Validation Results for the <i>Distance between sutures equal</i> Metric . . .	128
5.25	Validation Results for the <i>Suture tension appropriate</i> Metric	130
5.26	Inter-Rater Reliability (IRR) Among RCSI Surgical Experts' Assessments	132
5.27	Validation Results of the SUGAR Tool	134

Acronyms

AI Artificial Intelligence.

AI HLEG High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence.

CNN Convolutional Neural Network.

CST Core Surgical Training.

CV Computer Vision.

DL Deep Learning.

DPIA Data Protection Impact Assessment.

ERB Ethics Research Board.

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation.

GOALS Global Operative Assessment of Laparoscopic Skills.

GRS Global Rating Scale.

HD High Definition.

HMM Hidden Markov Models.

ID IDentification.

IRR Inter-Rater Reliability.

ML Machine Learning.

MU Maynooth University.

OSATS Objective Structured Assessment of Technical Skills.

PIL Participant Information Leaflet.

RCSI Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland.

REC Research Ethics Committee.

RGB Red, Green and Blue.

SDGs Sustainable Development Goals.

sRGB Standard Red, Green and Blue.

SUGAR Surgical sUturing GrAdeR.

UN United Nations.

XAI eXplainable Artificial Intelligence.

YOLO You Only Look Once.

Nomenclature

- Acc* Accuracy: number of correct assessments over the total number of assessments.
- AP* Average Precision: computes the area under the precision-recall curve, providing a single value that encapsulates the model's precision and recall performance.
- Box* Box(P, R, mAP50, mAP50-95): this metric provides insights into the model's performance in detecting objects.
- F1* F1 Score: harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced assessment of a model's performance while considering both false positives and false negatives.
- IoU* Intersection over Union: measure that quantifies the overlap between a predicted bounding box and a ground truth bounding box. It plays a fundamental role in evaluating the accuracy of object localization.
- IRR* Inter-Rater Reliability: indicates the degree of agreement among independent evaluators who assess or grade the same object, signaling consistency and objectivity in their evaluations.
- mAP* Mean Average Precision: mAP extends the concept of AP by calculating the average AP values across multiple object classes. This is useful in multi-class object detection scenarios to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance.
- mAP50* mean Average Precision 50: calculated at an IoU threshold of 0.50. It's a measure of the model's accuracy considering only the "easy" detections.
- mAP50 – 95* mean Average Precision 50-95: average of the mean average precision calculated at varying IoU thresholds, ranging from 0.50 to 0.95. It gives a comprehensive view of the model's performance across different levels of detection difficulty.

Mask Masks(P, R, mAP50, mAP50-95): this metric provides insights into the model's performance in detecting objects.

P Precision: proportion of true positives among all positive predictions, assessing the model's capability to avoid false positives.

R Recall: proportion of true positives among all actual positives, measuring the model's ability to detect all instances of a class.

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter introduces key aspects of the SUGAR Surgical Suturing Grader Master's Thesis: the motivation driving the exploration of CV technologies and the development of a Proof-of-Concept for the novel SUGAR automated suturing skills assessment and grading tool, the problem statement that establishes the context of the research, clearly identifying the existing issue that the study addresses, and a short reference to the research's potential impact. The chapter is complete with the description of the Thesis's structure.

1.1 Motivation

Suturing is a fundamental surgical skill required in a variety of operations and, as such, surgical trainees' skills are meticulously evaluated by surgical educators. Currently, this evaluation is based on subjective rating scales that often lack precision and reproducibility [1], and has been proven to be resource intensive, time-consuming and expensive [2]. Also, there is the potential for subjectivity and bias. Therefore, a need for objective methods has motivated the development of technology-based approaches, determining a precise quantification of metrics that define best surgical practices factors, capable of encapsulating potential value to certification organisations, credentials committees and surgical educators, as well as of providing surgeons in training with objective feedback [1]. In fact, several studies highlight that diverse metrics correlate with surgeon experience, learning curve progression, and patient outcome measures and can be calculated and used to distinguish surgeon skill levels [3].

Based on those metrics, Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods, such as Computer

Vision (CV), Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL), have been developed: CV algorithms excel in analysing surgical videos to automatically assess suturing techniques, ML techniques have proven their worth in determining a surgeon's level of expertise, and DL methods are being employed to predict the level of surgical expertise directly based on (kinematic or video) data, without intermediate feature calculation [2, 4]. When compared with manual video-based assessment, these AI-based methods require less instructor-hours and are considered faster, more reproducible, and potentially less subjective [5]. In addition, the assessment system is always available for training purposes.

In this context, this Master's Thesis aims to develop a Proof-of-Concept for a novel video-based approach for observing the continuous hand movements of surgical trainees and of expert trainers and the movements of surgical tools with a camera, and then applying a combination of advanced and traditional CV techniques to model and evaluate the surgical suturing skills demonstrated in the observation. Since the SUGAR grader system is based on the video data analysis of hands' and surgical tools' movements rather than sensor-based data, it can be extended to provide real-time feedback to surgical interns doing surgical exercises or even to surgeons while performing an actual surgery [6].

1.2 Problem Statement

Assessing suturing skills is a particular challenge in the evaluation and verification of surgical skills in surgical trainees' education because it is a resource- and time-intensive task, involving some degree of subjectivity and bias. Thus, there is the need for an assessment process of suturing technical skills that is automated, reliable, accurate and useful.

Given the need for objective methods in the evaluation of surgical suturing skills, this Thesis aims to establish a Proof-of-Concept for a novel low-cost CV-based video tool (SUGAR), capable of assessing and grading surgical suturing skills. Following the definition of relevant performance criteria for common surgical suturing tasks, an expert system is developed to measure the similarity of surgical trainees' and surgical trainers' performance with the defined criteria, thus contributing to an objective and reliable grading process. In this context, several models are thoroughly analysed and compared in order to obtain the most promising and effective CV models for this Proof-of-Concept, bringing forth a tool with high levels of accuracy and recall. Also, cost and computation time aspects are considered, given the growing preference for

low-cost real-time educational and training systems.

1.3 Potential Impact

The pressing need for better and objective grading systems in the assessment of surgical suturing skills within surgical training and educational programmes and the increasing relevance of AI-based technologies to advance training and educational tools, including those applicable to surgical training and assessment, are significant drivers to the impact of the work developed in this Thesis.

It is expected that the need for fully trained surgeons and for highly competent surgical trainers will continue to rise worldwide for the next decades, as the shortage of healthcare professionals takes on a global scale. This expectation places emphasis on surgical training programmes, so that they may significantly reduce the time taken to train surgeons, while designing more streamlined, efficient and evidence-based surgical training and continuing to produce highly skilled surgeon professionals.

Abundant scientific evidence has emerged on the feasibility of using AI-powered technologies to automate the assessment of surgical skills, namely using video imagery analysis for relevant feedback and objective scoring. A more automated approach to suturing training is deemed to facilitate a larger number of surgical trainees to be trained, with the right set of highly qualified surgical skills and competences that ultimately contribute to greater patient safety (a direct relationship has been established between surgical performance and clinical outcomes, such as hospital readmission and complication rates [7]), a highly positive societal impact.

1.4 Thesis Outline

The long-term goal of this Thesis's work is to advance automated approaches to suturing training through the use of AI, particularly CV and DL, offering real-time performance tracking, personalised feedback, and enhanced skill retention. The successful achievement of a Proof-of-Concept for an automated suturing skills grading tool will help cement innovative AI-enabled training approaches as a new paradigm in the objective assessment of suturing skills and performance, improving skill acquisition and long-term proficiency.

This Thesis is organised in the following chapters:

- Chapter 1: **Introduction** - This chapter gives an overview of this work and highlights the potential contributions of this Thesis.
- Chapter 2: **Technical and Related Background** - This chapter provides an overview of existing literature and relevant research on topics of suture quality assessment. It takes the reader through the advances in surgical training simulators and the use of CV and DL techniques for the purposes of surgical training and suturing skills assessment.
- Chapter 3: **Methodology** - This chapter describes the methods used in this Thesis to achieve the defined goal and address the stated problem. The logic behind the work is explained, including the generation of datasets and the CV models' training, testing and validation procedures. A dedicated emphasis is also given to the Thesis's ethics dimension.
- Chapter 4: **Implementation** - This chapter addresses the development of the proposed Proof-of-Concept, as it details the performed work concerning the generation of datasets, the training, testing and validation of the CV model detecting the suturing tools, the identification of relevant metrics to assess the quality of suturing skills and the development of a new expert system, hard-coded into the CV-enabled SUGAR suturing grading system as a Proof-of-Concept.
- Chapter 5: **Experimental Results** - This chapter documents the validation of the CV-based SUGAR grading tool Proof-of-Concept, and its evaluation by comparison with real surgical suturing reviews performed by three surgical experts. A specific section is dedicated to the value of the *Inter-Rater Reliability* indicator.
- Chapter 6: **Discussion and Impact** - This chapter elaborates on the Proof-of-Concept's achieved results, explaining the main outcomes of the performed work. Additional insight is given with respect to the prospective impact that may be generated through the adoption of CV-based surgical suturing grading systems.
- Chapter 7: **Conclusions and Future Work** - This chapter concludes the Thesis's work and provides guidance for possible future research directions to advance the developed Proof-of-Concept, as well as to further improve the state-of-the-art of AI-based assessment of surgical suturing skills and competences.

Chapter 2

Technical and Related Background

This chapter summarises the technical and related background of the Master's Thesis, which serves as the theoretical framework for the performed research, allowing for a better understanding of the different concepts, theories and methodologies applied to the use of AI-based technologies in the advancement of the process and tools for training suturing skills and competences.

2.1 Defining the Problem

Medical education aims to provide students with basic professional skills and competences, having patient safety as the top priority to consider. Suturing is a fundamental surgical skill required in a variety of operations that all medical surgical trainees learn during their education. The complicated nature of this surgical task necessitates a development of high level of expertise, dexterity and coordination, which can only be obtained by prolonged training and practice. Particularly, surgical skills are important due to the direct relationship between surgical performance and clinical outcomes, such as hospital readmission and complication rates and to the assumption that the proficiency of the operating surgeon is an important factor underlying variation in clinical outcomes [7]. As a result, surgical trainees' skills are meticulously evaluated by surgical educators (expert evaluation is the gold standard), in what is deemed quite a burdensome process for experienced surgeons, particularly under increasing workload and difficult conditions that draw them away from clinical responsibilities [8, 9].

Traditionally, surgical suturing skills evaluation involves observer-generated task-specific checklists and global rating scales, non-standardised methods that, depending

on the expert surgeon’s preferences and style, have been proven to lack precision, quantitative data and reproducibility [1, 10, 11], while being highly subjective and prone to bias [2, 12].

Therefore, a need for objective methods has motivated the development of technology-based approaches to surgical training, capable of determining precise quantification of metrics to define best surgical practices factors with potential value to providing surgeons in training with objective feedback [1, 9]. Objective methods for surgical training involve using quantifiable metrics to assess and improve surgical skills, moving beyond subjective evaluations. These methods include tracking tool movements, measuring task completion time, and utilising simulation-based training with objective feedback, as well as applying AI algorithms to analyse surgical performance. Tracking the movements of a surgeon’s hand and of surgical instruments is a critical step towards automating the measurement of a surgeon’s technical skills [3]. In fact, tool trajectory-based metrics have been shown to correlate with surgeon experience [10], learning curve progression [11], and patient outcome measures [12], and can be calculated and used to distinguish surgeon skill levels [3].

Moreover, ML methods [9, 13] capable of determining a surgeon’s level of expertise based on relevant metrics have been developed, as well as DL techniques [14, 15] to assist in predicting the level of surgical expertise directly based on the (kinematic or video) data, without intermediate feature calculation. When compared with manual video-based assessment, these AI-based methods require less instructor-hours, and are considered faster, more reproducible, and potentially less subjective. In addition, the AI-enabled assessment system is always available for training purposes.

Leveraging on relevant state-of-the-art knowledge, this Master’s Thesis aims to develop a Proof-of-Concept for a novel CV-based tool capable of assessing and grading surgical suturing skills and competences, supporting medical training and education purposes.

2.2 Suture Quality Assessment

Suture quality assessment involves evaluating various characteristics of sutures and their performance in surgical procedures, in which key aspects include tensile strength, knot security, tissue reaction, and handling properties. The assessments can be performed using objective metrics, such as measuring the gap between the laceration and insertion points, analysing suture placement or timing the operation’s

duration; or subjective assessments that often use checklists and rating scales to evaluate technique and overall performance.

Currently, in surgical education, the competency of a resident surgeon to perform a specific suturing task is generally based on subjective rather than objective assessments. The traditional subjective assessment of surgical skills' proficiency is therefore guided by relevant hand movements of the surgeon and translated to several scales, with the most common being the Objective Structured Assessment of Technical Skills (OSATS) and the Global Rating Scale (GRS). Both these scales aim to provide a structured and objective evaluation of surgical techniques and are mostly used in surgical training. Other scales, such as the Zwisch scale and the Dreyfus scale, focus on faculty guidance and resident surgical autonomy and independence.

In the late Nineties, Martin *et al.* developed a valid and reliable tool to assess surgical skills, known as the Objective Structured Assessment of Technical Skills (OSATS) [16]. This global rating scale is a multi-station performance-based examination of surgical skills, allowing to test and measure the trainees' surgical skills performing an open wound suture on a bench model [17]. Eight 15-minute stations are used for bench model simulations of seven surgical procedures appropriate to general surgery: the excision of a skin lesion, the insertion of a T-tube, abdominal wall closure, hand-sewn bowel anastomosis, stapled bowel anastomosis, control of inferior vena cava haemorrhage, pyloroplasty, and tracheostomy. Using a 5-level scale, seven metrics allow to evaluate the skills of surgical trainees: Respect for Tissue, Time and Motion, Instrument Handling, Knowledge of Instruments, Flow of Operation, Use of Assistants and Knowledge of Specific Procedure. The examiners mark the trainees' performance using two evaluation tools, an operation-specific checklist and a global rating scale to assess performance on simulated surgical procedures, helping to ensure competency in essential surgical skills, including suturing [17, 18].

Although the OSATS is considered to be a validated tool for global assessment of operative competence, there was no equivalent for laparoscopic surgery. As laparoscopic surgery is the standard for an increasing list of procedures, there was a need for a valid and reliable assessment tool that could address the specific requirements of laparoscopic surgery. To evaluate these skills, in 2005, Vassiliou *et al.* developed the Global Operative Assessment of Laparoscopic Skills (GOALS), a non-procedure-specific assessment tool that could be applied to any procedure in minimally invasive surgery [19]. The GOALS scale uses a five-point Likert scale to evaluate a surgeon's depth perception, bimanual dexterity, efficiency, and tissue handling [19], and it is often used as a measure for which to compare other methods of surgeon technical skill classification [20, 21].

The OSATS assessment method has now been adopted by many academic centres to measure operative performance in the operating theatre and provide feedback to trainees, but its application in surgical training programmes remains limited due to the need of surgical instruments and expert trainers' availability [22]. Importantly, both the OSATS and the GOALS methods include the quality assessment of sutures in variables associated with the sutures' size, density, symmetry and orientation.

Since the evidence of the association between technical surgical skills and patient outcomes is growing, the surgical community as well as healthcare organisations are seeking solutions to objectively measure a surgeon's competences and avoid negative impact of variation and learning curves. Objective competence assessment is thus needed to improve the quality of surgery, which in turn will lead to better performance-adjusted surgical education, accommodating the certification of surgeons after successful training and helping to obtain robust data in clinical trials investigating new surgical techniques.

2.3 Surgical Simulators for Training Purposes

As surgical outcomes may be enhanced through skill improvement training, simulation-based training and assessment have received special attention in recent years, particularly when involving sensor-enabled simulations and surgical simulators that are capable of simulating an aspect of a surgical procedure and of assessing and/or training the surgical trainee's skill on a given task. In addition, surgical simulators for training have the benefit of not involving risks and patient discomfort [1, 5].

As a result, many and diverse specialised systems with the ability to measure surgical proficiency have been proposed. Examples of such systems are the BLUE-DRAGON system, the MISTVR system, the LapSim, the ProMIS system, the ROVIMAS system, the WKS system, the Wasada Bioinstrumentation (WB) system, the BSN technology, and the Immersion Simulators, among others [5]. Many of these systems use time as a metric for measurement of surgical proficiency; other measures of proficiency include the kinematics of the laparoscopic tools (BLUE-DRAGON [23, 24, 25], ROVIMAS [11]) and the smoothness of the movements (ProMIS). The WKS system [26, 27, 28] measures force and movement of the dummy skin in suture/ligature training system to evaluate performance, whereas the BSN technology [29] uses wireless sensor glove and body sensor network to enable hand gesture data to be captured and analysed with Hidden Markov Models (HMM) for surgical skill assessment. The WB system [30] uses a series of sensors to track head, arm and hand movement and as well as

several physiological parameters to analyse the surgeon's performance. However, surgical simulators and, particularly, the integration of sensors, typically interfere with surgical execution, including the need for sterile equipment, and require a complex and expensive setup [1] that obstacle their broad deployment.

Notwithstanding, multiple studies have demonstrated that kinematic data can provide valuable information in the assessment of surgical skill [31]. Based on kinematic data, different skill-evaluation metrics are calculated, such as procedure time, path length, number of hand movements, and working volume [2, 32]. In parallel, different metrics for skill assessment may be identified in literature, usually classified as force-based metrics [33], motion-based metrics [9, 34] and image-based metrics [2, 6, 35, 36]. It is noted that hand and/or surgical tool motion obtained via sensor-based kinematic data have also been examined to extract motion-based metrics, with the ability to distinguish the surgeon's skill level [33, 37, 38, 39, 40].

2.4 CV Techniques for Surgical Training Purposes

In the face of the barriers to the effective deployment of surgical simulators for training, new avenues were procured to improve the objective assessment of surgical skills.

Compared with manual assessments, AI-based approaches, including CV, ML and DL methods, require less trainer-hours and are faster, more reproducible, potentially less subjective, and always available for training purposes [5]. This flexibility resulted in numerous successful applications in surgical education [41], with the work being developed for surgical instrument tracking, workflow analysis, the identification and identification of critical anatomical structures, and basic surgical skills, such as suturing and knot-tying [42, 43, 44, 45, 46], as the basis to estimate and/or predict surgical quality [47, 48].

Several studies have addressed AI-powered methods capable of automating the evaluation of technical skills based on a surgeon's movement patterns [49], highlighting the potential to improve surgical practice by providing objective, reproducible and scalable feedback to surgical trainees [3]. Metrics of interest, such as path length, velocity, acceleration, turning angle, curvature, and tortuosity, can be calculated and used to distinguish the surgeons' skill levels [50]. Also motion smoothness metrics, such as jerk, have been proven to point to a lack of mastery of a task, indicating a surgeon's progression along the learning curve [51]. Estimating instrument trajectories

from video feed using image-based tracking does unlock the ability to further explore the automated assessment of technical surgical skills, as no extra sensors or robotic systems' access are needed. Metrics may then be calculated directly from the image-based tracking results [52, 53, 54, 55, 56], notwithstanding the variations in the surgical scene leading to missed detections [2].

In particular, the use of CV-enabled techniques has been explored to generate tool position data and empower the calculation of motion metrics based on surgical videos, without relying on data outputs of a specific surgical device. These techniques have demonstrated the capacity to deliver kinematic data by using bounding boxes of object detection [52] or landmark detection [57] on hands or tool tips. As a result, a surgeon's technical skills could be evaluated during video review, performed by expert surgical trainers, using rating scales that assign values to specific characteristics exhibited by the surgeon's movements. As the CV-based analysis of surgical movements is based on the video data analysis of hand and surgical tool movements rather than sensor-based data, it can easily be extended to provide real-time feedback to surgical trainees while doing surgical exercise or to surgeons while performing an actual surgery [6]. In addition, video-based training does relieve some of the burden and scheduling issues associated with traditional surgical skill evaluation, and maintaining equivalent learning outcomes [5, 58, 59].

Although these CV-based methods have proven to be quite useful, there is still room for improvement by incorporating new data and newer and simpler methods. The use of ML and DL techniques have thus been explored to assess the surgical skills of medical trainees and provide relevant and timely feedback for medical skills training, involving metrics such as the number of stitches, the stitch length, the total bite size, and the stitch orientation [6, 60, 61, 62, 63]. Early ML techniques have been developed to determine the surgeon's level of expertise based on metrics such as procedure time, path length, number of hand movements, and working volume [64, 13] and to identify various stages of surgery: adaptive Support Vector Machines, Decision Tree analysis and HMMs have shown effectiveness in surgical applications, modelling temporal dynamics for surgical phase detection and cancelling hand tremors in real-time operations. However, these methods' reliance on high-quality training data, their static nature and the high susceptibility to variations in surgical equipment and settings have significantly limit their generalised application [65, 66].

Similarly, DL techniques have been explored for the automatic analysis of surgical video data [14, 15] and the prediction of the level of surgical expertise directly based on the (kinematic or video) data, without intermediate feature calculation [67, 68]. DL and deep transfer learning are thus important AI techniques in data science used

in statistical and predictive modelling [69, 70, 71, 72]. A type of DL architecture, CNNs are artificial neural networks primarily used for analysing visual data, namely images and videos, that exhibit the capability to process data with spatial or temporal relationships, being highly successful in a variety of real-world applications.

While CNNs are similar to other neural networks, they incorporate several convolutional layers, which adds an additional level of complexity. A CNN network consists of four main components: the input layer, the convolutional layer, the pooling layer, and the fully connected layer. A crucial part of a CNN is the layer clustering, which reduces the dimensionality of the size of convolved features as well as the computational power required for image processing. Pooling is divided into two categories, with max pooling returning the maximum value of the image section and average pooling returning the average value. The fully connected layer, or dense layer, receives the vectorized image feed to extract image classification features. The sigmoid function makes predictions based on previously extracted image properties from earlier levels. Data augmentation techniques, such as rotation, zooming, cropping, and filtering, can be used to increase the number of data and generate new data from existing datasets [73, 74, 75, 76], with the clear purpose of strengthening the deep neural network through diversification [73]. Deep transfer learning, or learning from related tasks, has gained attention recently [77, 78, 79]. It is a common technique for using deep CNNs on small datasets, which involves using the classifier layer from a pretrained CNN and fine-tuning it on a target dataset [80], thus reducing training demands.

Currently, CNN models excel at automatically learning and extracting features from visual data, making them well-suited for tasks such as image classification, object detection, and image segmentation [81, 82, 83, 84]. As a result, DL models, in particular CNNs, have become the dominant approach in CV. Specifically, object detection algorithms are divided into two main groups: two-stage algorithms and one-stage algorithms. In the two-stage algorithms, the first stage extracts regions of interest, namely those regions where the objects are expected to be found. The second stage involves classifying the objects and locating their bounding boxes [2]. Two-stage algorithms, such as Faster R-CNN [85] and Mask R-CNN [86], are characterised by high accuracy rates and long run time, a reason for their lack of appropriateness for real-time applications. In contrast, the one-stage object detection algorithms do not require intermediate steps, as they frame the object detection as a single regression for both identifying bounding boxes and classifying them in one stage. These algorithms are less accurate but, because they work much faster than the two-stage algorithms, they are more suitable for real-time applications. This

group includes the SSD algorithm [87], RetinaNet [88] and all versions of You Only Look Once (YOLO) [89, 90, 91].

Today, the one-stage object detection algorithms, namely the YOLO algorithms [23], are deemed highly effective to process images, namely in the surgical tool detection domain [24]. YOLO is a CNN, consisting of several layers and using multiple detection heads to provide detection at diverse image scales, with each head presenting four convolutional layers and one YOLO prediction layer. YOLO uses non-maximum suppression to address the problem of multiple detections of the same object [2]. More recently, YOLO has played a significant role in surgical skill assessment by enabling automated, real-time tracking of surgical instruments and hands within video recordings. This capability allows for the extraction of valuable metrics like time, path length, and hand movements, which are then used to evaluate surgical proficiency. By leveraging YOLO's object detection capabilities, researchers can move beyond manual assessments and develop objective, data-driven methods for evaluating surgical skill [92, 93].

As YOLO algorithms are deemed highly effective to process imagery [36, 37], they are often chosen over traditional CNN-based object detection models in medical settings for their real-time processing capabilities, high accuracy and efficiency. While CNNs capture object details at multiple scales, improving object detection, YOLO's unified detection framework provides speed advantage, balances accuracy and speed, understands the global context of images and operates efficiently on limited resources, suitable for mobile and edge devices. Although YOLO requires a high volume of quality data and significant computational power, it is manageable with scalable cloud computing that adjusts to demand [94].

Hence, YOLOs emerged as the paradigm of real-time object detection owing to their effective balance between computational cost and detection performance. Still, given that the design of YOLO components lack thorough inspection, resulting in noticeable computational redundancy and limited model capability, Wang *et al.* optimised the efficiency and accuracy of various YOLO components, reducing computational overhead and enhancing capability. The outcome was a new generation of YOLO series for real-time end-to-end object detection, dubbed YOLOv10, capable of achieving state-of-the-art performance and efficiency across various model scales [95]. Currently, one of the latest YOLO iterations, the YOLOv11, is designed to excel in speed and accuracy for object detection tasks, while supporting a range of CV tasks, including object detection, instance segmentation, image classification, and pose estimation. Importantly, it also presents lower memory requirements during training and inference compared to previous models [96].

Further, as a CNN, YOLO autonomously learns spatial hierarchies from images for precise and efficient analysis, an approach widely used in medical imaging applications, including laparoscopy, endoscopy, and cataract surgery. Nevertheless, it requires support with phase identification during surgical procedures due to the visual similarities and absence of temporal data [97]. To overcome this, studies have incorporated temporal features to evaluate surgical skills. For example, Funke *et al.* used I3D ConvNets for automatic skill evaluation based solely on video data, achieving high classification accuracies without the need for additional hardware. By combining spatiotemporal feature extraction, these methods achieved impressive accuracy in categorising surgical skills [68]. These studies show significant advances in surgical phase detection and skill assessment, by efficiently employing DL models to interpret video data, incorporate temporal dynamics, and investigate multi-task learning to improve performance. However, the focus on high-level phase identification or global skill measures tends to overlook the detailed understanding of procedural nuances associated with the finer sub-phases within suturing tasks [68].

Overall, AI-based surgical performance assessment has the potential to be incorporated into surgical training in order to deliver accurate performance assessment, which is objective, reproducible and not resource-intensive. This technology not only provides surgical trainees with access to regular, consistent and relevant feedback, allowing them to track and progress up their learning curves more rapidly, but also could potentially enable certifying bodies to deem surgical competence or assess how surgeons perform with novel technologies or techniques in the operating room. Notwithstanding the fact that many video-based surgical quality assessment tools have been thoroughly investigated, the validation of these tools continues to remain highly complex due to the diverse nature of surgical procedures, the subjective element of surgical skill assessment, and the challenges in creating comprehensive and standardised datasets [98].

2.5 CV Techniques for Suturing Skills Assessment

Within the surgical applications field, the use of Computer Vision in surgical suturing has also been explored: Iyer *et al.* [99] developed a CV-based application for an automated robot arm for suturing, in which the needle's colour was modified to ensure its detection, an approach non-fitting to real settings, and Wengert *et al.* [100] used CV to track and estimate the pose of a suturing needle in real-time. Further, CV has also been used to extract image-based metrics as a means to quantify surgical

skills [3, 6, 60, 62].

Using CV techniques enables the calculation of metrics based on suture images, without relying on data outputs of a specific surgical device. Several studies have addressed methods to automate the evaluation of suturing skills based on a suture's performance, involving metrics of interest such as bite size (the length of suture across the wound), pitch size (the interval distance between sutures), skewness of angle (the degree to which the sutures' angles are off from being symmetrical), symmetry across the wound (the mirroring of sutures on each side of the wound), suture orientation (the placement of sutures relative to the wound edges), knot location (the distance of the knot relative to the wound) and leftover length [60, 62, 101, 102].

A significant system was developed by Frischknecht *et al.* [60], who developed a CV-based system for continuous sutures that had the user manually trace a line of the wound to enable the system to detect the suture lines automatically and deliver several metrics (number of sutures, total bite size, suture length, suture orientation and suture separation), clearly distinguishing the sutures made by experts from those performed by novices. Overall, these studies highlighted the potential to improve surgical practice by providing objective, reproducible and scalable feedback to surgical trainees [3]. As CV-based analysis of suture performance is based on the image data analysis rather than sensor-based data, it can easily be extended to provide real-time feedback to surgical trainees doing surgical exercise or to surgeons while performing an actual surgery [6].

Concerning relevant CV techniques dedicated to suturing skills, it is also noted the works of Ton *et al.* in the development of a CV algorithm to assess suturing abilities, including the entry and exit times and points of the suture needle and the length of the needle track [103]; of Handelsmann *et al.* that used a combination of CV-based software and fiber optic strain sensors to evaluate suture performance [104]; and of Dosis *et al.* that argued the possibility to conduct an objective assessment of surgical skills using skill-based video analysis systems [39].

In 2023, Mahmud *et al.* used CNN transfer learning to predict the success of suture images in what is the first study to use DL to classify suture images and assess the performance of six different CNN models (*VGG 16*, *VGG 19*, *Xception*, *Inception*, *Mobile Net* and *Dens Net*) [8]. With pre-trained weights for transfer learning, the well-known CNN models were used to classify a dataset containing two classes of images, successful and unsuccessful [105]. In this study, the images were augmented before being processed through the CNN convolutional layer and the CNN architectures were imported directly from the *Keras* and *Tensorflow* libraries

[106, 107, 108] with their trained weights. The performance of the CNN models was assessed using several metrics, including accuracy, specificity, precision, recall, and F1, and the results showed that, in particular, the *Xception* model demonstrated the highest accuracy (95%), precision (96%), recall (95%) and F1 measure (95%), thus suggesting significant effectiveness at correctly identifying and classifying suture images. The findings of this study indicate the potential to significantly improve surgical suturing skills and advance surgical education, while providing surgeons with efficient tools for digitising the surgical training process [8].

More recently, DL-based techniques incorporating kinematic data alongside video features and leveraging Graph Attention Networks have also improved accuracy in automated suturing skill assessment. This approach effectively leverages DL models to process video data, incorporate temporal dynamics, and explore multi-task learning to enhance performance, advancing the understanding of sub-phase coordination and its impact on skill evaluation, offering a novel perspective on automated suturing skill assessment [109, 110].

Despite these advances, many CV- and DL- based models frequently fail to distinguish handling overlapping or between visually similar surgical phases, reducing phase identification accuracy scenarios. This ongoing struggle to account for the variability introduced by different surgical tools equipment and environments reduces these models' precision and severely limits their generalised applicability across various surgical settings [111]. Hence, there is still a gap in the skill assessment of fine-grained sub-phases within suturing tasks, accounting for tool variability, handling overlapping and similar-looking phases. There is a need for a comprehensive CV-based approach that addresses these issues through intelligent spatial-temporal modelling. This study introduces an automated approach for surgical suturing skill assessment, aiming to reduce subjectivity in evaluations and provide personalised feedback for surgical trainees. A combination of advanced and traditional CV techniques is used to bridge the existing gap by intensive labelling of surgeon hands and surgical tools for improved accuracy, surgical sub-phase recognition and objective suturing skill evaluation.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter encompasses the creation of a purposely designed research methodological strategy to maximise the attainment of the Thesis's main goal, ensuring the validity and reliability of the work, while considering ethical principles.

The chapter presents an overview of the Thesis's methodological design and describes key aspects of the research methodology approach, encompassing the adopted data collection methods and the analysis techniques used, as well as the sampling strategy, the ethical considerations and the methodology limitations. It is also mentioned the aspects of the planned methodology that were revisited and adapted to meet changing conditions. Finally, a dedicated section is included to detail all the actions taken to obtain the required ethics approvals from the MU Ethics Research Board (ERB) and from the RCSI Research Ethics Committee (REC).

3.1 Overview of the Thesis's Methodological Design

The primary goal of this Thesis is to create and validate a Proof-of-Concept for a new and highly accurate CV-based tool for assessing and grading surgical suturing skills. Several YOLO CV models are assessed, and their objective values are analysed and compared, namely concerning accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score and computational time. It is noted that the YOLO CNN algorithm is selected for the work's CV model to analyse the images of sutures and the videos of surgical tools movements, due to its unprecedented advances in surgical object detection and instance segmentation. The combination of traditional and advanced CV techniques is part of the methodological approach adopted for this Master's Thesis.

Two datasets are deemed necessary, the first dataset dedicated to the suturing tools' detection and segmentation for the suturing video analysis and the second dataset focused on key suture components' detection and segmentation for the end-product image processing. More than 10000 images in the suturing tools dataset are created by applying manual labelling techniques to the images extracted from the suturing videos captured during the RCSI CST Bootcamp 2025. The suture components dataset results from the application of data augmentation techniques on the Noraset *et al.*'s dataset. Both datasets train the YOLO models to reliably detect and segment suturing tools and key suture components, with a success criteria of a precision of at least 90% and a recall factor of at least 85%.

This model is then applied to a dataset of at least 25 high-definition (HD) videos of surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers performing surgical suturing and at least 25 suture end-product images to reliably detect and identify the surgical tools' movements and the sutures' visual features, based on relevant suture quality metrics that are hard-coded into the model, following traditional CV techniques, and calculated.

The option for a traditional CV-based approach here-in is primarily determined by the need to meet a required level of AI explainability that enables the easy understanding and interpretation of the developed work. Also, it is acknowledged that there are still certain fields of CV where DL techniques have yet to consolidate significant development, such as 3D vision [112]. In addition, the traditional CV approach makes use of a less computationally heavy model that significantly reduces computation time and facilitates the delivery of a resource-efficient and cost-effective solution.

Finally, the accuracy and reliability of the SUGAR grader tool is the object of a thorough validation effort, involving first the analysis of the results of the automated surgical suturing skill grading system involving thirteen suture quality metrics, and then a comprehensive comparative analysis between the results of the novel automated surgical suturing skill grading system and the results delivered by the traditional human-based surgical suturing skill grading system (reviews performed by three RCSI surgical experts). The success criteria for the novel SUGAR Proof-of-Concept are to exhibit at least 70% precision in assessing surgical suturing skills, with a recall factor of at least 60%. This validation effort also helps to determine the feasibility of adopting a CV-based approach for an automated suturing skills assessment grading system.

The Proof-of-Concept developed in this Master's Thesis allows to demonstrate the

feasibility of applying a CV-based approach to the automated assessment of surgical suturing skills and competences. As a preliminary step towards an early validation of the SUGAR grader system's practical implementation, this work focuses on the core functionality of the automated suturing skills assessment tool, while also providing evidence to support the real potential and impact of the proposed approach for an objective, reproducible, and cost-effective method to evaluate surgical suturing skills, eventually replacing traditional subjective assessments.

3.2 Key Aspects of the Research Methodological Approach

As mentioned in section 1.2, this Thesis addresses the need for an objective, reproducible, and cost-effective method to evaluate surgical suturing skills, replacing traditional subjective assessments. It proposes to explore AI-based approaches to automated suturing skills assessment and develop and validate a Proof-of-Concept for a novel CV-based suturing skills grading system, the SUGAR tool.

In order to attain its goal, the research approach highlighted the importance of establishing a collaboration with relevant stakeholders, not only knowledgeable of the medical education landscape, but particularly proficient in the assessment of surgical suturing skills and highly motivated to innovate the traditional assessment methods. The RCSI presented the ideal profile to meet the requirements of the research approach: RCSI is the national professional training body for surgery in Ireland, being a world leading international health sciences university, at the forefront of healthcare education and research since 1784. A collaborative agreement was therefore reached for their involvement in the Thesis's work, as sources of valuable technical know-how, expertise and insight on suturing, on the focal points in surgical suturing tasks, on suture quality metrics and on the assessment and grading of surgeons' suturing skills. Also, the RCSI facilitated access to eligible human participants (surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers) to perform the suturing task to be recorded in video. As a result, this Thesis required the combined employment of quantitative methods, addressing large datasets to perform data analysis, and qualitative approaches, using interviews and observation to obtain an in-depth understanding of the RCSI experts' experience and perspective. In fact, the data collection methodology encompassed a set of unstructured interviews or discussions with different RCSI's expert surgical trainers, helping to build an insightful framework on the specificities of suturing skills assessment and grading,

particularly with respect to the relevant metrics to be considered for the validation of the SUGAR suturing skills assessment and grading tool.

With respect to data analysis methods, and considering the Thesis's scope, the research methodological design combined the application of traditional and advanced CV techniques to develop the novel SUGAR automated surgical suturing skill grading tool, in order for it to have a reliable and accurate object detection capability, and to integrate and calculate relevant suture quality metrics. In this context, CV is an AI field focused on enabling computers to identify and process visual inputs. For this Thesis, CNNs, specifically the YOLO algorithms [89, 90, 91] were identified as particularly well-suited for image and video processing (they can identify patterns and features within visual data and reliably track hands' and surgical tools' trajectories). In fact, when fast and accurate object detection is required, the one-stage YOLO algorithms are considered one of the most prominent object detection algorithms.

The statistical approach for the Thesis involved the assessment of the performance of the object classification algorithms and of the sutures' quality. The metrics for the object classification algorithms were accuracy (overall correctness by dividing the total number of correct predictions by the total number of predictions), precision (accuracy of positive predictions), recall (ability to identify all positive cases) and the F1 score (balances precision and recall), whereas the metrics for suture quality were based on prevailing surgical skills assessment scales, such as the OSATS scale [16]. It was also considered the importance of including any assessment scales or methods used by the RCSI Department of Surgical Affairs when evaluating the skills and competences of their surgical trainees.

Finally, and similarly to the work performed by the Fathollahi *et al.*'s study [3], a comprehensive comparative analysis of the novel SUGAR tool's results with the results produced by the traditional human-based surgical suturing skill grading system was selected to complete the Thesis's validation approach, and extract meaningful conclusions not only about the performance of the developed SUGAR tool, but also about the feasibility of applying CV methods to automate surgical suturing quality assessment and grading.

Another element of the Thesis's research methodological design was the sampling strategy. Literature references, namely the work performed by Sundhagen H., *et al.* [113] and by Ahmed K., *et al.* [114] helped to determine that 25 high-definition suturing videos suffice to validate the SUGAR System as a Proof-of-Concept. The capture of these 25 videos to validate the system's model would involve at least 15 participants, 12 Year 1 surgical trainees from the national surgical training

programme and 3 expert surgical trainers of the RCSI. Although reduced, this number of participants was deemed adequate to ensure that 25 videos would be captured, while also trying to anticipate possible availability issues from recruited surgeons. Importantly, the rationale for the sampling balanced the need for sufficient data with practical considerations, such as time and ethical concerns, while considering the conclusions that studies involving 15 participants are justified in qualitative research and when dealing with specific populations or conditions where larger samples are difficult or impractical to obtain [115].

Concerning ethics, the Thesis’s research methodological design recognised the need to address the specifics of human participation (the informed consent, the confidentiality and data protection), but also the relevance of AI explainability in surgical applications. The implementation of the Thesis’s ethical considerations is detailed in section 3.3.

Finally, it was also acknowledged the inherent limitations of the proposed methodological research design, namely the time constraints for implementing the proposed work and the need to obtain ethical approvals from the ethics committees of MU and of the RCSI, which could potentially be a very lengthy and time-consuming process. On methodological limitations, it was also recognised that, although unavoidable, the evaluation to be conducted by the RCSI expert surgical trainers using their traditional human-based method entailed an inevitable subjective analysis, which would affect the validation approach. Further, it was acknowledged the potential constraint to the proposed work derived from the inherent technical limitations of CV and DL models, such as the difficulty to detect objects in overlap, the failure in distinguishing visually similar surgical phases, the difficulty to generalise, the need for high volumes of data and highly intensive computational resources, and the “black box” problem (inherent difficulty to explain the algorithms’ learning and analysis processes) [111].

Aside from the above-mentioned general aspects, specific features in the Thesis’s research approach and methods were deemed as pivotal to ensure the attainment of the Thesis’s goals, always safeguarding the validity and reliability of the overall research results. These were the Video Capture Setup (data collection), the CV Model Training and Validation (YOLO models training) and the Suture Quality Assessment Metrics (model validation).

3.2.1 Video Capture Setup

On June 5th, 2025, at a meeting held to plan the start of the video capturing activities, Donncha Ryan highlighted the interest of RCSI to have their new suturing station used, tested and validated in this project. The suturing station had been purposely designed and built by Professor Oscar Traynor and Donncha Ryan for the surgical suturing skills assessment of surgical trainees and would fit well with the video recording activity.

Figure 3.1: The RCSI's Suturing Station Disassembled

As shown in Figure 3.1, the suturing station setup consists of a solid 3D-printed base connected with two protrusions, one that holds the camera and the other that features a small lamp. The camera is a Microsoft Modern Webcam that can produce up to 1080p 30fps video output with an expansive 78° field of view. The camera was chosen for the video quality produced, despite its closeness to the suturing pad, surgeon's hands and surgical tools. The lamp has several degrees of light intensity and a large range of colour from a warm yellow undertone to a cold blue undertone.

Figure 3.2: The RCSI's Suturing Station

As the station setup was adequately aligned with the proposed video recording activity, and ultimately with the validation of an automated suturing skill assessment and grading tool using RCSI suture quality metrics, a decision is made to use three of the RCSI's suturing stations to capture the suturing videos.

Originally, it was thought to use the suturing station setup sideways, with the light and webcam capturing the suturing task from the side, at a downward angle. However, after a meeting with Dr. Dara O'Keeffe and Dr. Eoghan Burke from the RCSI, it was decided to use the setup vertically, with the camera capturing the suturing task from the front, at a downward angle, and the light was removed. To ensure proper lighting for the recordings, table lights were provided by the RCSI and attached to the tables near each of the three setups. Each lamp was directly above each setup at the highest setting. This also allowed for the discarding of the converters, which permitted for two cameras and two lights to be connected to one single computer for storing purposes.

In addition, the required surgical suturing equipment to perform the suturing task was kindly provided by the RCSI, comprising a suturing pad with at least one vertical laceration, a needle holder, a toothed forceps, a suture-cutting scissors and 3-0 nylon suture with a reverse-cutting needle. If the voluntary participant ran out of suture, a new one would be provided. At the end of the suturing task, the sutures were cut from the suturing pad and the needle was discarded in a sharps bin.

To record the suturing videos, two computers were used: a MSI Titan 18 HX A14VIG with Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-14900HX (2.20 GHz) processor, 64,0 GB RAM and NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU; and a HP Spectre x360 Convertible 13-aw2xxx with 11th Generation Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1165G7 (2.80 GHz) processor, 16,0 GB RAM and Intel(R) Iris(R) Xe Graphics GPU. Since there are three suturing stations, the MSI Titan computer has one of the webcams associated with the pre-installed Windows Camera application and another webcam associated with the OBS Studio 31.0.3 (64-bit) application. The third webcam was linked to the HP Spectre and

associated with the pre-installed Windows Camera application. All video recordings were obtained with 1080p 30fps video output, as this is the cameras' maximum resolution. The camera associated with OBS Studio did not record audio, while the ones associated with the Windows Camera did. All audio was immediately removed with a video editing programme, to ensure full anonymity of the participants. The video editing programme was again used to create shorter videos solely focused on the performed suturing task (video with no movement before/after the suturing task is removed). The suturing station recording set is shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: The RCSI's Suturing Station Recording Setup

3.2.2 CV Model Training and Validation

The one-stage YOLOv10 algorithm is considered one of the most prominent object detection algorithms because of its fast and accurate object detection capability. In September 2024, the YOLOv11 algorithm is released, presenting unprecedented speed and accuracy in object detection tasks, with the advantage of supporting a range of CV tasks, including object detection, instance segmentation, image classification, and pose estimation. As a result, both these CV CNN algorithms were selected for this Thesis's work to reliably detect and segment the surgeon's hands, the surgical tools and key suture components. The results of the model training were then compared and the one presenting the most promising results, concerning accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score and computational time, is the selected model to use for the automated suturing skills assessment and grading tool. The success criteria for the YOLO algorithm are to exhibit at least 90% accuracy and at least 85% recall in surgical object detection.

During discussions with Professor Oscar Traynor and Dr. Dara O’Keeffe concerning the relevant metrics to assess and grade suturing skills and competences, it became clear that the RCSI was interested in using a fully explainable automated suturing skill assessment and grading tool, as the RCSI is the official responsible entity for formally assessing and grading the surgeons’ suturing skills and needed to be able to provide insight into their grading decisions.

To accommodate the RCSI’s requirement and pursue a responsible and transparent AI research, a decision was made to use the application of traditional CV techniques instead of the DL *Xception* model to validate the relevant suture quality metrics, as proposed on the work of Mahmud, S. *et al.* [8]. It is known that DL models are black-box in essence, which means that they use complex algorithms to produce predictions or decisions without providing explicit insights into their internal workings. In fact, while DL models often achieve high accuracy levels, they do lack transparency and interpretability. In this Master’s Thesis, the relevant quality suture metrics are then validated through an expert system based on hard-coded traditional CV, functioning as a white-box technique for superior model interpretability and explainability. In addition, the option for a traditional CV-based approach also contributes to surpass specific limitations of the prevailing DL techniques, such as the failure in handling 3D vision and the need for high volumes of data and highly-intensive computational resources [112].

3.2.3 Suture Quality Assessment Metrics

Within the validation approach defined in the Thesis’s designed methodology, it was included the need to identify relevant suture quality metrics to ultimately evaluate the performance of the novel CV-based surgical suturing assessment and grading tool.

Five meetings¹ with the RCSI’s expert surgical trainers, Professor Oscar Traynor, Dr. Dara O’ Keffee, Dr. Eoghan Burke, Dr. Ghazal Haque and Donncha Ryan, were dedicated to the suture quality metrics advocated by the RCSI. Overall, the RCSI uses four main suture quality assessment scales:

- **The OSATs:** Each of the 7 OSATS metrics have a range of 1 to 5 where 1 is extremely bad and 5 is excellent work; these are combined to a Global Rating Scale (5-35) that translates into how well the surgical trainee sutures; it adds a

¹These meetings took place at the RCSI facilities on January 29th 2025, May 29th 2025, June 24th 2025, June 30th 2025 and July 30th 2025.

qualitative element to the otherwise binary and objective assessment of suture skills and competences, allowing to distinguish between two surgical trainees that achieve the same result with different easiness and flow;

- **The Station 2 Wound Closure and Vessel Ligation:** It contains several sections, each with binary metrics – *vessel ligation in continuity* (5 metrics), *vessel ligation – divided* (5 metrics), *vertical mattress suture – hand and instrument ties* (13 metrics), *subcuticular suture* (10 metrics); at the end, the examiner deems the trainee’s competent (pass), incompetent (fail) or borderline (relevant for statistics) performance; if the trainee is marked as fail, the examiner must provide feedback by writing down 3 aspects that had a positive assessment and 3 aspects that were poorly evaluated;
- **The Station 3 Wound Management of Forearm Lacerations:** It presents several sections, each with binary metrics – *closure with interrupted sutures* (6 metrics), *vertical mattress suture* (3 metrics), *subcuticular suture* (6 metrics), *end product inspection and general considerations* (6 metrics); it follows the same procedures as the Station 2;
- **The Brian Lane Medal:** It is comprised of several sections, each with binary metrics – *knot tying* (13 metrics), *interrupted sutures – hand and instrument ties* (11 metrics), *vertical mattress suture – hand and instrument ties* (10 metrics), *subcuticular suture* (9 metrics); at the end, the examiner determines if the trainee is competent (pass), incompetent (fail) or borderline (relevant for statistics), which is independent of the scores previously given; there are clear instructions on how the trainee must proceed: tie five knots in five different directions and turn the jig by 90° in a clockwise direction for every knot; first knot is a reef knot with short end away from you, the second knot is a reef knot with short end to your right, the third knot is a reef knot with short end towards you, the fourth knot is a reef knot with short end to your left and the fifth knot is a surgeons knot and reef knot with short end away from you initially.

Considering that the RCSI was mostly interested in validating the novel automated surgical skills assessment and grading tool with their own suture quality metrics, it was decided to focus the Thesis’s suture quality metrics on three of the four assessment scales used by the RCSI: the Station 2 Wound Closure and Vessel Ligation, the Station 3 Wound Management of Forearm Lacerations and the Brian Lane Medal. These three scales were analysed with the assistance of the RCSI experts and a set

of thirteen (13) metrics was then identified to validate the overall performance of the SUGAR grading system.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

The work implemented as part of this Master's Thesis adheres to the highest standards of research integrity and is particularly attentive to the main ethical principles governing human subject research: respect for autonomy, respect for private life, beneficence and non-maleficence. These principles are encapsulated in relevant the European and national regulations, including the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [116] and the Irish data protection law [117].

Considering the Thesis's goal, scope and methodological approach, the ethical considerations highlight human participation (e.g., the capture of video recordings of surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers performing sutures), the subsequent processing of personal data (e.g., the informed consent forms) and the use of AI technologies.

3.3.1 Human Participation

As the Thesis's research involves human participation, namely for the video capture activity, with the start of the work, the applications to the research ethics committees of MU and of the RCSI have been filled-in, with the expectation that the approvals/opinions would be granted expeditiously. It is noted that, only after the granting of those ethics' approvals/opinions, could the recruitment of the volunteer surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers start, based on eligibility criteria referring to their surgical suturing skills and competences, without discrimination based on any ground, such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation.

Only healthy adults who can give informed consent are voluntarily involved in the Thesis's research activities, following adequate informed consent procedures for human participation in research, to be obtained prior to the start of the research participants' involvement.

3.3.2 Data Protection

This Thesis involves the processing of personal data, comprised of informed consent forms to be signed by all the healthy adult surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers that agree to perform suturing videos. These videos are required to validate the novel CV-based suturing skills assessment and grading tool.

In this context, consideration is given to the level of anonymity required to meet the needs agreed during the informed consent process. Anonymisation techniques are in place to protect the participants' identities in the process of analysing, publishing, and sharing the data, including the digital image recording data.

At all moments, the work is committed to strictly comply with data protection principles, recognising the rights of data subjects, such as the right to be informed (art. 12 GDPR), the Right to access the data, the Right to rectification (art. 16 GDPR), and the Right to object to certain types of processing (art. 21 GDPR) [116].

3.3.3 AI Explainability

The Thesis's work entails the development, deployment and use of AI-based algorithms and techniques, used to attain a reliable detection and identification of suturing needles, suturing tools and hand movements in video imagery.

These AI-based algorithms and techniques are developed considering the seven principles leading to trustworthy AI - Human agency and oversight, Technical robustness and safety, Privacy and data governance, Transparency, Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, Societal and environmental well-being, and Accountability -, promoted by the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence of the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG) [118], and comply with the EU AI Act [119].

AI robustness and trustworthiness of the performed work is ensured by building the AI models to follow standard methodologies for algorithm, hyper-parameter, and variable selection and to incorporate different approaches to explainability, depending on the used models. eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques are applied, following explainability by design approaches and general white-box explainers.

In fact, in order to improve the explainability and transparency of the Thesis's work, a decision was made to replace the DL *Xception* model, a highly accurate black-box model that had been initially considered to validate the defined suture quality metrics

and the performance of the novel automated suturing skills assessment and grading tool, with the hard-coding in Python of traditional white-box CV techniques to implement the suture quality metrics and accomplish those validation tasks.

With the use of traditional CV techniques for validation purposes, this Thesis is able to guarantee the integrity and security of the AI-generated data, with the capability to explain and demonstrate the data sourcing, the generated processing and the validation algorithms implemented by the researcher.

3.3.4 Ethical Approvals/Opinions

With the start of the Thesis's work involving the collaboration with the RCSI, it was clear that the activities involving human participation, namely the collection of surgical suturing videos performed by surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers to validate the work's results, required ethical approvals/opinions from the relevant ethics committees of both MU and the RCSI.

On February 24th 2025, the online application of the RCSI for ethical approval is completed and submitted for approval. The same process is initiated on March 13th 2025 for the MU ERB. During both processes, handled in parallel, a number of relevant Thesis-related documents are produced: the Study Protocol, the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), the Risk Assessment Analysis (in Appendix 2 of DPIA), the Participant Information Leaflet (PIL), and the Consent Form (Appendix A).

On March 11th, 2025 and on March 13th, 2025, meetings were held at MU with Prof. Gerard Lacey and with Brian Phelan, a MU PhD student, to discuss the University's ethics application. On March 15th, a Risk Assessment form was submitted to MU. On May 20th, 2025, the MU ERB requested additional information on the research, including the PIL and the Consent Form. As a result, on June 9th, 2025, the ethics application for the MU REC was revised, as well as the attached documents.

On March 20th, 2025, a new version of the Ethics application to the RCSI REC is submitted, with all the required documents attached. On April 30th, 2025, a formal review request is received from the RCSI REC, with follow-up questions. On June 5th, 2025, an online meeting with Donncha Ryan allowed to proceed with the submission of a revised version of the ethics application, including the answers to the follow-up questions. A second edition of additional questions is then received on June 9th, 2025. Two days later, with Donncha Ryan's support, a revised version of the ethics application was submitted to the RCSI REC, including the answers to the

last batch of follow-up questions.

It is noted that, as the exchanges with the ethics committees of MU and the RCSI unfolded in parallel, and time passed, it was necessary to realistically adjust the expectations for the human participation. All ethics-related documents were updated accordingly.

On June 12th 2025, the ethical approval is granted by the Research Ethics Committee of Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland and, one day later, on June 13th 2025, the ethical approval is granted by the Ethics Research Board of Maynooth University (Appendix A).

With the granting of the required ethics approvals to the research study, the recruitment of participants and the data collection phase of the Thesis were authorised to proceed in the planned dates.

The monitoring and oversight of the Thesis's research activities has been implemented, under the supervision of Professor Gerard Lacey, and in close collaboration with the legal and ethics experts at MU and the RCSI.

Throughout the execution of the Thesis, no ethical issue has been raised. The ethical principles and mandatory requirements have been duly complied with. Also, no ethical concerns such as environmental damage, political or financial or other adverse consequences have been experienced.

Chapter 4

Implementation

This chapter describes the implementation work involved in developing the Proof-of-Concept for the novel SUGAR automated suturing skills assessment and grading tool. It starts by presenting the development of the SUGAR Lite prototype, which provided a starting baseline for the implementation of this Thesis's Proof-of-Concept by investigating the feasibility of a CV-enabled tool to detect and identify reliably key suture components in end-product imagery. It then details the implementation of the Thesis' work, including the video data capture process, the elicitation of relevant suture quality metrics, the manual-based reviews performed by RCSI surgical experts, the creation of the datasets for the Proof-of-Concept demonstration, the training of the CV model and its two-folded validation effort: first, with a statistical and quantitative analysis of the results produced with respect to the thirteen suture quality metrics; and then with a comparative analysis of the results from the traditional human-based assessment (expert reviews of suturing videos) and the results of the novel CV-based SUGAR suturing skills assessment and grading tool.

4.1 SUGAR Lite: A First Step Towards CV-based Suturing Skill Assessment

At the foundation of this Master Thesis is the work conducted in SUGAR Lite [120], which demonstrated the feasibility of a CV-based tool to detect and identify reliably key suture components, and analyse suture images to accurately calculate metrics relevant for assessing the suture's quality. It focused on interrupted sutures, a suturing technique of non-connected stitches with a knot being placed in each stitch and the leftover or the ends of the thread after the knot.

Images of sutures applied to a linear wound were captured from a top view and zoomed in the wound were used, whereas a reliable method to detect and identify those suture components was deemed fundamental to assess the quality of the suture. In addition, the work was based on measurements that are defined in terms of distances and angles between key points of suture components. It is noted that, in contrast to simple continuous sutures, interrupted sutures are more complex to analyse, as they add components (knots and leftovers) and require an algorithm that is able to accurately separate suture components and not be based on edge detection. Based on pre-defined qualification criteria for surgical sutures, a CV-based model was trained on the Noraset *et al.*'s dataset [31] and developed to measure the similarity of performed suture images with the defined criteria, thus presenting an objective and reliable quality assessment process. In this context, the CV algorithm was applied, and its results were analysed in order to obtain an automated, reliable, accurate and useful system for assessing suture quality.

4.1.1 Data Collection and Assembly

In SUGAR Lite, two datasets of about 260 suture images, each comprising at least five sutures, were collected from *Roboflow* for YOLOv11 and combined into one dataset, with the only class being a single *suture*.

In total, five suture image datasets were analysed and compared as presented in Table 4.1. The *Suture* dataset was obtained in *Roboflow*, containing a total of 25 images. Through data augmentation techniques, the dataset was increased to 71 images (69 for training, 2 for testing). The *Suture* dataset is available at <https://app.roboflow.com/sugar-o862x/suture-tl1qx-d8pu1/1>. The *Suture1* dataset was obtained in *Roboflow*, containing a total of 50 images. Through data augmentation techniques, the dataset was increased to 128 images (117 for training, 6 for validation, 5 for testing). The *Suture1* dataset is available at <https://app.roboflow.com/sugar-o862x/suture1/1>. These two augmented datasets were further combined into one, an operation facilitated by the presence of non-conflicting labels associated with each dataset, consisting of the single class *suture*. This original dataset was dubbed *Suture2* and was comprised of 199 images (186 for training, 8 for validation, 5 for testing). The *Suture2* dataset is available at <https://app.roboflow.com/sugar-o862x/suturing-w6exl/1>. These three datasets included the label *suture* and were used as a starting point for detecting individual stitches and test the models' performance.

Lastly, Noraset *et al.*'s dataset was obtained from *CodeOcean* and dubbed *3dv-*

2, containing 225 images (185 for training, 30 for validation, 10 for testing) [31]. Available at <https://app.roboflow.com/sugar-o862x/3dv/2>, this dataset was collected from images of suture practice end-products performed by novices and experts, with manual annotations for training models and evaluating the system. These annotations included the labels *knot*, *leftover*, *stitch* and *wound*, enhancing the complexity of the system and allowing for an increased number of metrics to be analysed. It is noted that, in this dataset’s collection, there were two phases: the first consisting of novices using silk thread and the second gathering both novices and experts using nylon thread. This difference is relevant as the nylon thread is considerably thinner, making it more challenging to identify and, thus, to segment components. In addition, images of the second phase had a marker line on an incision. The obtained dataset was subject to data augmentation techniques, originating the dataset *3dv-1* with 539 images (471 for training, 51 for validation, 17 for testing). This dataset is available at <https://app.roboflow.com/sugar-o862x/3dv/1>.

Table 4.1: The Five Datasets Used in SUGAR Lite

#	Dataset	# Images	Labels
1	Suture	71	suture
2	Suture1	128	suture
3	Suture2	199	suture
4	3dv-2	225	stitch, wound, knot, leftover
5	3dv-1	539	stitch, wound, knot, leftover

4.1.2 Suture Quality Metrics

In SUGAR Lite, relevant suture quality metrics were analysed and evaluated to determine that:

- The bite size (length of each stitch) is equal across the wound;
- The pitch size (distance of between each stitch) is equal across the wound;
- The left bite size (interval distance between the stitch’s left extremity and the wound) is equal across the wound;
- The right bite size (interval distance between the stitch’s right extremity and the wound) is equal across the wound;
- The skewness of angle (orientation of each stitch) is equal across the wound;

- The orientation of each stitch is approximately 90° to the wound;
- The location of each knot is the same relative to the wound and across the wound;
- The length of each leftover is equal throughout the sutures.

4.1.3 CV Software Application and Model Training and Validation

In general, when fast and accurate detection is required, the one-stage YOLOv11 CV algorithm is considered one of the most prominent object detection algorithms, being the selected algorithm for this work. This selection was also directly linked to YOLOv11's advanced instance segmentation capability, which delivers fine-grained, pixel-level object detection that delineates precise object boundaries.

In SUGAR Lite, the CV algorithm involved two successive stages: 1) Image Processing and 2) Metrics Extraction. In the Image Processing stage, the applied CV algorithm used advanced segmentation techniques to detect and identify key suture components: stitches, knots, leftovers and wound. In the Metrics Extraction stage, the suture information was used to compute metrics for suture quality assessment. It was expected that the CV model's training, validation and testing effort would attain accuracy and recall levels higher than 85%. Then, the suture quality assessment metrics were calculated based on the estimated distances and angles between key points of suture components. The software for the image processing stage and for the metrics extraction stage was written in Python.

SUGAR Lite adopted instance segmentation to enable a precise analysis of suture quality metrics. As such, the CV algorithm YOLOv11 was chosen and trained with the previously mentioned datasets. Table 4.2 presents the model training and validation performed.

Table 4.2: Model Training and Validation of SUGAR Lite

#	Dataset	Model	Precision (%)	Recall(%)	Score (%)
1	Suture	YOLOv11n	28.8	33.3	31.0
2	Suture2	YOLOv11n	93.2	91.9	92.5
3	Suture	YOLOv11s	88.6	86.5	87.5
4	Suture1	Trained Model 1	93.4	86.5	89.9
5	3dv-1	YOLOv11n	91.8	78.3	85.0
6	3dv-1	YOLOv11n	86.0	83.3	84.6
7	3dv-1	YOLOv11m	92.8	83.5	88.1
8	3dv-2	YOLOv11x	84.8	81.9	83.3
9	3dv-2	YOLOv11n	72.2	79.8	76.0
10	3dv-1	YOLOv11l	86.8	88.4	87.6
11	3dv-1	YOLOv11l	91.8	86.7	89.2

All model training parameters were similar, with 100 epochs and a batch size of 16, with the exception of Train 11, with 200 epochs. The computation time parameter was not deemed relevant, for the datasets were not large and, consequently, the training time was fast and similar throughout the different model trains, rounding up to a few minutes. Train 8 was the exception, as the extra-large YOLOv11x model that was trained took around 3 hours to complete. The performance score was calculated for each trained model, by calculating the weighted average value using precision and recall. In Table 4.2, it is possible to observe that the Trained Models 2 and 4 presented the best results in accuracy and recall.

However, they were limited to applications using a single parameter (i.e., suture). On the other hand, the *3dv-1* and *3dv-2* datasets allowed to detect and classify four distinct suture components (*stitch*, *knot*, *wound* and *leftover*), making them more suitable for the Project’s objectives. Based on the obtained results, the model selected for the Project’s suture metrics analysis was the Trained Model 11, which displayed the best score (89.2%) for the *3dv-1* dataset.

4.1.4 Suture Quality Analysis Through Metrics

The suture quality analysis performed in SUGAR Lite was the result of the expert system hard-coded software using the Python language. Code functions were created to calculate the length between two 2D points, the distance between two 1D points, the average of values in a vector, the stitch orientation and the wound orientation. Particularly, the stitch orientation received the coordinates of the two extremities of the stitch, applied the *atan2* function to obtain the angle in radians and converted

the angle into degrees for easier interpretation. Similarly, the wound orientation received the two extremities of the wound, applied the *atan2* function to obtain the angle in radians, converted the angle into degrees and added 90° as the wound was vertical, rather than horizontal. It is noted that this work assumed that all stitches were approximately horizontal and all wounds vertical and linear.

When applying the Trained Model 11 (see Table 4.2) to a suture image, the outputs analysed and used in this work consisted of the object classification and the several normalised point coordinates which segment it. Given the high number of coordinates per detected object, the first step was to create separate matrices for each class label, which were filled with the relevant coordinates. For each knot, the average of all its x coordinates is calculated and stored. For each leftover and stitch, the left and right extremities are collected and stored. For each wound, the lower and upper extremities are collected and stored. Further, the stitch matrix consisting of the relevant coordinates is sorted from the lowest to the highest and from left to right.

Next, to assess the suture's quality, several metrics were analysed: knot placement, suture orientation, skewness of angle, bite size, pitch size, leftover length, left bite size, right bite size, overall suture symmetry and overall suture quality.

The ***Knot Placement Quality*** was assessed by comparing an established threshold to the absolute difference between each knot's x coordinate and the average of all knots' x coordinates. Given the threshold defined for this metric, if the absolute difference was less than 0.012, the knot was considered correctly placed, otherwise it was considered incorrectly placed. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The ***Suture Orientation Quality*** pertains to the perpendicularity between each stitch and the wound, assessed by comparing the established thresholds to the absolute difference between each stitch orientation and the wound orientation. Given the thresholds defined for this metric, if the absolute difference was greater than 80° and less than 100° , the stitch orientation was considered correct, otherwise it was considered incorrect. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The ***Skewness of Angle Quality*** refers to the uniformity of stitch orientation, in this case it should be approximately horizontal. This metric was assessed by comparing the established threshold to the absolute difference between two subsequent stitch orientations. Given the threshold defined for this metric, if the absolute

difference was less than 15° , the stitches were considered aligned, otherwise they were considered incorrect. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The *Bite Size Quality* is associated with the uniformity of stitch length, assessed by comparing the established threshold to the absolute difference between each stitch bite size and the average of all stitches' bite sizes. Given the threshold defined for this metric, if the absolute difference was less than 0.03, the stitches were considered to have approximately the same bite size, otherwise they were considered incorrect. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The *Pitch Size Quality* links with the uniformity of the distance between each stitch, assessed by comparing the established threshold to the absolute difference between two subsequent stitches' pitch size and the average of all pitch sizes. Given the threshold defined for this metric, if the absolute difference was less than 0.03, the stitches were considered evenly spaced, otherwise they were considered incorrect. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The *Leftover Size Quality* is assessed by comparing the established threshold to the absolute difference between each leftover length and the average of all leftovers' lengths. Given the threshold defined for this metric, if the absolute difference was less than 0.015, the leftovers were considered to have approximately the same length, otherwise they were considered incorrect. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The *Left Bite Size Quality* is based on the uniformity of stitch length from the left extremity to the wound. Since it is assumed that the wound is vertical and linear, the left bite size was analysed through the left extremity's x coordinate, in order to simplify. This metric was assessed by comparing the established threshold to the absolute difference between each the distance between two subsequent stitches' x coordinates and the average of all these distances. Given the threshold defined for this metric, if the absolute difference was less than 0.02, the stitches were considered to be approximately aligned on the left of the wound, otherwise they were considered incorrect. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The *Right Bite Size Quality* relates with the uniformity of stitch length from the

right extremity to the wound. Since it was assumed that the wound is vertical and linear, the right bite size was analysed through the right extremity's x coordinate, in order to simplify. This metric was assessed by comparing the established threshold to the absolute difference between each the distance between two subsequent stitches' x coordinates and the average of all these distances. Given the threshold defined for this metric, if the absolute difference was less than 0.02, the stitches were considered to be approximately aligned on the right of the wound, otherwise they were considered incorrect. The success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

The *Overall Suture Symmetry* considers the uniformity of stitch length on the left and on the right of the wound, also known as left and right bite size, respectively. Since it was assumed that the wound is vertical and linear, the left and right bite sizes were analysed through each stitch's x coordinates, in order to simplify. This metric was assessed by adding the amount of successfully aligned stitches on each side of the wound and dividing by two. Then, the success rate was converted into a percentage and printed.

Lastly, the *Overall Suture Quality* averaged all the metrics' percentages, grading the analysed suture as inadequate ($<50\%$), adequate ($<70\%$), good ($<80\%$), very good ($<90\%$) and excellent ($\geq 90\%$).

4.1.5 System Validation

Because the selected *3dv-1* dataset provided images of suture end-products by novices and experts, an image of each suture was analysed visually by the author and by the designed system. The established thresholds were adjusted as necessary to provide an accurate grade based on the established metrics.

Figures 4.1 and 4.2 present images of the suture end-products made by a novice and by an expert, respectively.

Figure 4.1: SUGAR Lite Grading a Novice's Suture Quality

In Figure 4.1, the grades given to the novice on each metric were:

- Knot Placement: 16.67%
- Suture Orientation Quality: 100.00%
- Skewness of Angle: 90.91%
- Bite Size Quality: 16.67%
- Pitch Size Quality: 100.00%
- Leftover Size Quality: 83.33%
- Left Bite Size Quality: 100.00%
- Right Bite Size Quality: 40.00%
- Overall Suture Symmetry: 70.00%
- **Overall Suture Quality: 68.45% (Adequate)**

Figure 4.2: SUGAR Lite Grading an Expert's Suture Quality

In Figure 4.2, the grades given to the expert on each metric were:

- Knot Placement: 100.00%
- Suture Orientation Quality: 60.00%
- Skewness of Angle: 88.89%
- Bite Size Quality: 80.00%
- Pitch Size Quality: 100.00%
- Leftover Size Quality: 100.00%
- Left Bite Size Quality: 100.00%
- Right Bite Size Quality: 75.00%
- Overall Suture Symmetry: 87.50%
- **Overall Suture Quality: 87.99% (Very Good)**

This work presented a CV-enabled tool capable of automating the assessment of suture quality. SUGAR Lite is capable of reliably detecting and identifying key suture components in interrupted sutures and extracting knot placement, suture orientation, skewness of angle, bite size, pitch size, leftover length, left bite size, right bite size, overall suture symmetry and overall suture quality metrics.

Several model trainings were performed to guarantee the selection of the best model, with the most promising results belonging to the Trained Model 11. Then, ten metrics were selected based on related work, and hard-coded to enable subsequent analysis and grading, conducive to the assessment of the sutures' quality. In overall, the SUGAR Lite grader exhibited promising results regarding the metrics' grading, distinguishing between the quality of sutures performed by a novice and an expert.

Still, despite exhibiting high precision and recall values, the SUGAR Lite CV model also presented limitations, namely concerning the capability to correctly detect and segment objects. Indeed, the dataset is one of the most prominent influencers in the model's correct and successful training, with large and diverse datasets considered important. The used dataset presented challenges identified by Noraset *et al.* [31], mentioned in section 4.1.1.

It was therefore noted the need to obtain a larger and more diverse suture image dataset, as well as to further investigate the model's performance on video and/or real-time settings. These limitations are addressed in the present Master's Thesis, leveraging on the results of the SUGAR Lite work that clearly pointed towards

the feasibility of applying a CV-based approach to an automated tool for assessing sutures' quality.

It is also worth mentioning that the SUGAR Lite project has inspired a paper that was published in the 14th Conference on New Technologies for Computer/Robot Assisted Surgery (CRAS) 2025 Proceedings, having won a prize of "Best Poster" [120].

4.2 SUGAR: The Novel Automated Surgical sUturing GrAdeR Proof-of-Concept

Leveraged by a sustained body of knowledge (chapter 2) and inspired in the promising findings and conclusions of the SUGAR Lite prototype (section 4.1), the development work of the Proof-of-Concept for the novel SUGAR automated suturing skills assessment and grading tool starts.

4.2.1 Data Capture

Following the attainment of the required ethics approvals from MU and RCSI (see section 3.3), it is possible to proceed with the recruitment of at least 15 research participants and the recording of at least 25 suturing videos. At this time, it is already decided to recruit at least 12 Year 1 surgical trainees from the national surgical training programme and at least 3 expert surgical trainers from RCSI that were enrolled to take part in the RCSI CST Bootcamp 2025 edition.

Hence, prior to the start of the CST Bootcamp 2025 training, the RCSI reached out to the CST Bootcamp 2025's registered participants by email, introducing the SUGAR Master's Thesis and stating how any surgical trainee or surgical trainer would be able to voluntarily support the Thesis's work, by agreeing to perform a suturing task and having that activity recorded in video. This email included the presentation of the Study Protocol, the PIL and the Consent Form as attachments. These documents can be found in Appendix A. This initiative brought early awareness to the Thesis's work and to the purpose of the participants' involvement, with several CST Bootcamp 2025 participants already agreeing to perform the suturing videos and sending their signed Consent Forms.

Figure 4.3: Consent Forms for the Participants in the Suturing Task

The recording setup described in section 3.2.1 was installed at the RCSI premises and is shown in Figure 4.4. Two computers are connected to three suturing stations to record the videos.

Figure 4.4: Deployment of Suturing Stations at RCSI for the Suturing Task

In addition, on the first day of each course of the CST Bootcamp 2025 training (the 90 surgical trainees attending the CST Bootcamp 2025 edition were divided into three 3-day courses), there was a session about the SUGAR Master's Thesis, inviting the surgical trainees and the surgical trainers to perform suturing videos during the Bootcamp intervals. The voluntary participants would have to perform a simple interrupted suture (the most common and straightforward technique for wound closure) on a vertical laceration with the surgical instruments, using the RCSI suturing station. They were briefed that there is no time constraint to the task, nor a minimum number of sutures nor instructions to fully close the laceration in the skin pad. Participants were at the liberty to stop at any given moment, regardless of the level of completion of the suturing task. The participants were also informed of their rights, including their full anonymity, as they decided to take part in the suturing task. The PIL and the Consent Forms were provided to the CST Bootcamp 2025 participants and they were encouraged to read them and to sign the form, should they agree to participate in the suturing task and before any suturing task took place. A Q&A session completed the SUGAR Master's Thesis introduction, enabling the CST Bootcamp 2025 participants to fully understand the purpose and scope of their potential involvement.

On July 1st, 2025, the data capture phase of the Master's Thesis started and it was completed by July 11th, 2025. For twelve days, Year 1 surgical trainees and RCSI

expert surgical trainers at the CST Bootcamp 2025 adhered to the initiative and shared their suturing skills in video. At the end of the data capture phase, a total of 51 HD suturing videos was captured, 38 of them performed by 35 surgical trainees and 13 of them performed by 10 expert surgical trainers. The goal of achieving at least 25 HD suturing videos and involving at least 15 participants is far exceeded, with added benefits to the Thesis's work.

An example of a participant performing a suturing task is shown in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Research Participant Performing the Suturing Task

4.2.2 Suture Quality Metrics

Important meetings were held from October 17th, 2024 to July 30th, 2025 with representatives of the Surgical Affairs Department of the RCSI – Professor Oscar Traynor, Donncha Ryan, Dr. Dara O’Keeffe, Dr. Eoghan Burke and Dr. Ghazal Haque – to identify user needs, gaps, shortcomings and requirements. Alongside a better awareness and understanding of the medical education field, and of the surgical suturing assessment process in particular, these meetings addressed the definition of the suture quality metrics considered most relevant by the RCSI to validate the automated SUGAR grader, and the coordination of the expert reviews of the collected suturing videos and suture end-product images.

On June 24th, 2025, a first draft of a metrics list is created, based on the four suturing assessment score sheets (OSATS, Station 2, Station 3 and Brian Lane Medal) currently used by RCSI. On June 30th, 2025, in a meeting dedicated to the suture quality metrics with Dr. Dara O’Keeffe, the metrics were thoroughly discussed,

and a precise understanding of the movements required for their assessment was gained.

As a result, a selection of relevant suture quality metrics was applied and the metrics list was fine-tuned to a final set of thirteen (13) metrics, of which one (1) to be applied to human-based input collected before the suturing task starts, seven (7) to be applied to the suturing videos and five (5) to be applied to the suture end-product images. On July 30th, 2025, a final meeting was held at the RCSI facilities with Dr. Ghazal Haque in which the observation of various suturing videos allowed to discuss in great detail relevant surgical suturing skills and how to identify whether each of the metrics was being performed correctly or not, especially considering the absence of 3D information.

Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Human-based Input

Following the RCSI's guidance, one relevant suture quality metric to validate with the SUGAR system is applied before the start of the suturing task:

- Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size; non-absorbable (absorbability); monofilament (structure).

The *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure) metric* is analysed through a series of short multiple choice questions asked at the beginning of the suturing task performed by each participant. Concerning a laceration on the forearm,

- On size: 2-0, 3-0, 4-0, or 5-0 are available answers; the 3-0 and 4-0 options are considered correct answers;
- On absorbability: absorbable or non-absorbable are available answers; the non-absorbable option is the correct answer;
- On structure: monofilament or braided are available answers; the monofilament option is the correct answer.

If the participant answers at least one of the questions incorrectly, this metric is considered as *Not Done*.

Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suturing Videos

Following the RCSI's guidance, the seven most relevant suture quality metrics for suturing videos to validate with the SUGAR system are:

- Correct placement of needle within the needle holder;
- Insertion of needle at the right angle with respect to the skin;
- Needle inserted and removed using supination;
- Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges;
- One pass of needle per suture insertion;
- Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot;
- Handled needle with forceps, not fingers.

These metrics are assessed in the analysis of the video as the suturing task is performed.

The *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder* metric is assessed by observing where the needle holder grasps the needle. The approximate correct position is 2/3 of the way around the needle point (see Figure 4.6). By holding the needle incorrectly, there is greater risk of the needle being dropped, bent or broken, wrongly manoeuvred or even stabbed into the tissue or suturing pad, as well as cause inadequate tissue penetration and excessive tissue trauma. If the participant does not correctly place the needle within the needle holder, this metric is assessed as *Not Done*.

Figure 4.6: Correct Placement of Needle Within the Needle Holder

The ***Insertion of needle at the right angle to the skin metric*** is examined by observing whether the participant is piercing through the skin at an approximate right angle by grasping the skin with the toothed forceps and holding it vertically to aid the achievement of the correct insertion angle. If done incorrectly, the needle is more prone to not achieve the correct depth, which translates into a suture that is too superficial and at risk of unravelling more easily. If the participant does not insert the needle at the right angle to the skin, this metric is assessed as *Not Done*.

The ***Needle inserted and removed using supination metric*** is reviewed by observing whether the participant inserts and removes the needle through a small rotatory movement performed by the wrist rather than horizontally, dragging the needle. Using supination, the needle exits in the depth of the wound; when being dragged, the needle exits superficially. When supination is not performed correctly, it can cause additional unnecessary trauma to the already existing laceration. If the participant performs the insertion and removal using supination, this metric is assessed as *Done*.

The ***Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from incision edges metric*** is evaluated by observing the approximate distance between each bite and the laceration. When the appropriate bite size is not achieved, the sutures become at risk of unravelling, with the laceration reopening. If the participant does not insert and remove the needle at the correct distance from the incision edges, this metric is assessed as *Not Done*.

The ***One pass of needle per suture insertion metric*** is inspected by assessing whether the participant hesitates when inserting the needle or whether the participant inserts it incorrectly and removes it to retry. While the hesitation merely reflects how experienced and at-ease the participant is with performing simple interrupted sutures, the removal to retry causes unnecessary additional physical trauma near the laceration. If the participant performs more than one pass of needle per suture insertion, this metric is assessed as *Not Done*.

The ***Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot metric*** is appraised by whether the participant pulls the long thread back on top of the short-end to keep the tension on the first throw, since the other throws serve merely to stabilise the knot and keep the tension. When the locking of the suture is

not performed, there is an increased risk of the suture unravelling due to incorrect tension. If the participant does not perform the locking of the suture, this metric is assessed as *Not Done*.

Figure 4.7: The Surgeons' Knot (source: RCSI)

The *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers metric* is judged by whether the participant grabs the needle with their fingers at any point during the suturing task. While it does not affect the overall quality of the suture, it is considered a safety hazard to handle sharp instruments without the proper tools and there is a higher contamination risk. If the participant handles the needle with fingers, this metric is assessed as *Not Done*.

Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suture End-Product Images

In accordance to the RCSI's guidance, the five most relevant suture quality metrics for suture end-products to validate with the SUGAR system are:

- All sutures parallel to each other;
- All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound;
- Distance between sutures appropriate;
- Distance between sutures equal;
- Suture tension appropriate.

These metrics are assessed in the analysis of the suture end-product image, after the suturing task is performed.

The *All sutures parallel to each other metric* is analysed by whether the sutures are parallel to each other throughout the suture. Some experts also analyse whether the sutures are perpendicular to the laceration, which is a cause for increased subjectivity for this particular metric.

The *All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound metric* is analysed by whether the suture extremities are placed approximately at the same distance from the laceration, presenting a similar bite size on both sides of the laceration throughout the suture.

The *Distance between sutures appropriate metric* is analysed by whether the spacing between each suture is considered correct, presenting a pitch size that is not too little, which results in an increased use of resources without need and potential additional tissue damage, or too large, which increases the risk of the sutures unravelling and the incision edges not being closed, compromising the wound's healing.

The *Distance between sutures equal metric* is analysed by whether the spacing between each suture is approximately equal, presenting a similar pitch size throughout the suture.

The *Suture tension appropriate metric* is analysed by whether the tension is *too little*, associated with gaps present in the laceration (see Figure 4.8a), or *too much*, associated with sutures that are difficult to see and with a lighter colour presenting itself throughout the laceration (see Figure 4.8b).

(a) Sutures Displaying *Too Little* Tension

(b) Sutures Displaying *Too Much* Tension

Figure 4.8: Sutures Displaying Incorrect Levels of Tension

4.2.3 Video Reviews by Surgical Experts

Considering the uniqueness and novelty of the CV-based suturing skills assessment and grading tool, it is acknowledged the relevance of defining and implementing the tool's sound validation approach. In this context, and because the tool's reference suture quality metrics are identified and specified by the RCSI surgical experts, based on the suturing skills assessment and grading system at RCSI, it is fundamental to include in the validation approach a cross-check between the automated tool's assessment results and the results of the traditional human-based suturing skills assessment.

Figure 4.9: SUGAR Video Expert Review Website

Hence, to facilitate the gathering of the RCSI expert reviews of the captured data, a website (see Figure 4.9) was created and shared with the RCSI surgical experts to allow them to watch and review the captured anonymised suturing videos and suture end-product images and provide their reviews following the identified suture quality metrics, using the developed online form presented in Figure 4.10. The aim is for each suturing video and suture end-product image to be reviewed by two expert surgical trainers so that a more robust assessment can be built.

The website presents the suturing videos and suture end-product images, alongside their respective ID number. This ID number not only ensures that all participants performing the sutures remain anonymous, but also that the surgical experts do not know if the suturing videos and suture images are performed by a surgical trainee or by a surgical trainer, thus contributing to an unbiased review. In addition, the website indicates whether the reviews are complete and the names of the surgical experts providing them.

When submitting a review, the surgical experts need to provide their name and manually write the suturing video ID number under review. Once the reviews are submitted, they cannot be accessed by other surgical experts, avoiding the possibility of bias when performing the suture quality metrics' assessment. In addition, the website is updated to showcase whether the suturing videos and imagery have been reviewed, ensuring the surgical experts may focus on the suturing videos and images lacking reviews.

SUGAR
SURGICAL SUTURING GRADER

SUGAR Video Expert Reviews

Reviewer's name: *

Your answer _____

Video number: *

Your answer _____

Closure with interrupted sutures *

	Not Done	Done
Correct placement of needle within needle holder	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Insertion and exit of needle approx. 2-4 mm from incision edges	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 4.10: SUGAR Video Expert Review Form

4.2.4 Data Collection and Assembly

To train the novel SUGAR surgical suturing grader, it is necessary to analyse several datasets suitable for video analysis, leading to a general comparison between the latest versions of the YOLO algorithms: YOLOv10 and YOLOv11. It is noted that the analysis of images utilises the Noraset *et al.*'s dataset [31], used for the SUGAR Lite prototype (section 4.1).

For the YOLOv10 model, two datasets are collected for CV training, one dataset (*Surgical needle*) addressing the detection of surgical needles and the other dataset (*AIsture*) focusing on the detection of suturing tools, such as the forceps and the needle holder. These datasets are obtained from *Roboflow* and augmentation techniques, such as cropping, rotation, brightness, and blur, are used to create newer and larger versions. Originally, the surgical needle dataset *Surgical needle* was comprised of 2721 images, with 2695 for training and 17 for validation. After the application of data augmentation techniques, the surgical needle dataset comprises 6673 images, with 6616 for training, 31 for validation and 26 for testing, available at <https://universe.roboflow.com/renji-hospital/surgical-needle/dataset/9>. Similarly, the suturing tools dataset *AIsture* was comprised of 505 images, with 405 for training and 100 for validation. After the application of data augmentation techniques, this dataset comprises 4150 images, with 4050 for training and 100 for validation, available at <https://app.roboflow.com/sugar-o862x/aisuture-mwik4/1>. This dataset detects the surgeon's hands and several surgical suturing tools, namely the forceps, the needle holder, the scissors and the simulator.

For the YOLOv11 model, four datasets are collected for CV training: two of them (*Surgical needle* and *Segmentación de aguja 2*) are centred on the detection of the surgical needle and the other two datasets (*AIsture* and *Instance2*) support the detection of suturing tools, such as the forceps and the needle holder. All the datasets were obtained from *Roboflow* and different augmentation techniques, such as cropping, rotation, brightness, and blur, are applied to create newer and larger dataset versions.

The suturing needle dataset *Surgical needle* is collected from *Roboflow* for the YOLOv11 model training in two distinct formats: the first format contains bounding boxes and the second format uses oriented bounding boxes. The oriented bounding boxes precisely enclose the objects in the image, which is particularly useful when objects appear at various angles [121].

For the suturing needle's detection and segmentation, the *Segmentación de aguja 2*

was obtained from *Roboflow* for the YOLOv11 model training in an instance segmentation format. The instance segmentation model produces a set of masks or contours that outline each object in the image, considered useful for identifying objects, their location and their exact shape [122]. This dataset originally contained 826 images (578 for training and 248 for validation) and, after applying data augmentation techniques, which included cropping, rotating, brightness and blurring, a dataset of 8918 images (8670 for training and 248 for validation) is obtained, available at <https://app.roboflow.com/thesis-etwje/segmentacion-de-aguja-2-jz9al/3>.

The suturing tools dataset *AIuture* was also collected for the YOLOv11 model training in two formats: bounding boxes and oriented bounding boxes.

The suturing tools dataset *Instance2* was collected from *Roboflow* for the YOLOv11 model training in the instance segmentation format. This dataset detects and segments *bend hemostat*, *curved tip surgical scissors*, *dressing forceps*, *needle forceps*, *straight hemostat*, *straight-tipped surgical scissors*, *tissue forceps* and *hilt*. The *Instance2* dataset contains 301 images (240 for training, 47 for validation and 14 for testing). After applying data augmentation techniques, a dataset of 3661 images was generated (3600 for training, 47 for validation and 14 for testing), available at <https://app.roboflow.com/thesis-etwje/instance2-tqnxe/1>.

Regarding the dataset generated for the end-product image analysis, the Noraset *et al.*'s dataset was obtained from *CodeOcean*, containing 225 images (185 for training, 30 for validation, 10 for testing). Available at <https://app.roboflow.com/sugar-o862x/3dv/2>, this dataset was collected from images of suture practice end-products performed by novices and experts. These annotations included the labels: *knot*, *leftover*, *stitch* and *wound*, enhancing the complexity of the system and allowing for an increased number of metrics to be analysed [31]. It is noted that, in this dataset's collection, there were two phases: the first consisting of novices using silk thread and the second gathering both novices and experts using nylon thread. This difference is relevant as the nylon thread is considerably thinner, making it more challenging to identify and, thus, to segment components. In addition, images of the second phase have a marker line on an incision. The obtained dataset was subject to data augmentation techniques, originating a dataset containing 1746 images (1690 for training, 38 for validation and 18 for testing). One dataset was named *Sut2*, where the label *stitch* was converted to *suture*, and with another being named *Sut3* and altered to detect and segment *suture*, *knot* and *laceration*, with the leftover label being discarded, and named *Sut3*.

Table 4.3 summarises the six datasets used in SUGAR.

Table 4.3: The Six Publicly Available Datasets Used in SUGAR

Dataset	Scope	Model	# Images	Labels
AlSuture	Video	YOLOv10, YOLOv11 and YOLOv11-obb	4150	forceps, left hand, needle holder, right hand, scissors, simulator
Instance2	Video	YOLOv11-seg	3661	bend hemostat, curved tip surgical scissors, dressing forceps, needle forceps, straight hemostat, straight-tipped surgical scissors, tissue forceps, hilt
Segmentación de aguja 2	Video	YOLOv11-seg	8918	needle
Surgical needle	Video	YOLOv10, YOLOv11 and YOLOv11-obb	6673	needle
Sut2	Video	YOLOv11-seg	1746	suture, laceration, knot, leftover
Sut3	Video	YOLOv11-seg	1746	suture, laceration, knot

The YOLO models' training and validation work associated with the aforementioned datasets is presented in section 4.2.6.

4.2.5 Dataset Creation

After the thorough training and validation effort on the YOLO models with the six different datasets used in this Thesis, detailed in section 4.2.6, it became clear that the datasets collected from *Roboflow* were ineffective for detecting the surgical needle and the surgical tools in the videos captured for the SUGAR tool, particularly for training the CV models with the surgical tools dataset. Therefore, a decision is made to create a new dataset using the suturing videos captured in the RCSI CST Bootcamp 2025. This new dataset was denominated *Suture 3*. In order to obtain a large number of relevant and different images, the videos were selected randomly, and a frame is collected every 90 frames, which corresponds to 3 seconds of video. As 1500 images are collected, these are uploaded to *Roboflow* for manual labelling, a very time-consuming and thorough work. Figure 4.11 provide examples of the result of the manual labelling process: Figure 4.11a is the original image without labelling; Figure 4.11b is the image after manual labelling. The right hand is represented in purple, the left hand in red, the scissors in light blue, the needle holder in green, the forceps in orange, the laceration in yellow, the needle in dark blue and the sutures in pink.

Figure 4.11: Example of Manual Labelling Work Results

Because of the manual labelling work performed, the new created dataset is capable of detecting and segmenting *laceration, left hand, needle, needle holder, right hand, suture, suture cutting scissors, toothed forceps*, gathering 1528 images, with 1070 for training, 305 for validation and 153 for testing. After applying data augmentation techniques, including cropping, rotation, brightness and blurring, a new dataset was generated containing 11158 images, with 10700 for training, 305 for validation and 153 for testing.

4.2.6 CV Model Training and Validation

In order to design, develop and implement the new SUGAR tool and the CV-based approach to model a surgical suturing assessment process, it was important to articulate into the Thesis's work the relevant state-of-the-art knowledge on AI-based technologies.

Because the novel SUGAR automated suturing skills assessment and grading tool is based on object detection and segmentation, the YOLO algorithms are used for object detection and segmentation involving surgical suturing tools. It is noted that the SUGAR tool is already trained and validated for the suture and the different suture components, based on the SUGAR Lite work described in section 4.1.

From February 2025, the training of the YOLOv10 models started. The surgical needle and suturing tools datasets were obtained from *Roboflow* and data augmentation techniques were applied. Using the built datasets, several YOLOv10 algorithms were trained and compared. The most relevant results obtained are presented in Table 4.4 and Figure 4.12.

Table 4.4: Parameters and Results Obtained in YOLOv10 Models Training

#	Dataset	Model	Epoch	Batch	Computation Time (h)	Precision (%)	Recall(%)
1	OSN	YOLOv10n	100	20	0.56	58.6	54.1
2	OSN	TM1	100	80	1.67	59.8	51.4
3	OSN	YOLOv10x	100	10	3.75	63.0	50.6
4	OSN	YOLOv10m	275	20	4.58	80.6	51.4
5	ASN	YOLOv10s	100	20	2.33	80.5	68.8
6	ASN	YOLOv10m	100	20	4.17	90.7	70.8
7	AST	YOLOv10n	100	25	0.50	94.0	93.9
8	AST	YOLOv10s	100	10	1.53	96.6	96.7

OSN – Original Surgical Needle; ASN – Augmented Surgical Needle; AST – Augmented Suturing Tools; TM1 (or Trained Model 1) refers to the trained model obtained from the first training (in the above row).

(a) Precision and Recall values obtained in YOLOv10 models training**(b)** Computation Time taken in YOLOv10 models training**Figure 4.12:** YOLOv10 Models Training Results

As shown in Table 4.4, eight CV models were trained with the obtained datasets. The CV models that achieved relatively low precision and recall values are the first four trained CV models, with the next four CV models presenting higher percentages.

Further, Figure 4.12b demonstrates the computation time with respect to each CV model's training, with Trained Models 3, 4 and 6 yielding a relatively higher computation time. This is expected since the Trained Model 3 involves the largest YOLOv10 model in existence, the Trained Model 4 is associated with the highest epoch number, translating to a training approximately three times larger, and the Trained Model 6 is linked with a relatively larger dataset.

Overall, Trained Models 6 and 8 yield the most promising results for suturing needle detection and for suturing tools detection, respectively. Trained Model 6 achieved a precision of 90.7% and a recall factor of 70.8% for surgical needle detection, whereas Trained Model 8 achieved a precision of 96.6% and a recall factor of 96.7% for suturing tools' detection.

Figures 4.13 and 4.14 display the results from the most promising models' training

and validation, which highlight, throughout the training time, a reduction tendency in loss values and an augmentation tendency in precision, recall, mean Average Precision 50 and mean Average Precision 50-95 values.

Figure 4.13: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 6

Figure 4.14: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 8

The results obtained from the remaining training of the YOLOv10 models may be found in Appendix B.

Next, Figure 4.15 presents the predictions performed by the most promising trained models: the Trained Model 6, concerning the surgical needle dataset (Figure 4.15a) and the Trained Model 8, concerning the suturing tools dataset (Figure 4.15b).

(a) Validation Image Obtained from the Trained Model 6

(b) Validation Image Obtained from the Trained Model 8

Figure 4.15: Validation Images Obtained from Trained Models

The performed tests revealed the importance of batching and its impact in memory usage, with 20 batches being ideal for a computer with a GPU NVIDIA RTX4080 and 128GB RAM, and 25 batches for a computer with a GPU NVIDIA RTX4090 and 64GB RAM. Additionally, the recommended minimal number of epochs for training a YOLO model is 100.

After adequately training the CV models for the detection of the surgical needle and of the suturing tools, these CV models were applied and tested on the suturing videos captured during the RCSI CST Bootcamp 2025. Although the most promising training results of these models display a precision of 90.7% and a recall factor of 70.8% for surgical needle detection and a precision of 96.6% and a recall factor of 96.7% for suturing tools detection, a decision is made to analyse the performance of YOLOv11 models, since these models support oriented bounding boxes. In addition, the YOLOv11 algorithms are expected to improve the model's detection capability. The results of different YOLOv11 algorithms were compared and the most relevant training results are presented in Table 4.5 and Figure 4.16.

Table 4.5: Parameters and Results Obtained in YOLOv11 Models Training

#	Dataset	Model	Epoch	Batch	Computation Time (h)	Precision (%)	Recall(%)
1	ASN	YOLOv11n	100	16	0.89	75.9	77.1
2	ASN	YOLOv11m	100	16	2.35	78.3	82.6
3	ASN	YOLOv11l	150	16	2.57	88.0	75.0
4	ASN	YOLOv11l	150	16	3.58	80.9	75.0
5	AI	YOLOv11n	100	25	0.68	95.9	93.9
6	ASN	YOLOv11s-obb	100	30	2.01	99.0	72.9
7	ASN	TM6	100	30	7.13	92.6	78.5
8	SA2	YOLOv11n-seg	100	16	1.75	82.0	77.8
9	I2	TM8	100	25	0.70	95.3	97.4
10	SA2	YOLOv11n-seg	100	16	0.37	79.7	74.4
11	SA2	YOLOv11l-seg	150	16	1.64	80.8	77.8
12	I2	YOLOv11n-seg	100	25	0.68	97.5	98.4
13	Suture 3	YOLOv11l-seg	150	10	21.83	91.5	87.2
14	Suture 3	YOLOv11l-seg	200	16	28.02	92.0	87.3
15	Sut2	YOLOv11l-seg	200	16	7.40	95.7	89.8
16	Sut3	YOLOv11l-seg	200	16	3.67	95.6	90.3

ASN – Augmented Surgical Needle; AI – AI Suture; SA - Segmentación de aguja 2; I2 – Instance2; TM6 (or Trained Model 6) refers to the trained model obtained from the sixth training (in the above row); TM8 (or Trained Model 8) refers to the trained model obtained from the eighth training (in the above row).

Figure 4.16: YOLOv11 Models Training Results

As shown in Table 4.5, sixteen CV models were trained. As observed in Figure 4.16a, the models which achieved relatively low precision and recall values are the Trained Models 8, 10 and 11, with the Trained Models 5, 9 and 12 presenting higher percentages in precision and recall. Further, Figure 4.16b demonstrates the computation time with respect to each CV model’s training, with the Trained Models 13 and 14 yielding a relatively higher computation time. This is expected since the *Suture3* dataset is larger by several thousands of images with respect to the other datasets. As such, training linked to this particular dataset is at least three times longer than the other training displayed in Table 4.5.

After testing the datasets obtained from *Roboflow*, the YOLOv11 models were also determined to be inadequate to be applied for the detection of suturing tools in the captured videos, despite the increase that YOLOv11 yield in the validation values. Indeed, the suturing tools datasets that are publicly accessible are mainly comprised

of top-view static images of suturing tools laying on a table. Thus, although the models may present high precision and recall values for static suturing objects, they cannot accurately detect suturing tools during the suturing task procedure, due to the fact that they are being grasped, manoeuvred and slightly obstructed at times.

Figure 4.17 provides an example of an image taken from the *Instance2* dataset, composed of two straight haemostats represented in orange, two straight-tipped surgical scissors represented in blue, one hilt represented in yellow and one needle forceps represented in red.

Figure 4.17: Example of Image of the *Instance2* Dataset Showcasing Surgical Tools Annotations

In Figure 4.18 and Figure 4.19, the Trained Model 12 is used in a video for suturing tools detection. It is clearly observed the lack of adequacy in applying this model to the captured suturing videos. It is also noted that the Trained Model 12 is associated with the highest precision and recall values.

Figure 4.18: Examples of Object Detection by Trained Model 12

Figure 4.19: Another Example of Object Detection by Trained Model 12

The results obtained from the remaining training of the YOLOv11 models may be found in Appendix B.

Also, since the creation of a novel suturing tools dataset is deemed necessary, the *needle* label is now included in the list of objects to be detected and segmented, eliminating the need for a CV model dedicated solely to detecting and segmenting the needle.

As a result, because only the *Suture3*, *Sut2* and *Sut3* datasets are adequate for training the YOLOv11 models to apply to the suturing videos captured, the YOLOv11 models considered the most promising are Trained Models 14 and 16, which display precision values of 92.0% and 95.6%, and recall values of 87.3% and 90.3%, respectively. It is noted that the Trained Model 14 is dedicated to surgical suturing tools detection and segmentation, and the Trained Model 16 is focused on the end-product's suture components detection and segmentation.

Table 4.6 displays the results obtained in the YOLOv11 training in TM14, regarding the accuracy of the bounding boxes.

Table 4.6: Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM14 with YOLOv11 Models with Bounding Boxes

Object	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	mAP50 (%)	mAP50-95 (%)
Laceration	97.5	85.8	94.8	75.0
Left Hand	94.9	96.9	98.1	97.4
Needle	80.5	59.5	64.0	41.6
Needle Holder	92.5	95.5	96.2	89.1
Right Hand	92.9	97.6	98.7	95.5
Suture	89.0	79.8	86.1	52.8
Suture Cutting Scissors	95.4	94.8	97.4	95.7
Toothed Forceps	93.7	88.2	89.9	84.2
Overall	92.0	87.3	90.7	78.9

Table 4.7 displays the results obtained in the YOLOv11 training in TM14, regarding the accuracy of the masks (objects' contours).

Table 4.7: Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM14 with YOLOv11 Models with Masks.

Object	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	mAP50 (%)	mAP50-95 (%)
Laceration	76.3	67.0	74.6	39.3
Left Hand	95.0	96.9	98.1	95.5
Needle	68.9	50.5	51.8	18.9
Needle Holder	93.3	96.2	96.1	73.8
Right Hand	93.3	98.0	98.7	89.6
Suture	74.9	67.1	66.1	27.4
Suture Cutting Scissors	95.9	95.3	97.6	86.6
Toothed Forceps	94.1	88.6	92.0	71.4
Overall	86.5	82.5	84.4	62.8

Concerning the training of Trained Model 14 (TM14), Table 4.6 shows the objects' bounding boxes precision, recall, mAP50 and mAP-50-95 values, while Table 4.7 shows the objects' masks precision, recall, mAP50 and mAP50-95 values. The objects associated with the highest percentages are the right hand, the left hand and the suture cutting scissors, whereas the objects that have been the hardest to detect are the needle and the suture. Indeed, the needle is deemed to be a relatively difficult object to detect and segment due to its small size, ability to reflect light and its different appearances based on the point of view.

Similarly, the YOLOV11 models were trained with the newly augmented datasets for the end-product image analysis, *Sut 2* and *Sut 3*. It is noted that the Trained Model 16 (TM16) presents the most promising results with 95.6% precision and 90.3% recall.

Table 4.8 presents the results obtained in the YOLOv11 training in TM16, regarding the accuracy of the bounding boxes.

Table 4.8: Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM16 with YOLOv11 Models with Bounding Boxes

Object	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	mAP50 (%)	mAP50-95 (%)
Knot	97.3	97.2	99.1	67.0
Laceration	92.9	86.8	94.6	71.3
Suture	96.6	86.8	93.9	59.0
Overall	95.6	90.3	95.9	65.7

Table 4.9 presents the results obtained in the YOLOv11 training in TM16, regarding the accuracy of the masks.

Table 4.9: Parameters and Results Obtained in the Training of TM16 with YOLOv11 Models with Masks

Object	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	mAP50 (%)	mAP50-95 (%)
Knot	72.2	71.5	72.5	27.1
Laceration	85.6	78.9	82.9	35.1
Suture	62.1	55.2	56.0	28.8
Overall	73.3	68.6	70.5	30.3

Regarding the training of Trained Model 16, Table 4.8 shows the objects' bounding boxes precision, recall, mAP50 and mAP-50-95 values, while Table 4.9 shows the objects' masks precision, recall, mAP50 and mAP50-95 values. It is noted that the object associated with the highest precision percentage is the laceration, while the suture scores the lowest precision percentage, a result explained by the fact that leftovers can obstruct or be mistaken by a suture by the CV model.

Figures 4.20 and 4.21 display the results from the most promising models' training and validation, which highlight, throughout the training time, a reduction tendency in loss values and an augmentation tendency in precision, recall, mean Average Precision 50 values and mean Average Precision 50-95 values.

Figure 4.20: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 14

Figure 4.21: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 16

Figures 4.22 and 4.23 display the predictions performed by the most promising trained models: the YOLOv11 Trained Model 14, concerning the suturing tools dataset (Figure 4.22) and the YOLOv11 Trained Model 16, concerning the key suture components dataset (Figure 4.23).

Figure 4.22: Validation Image Obtained from the Trained Model 14

Figure 4.23: Validation Image Obtained from the Trained Model 16

4.2.7 Software Development Using Traditional CV Techniques

After having trained the YOLO models to adopt in the novel SUGAR automated suturing skills assessment and grading tool, and following the clear identification and definition of the suture quality metrics to consider for the validation of the CV-based SUGAR tool, the software development work starts.

The software development work in the Thesis involves the design and implementation in the SUGAR tool's code of relevant suture quality metrics to be assessed and graded. Firstly, it is addressed the suture quality metric applicable to the human-based input, then, the suture quality metrics applicable to the assessment of the HD suturing videos and, finally, the suture quality metrics applicable to the assessment of the end-product images of simple interrupted sutures, performed by surgical trainees and surgical trainers at the RCSI facilities.

Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Human-based Input

The Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure) metric

The *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure) choices metric* is the one metric that is assessed before the start of the video analysis. Three questions are asked to the surgical trainee on how to perform the suture regarding the appropriate size, absorbability and structure of the suture, in a forearm laceration. The surgical trainee selects the answer to each of the questions, with the associated result pending the correct answer to each question. If the surgical trainee answers at least one of the questions incorrectly, this metric is considered as *Not Done*, otherwise it is considered *Done*.

Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suturing Videos

The seven metrics assessed by the novel SUGAR tool's video analysis use the YOLO algorithms for object detection and segmentation in each frame, enabling the SUGAR tool to analyse the suturing videos as individual images.

It is noted that most of the suture quality assessment metrics applied to suturing videos are subjected to an analysis performed in two sequential stages, one determining whether the metric is performed correctly in each suture during the suturing task, and the other focusing on whether the metric is performed correctly throughout the suturing task, an assessment performed as soon as the suturing task is concluded. There is only one exception to this process: the *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder* metric is only assessed once, during the suturing task. Also, while the *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers* metric undergoes a two-stage analysis, it is not focused on the individual sutures, but whether the left or the right hands have held the needle.

In the SUGAR tool analysis, and to ensure a more precise calculation of these outputs, the rationale for each of the metrics is fine-tuned and refined as the CV model is tested in different validation runs. Specific thresholds are therefore defined and implemented in the code, based on the interpretation of the surgical experts' assessment reviews, to deliver superior assessment capability.

The first step for the assessment of the suture quality metrics in suturing videos is to store all the relevant coordinate points of the detected objects' segmentation. For each, the duplicate coordinate points are removed, and the remaining are reordered

from the lowest y value to the highest y value, that is, from the top coordinate point to the bottom coordinate point, respectively.

Laceration

If a laceration is detected, the left coordinate point, which is associated with the lowest x value, and the right coordinate point, which is associated with the highest x value, are stored. Then, if a coordinate point is within 20 pixels to the right of the left coordinate point, it is also stored as the left edge of the laceration.

Needle holder

If a needle holder is detected, the bottom coordinate point, associated with the lowest x value, and the right coordinate point, associated with the highest x value, are stored. Since the needle holder is held at an angle, the bottom coordinate point corresponds to the start of the left edge of the needle holder. Then, if a coordinate point is within 100 pixels from the bottom coordinate point and to its left, it is stored as part of the needle holder's left edge. If a coordinate point shares the same x value as the right coordinate point, it is stored as part of the needle holder's right edge. In addition, if a coordinate point is below the right coordinate point, within 150 pixels from its y value and within 40 pixels from its x value, it is also stored as part of the needle holder's right edge. Finally, if a coordinate point is within 150 pixels from the y value of the bottom coordinate point, it is stored as the bottom portion of the needle holder.

Needle

If a needle is detected, the top coordinate point, associated with the lowest y value, the right coordinate point, associated with the highest x value, and the left coordinate point, associated with the lowest x value, are stored. All coordinate points are stored as part of the needle. Then, if a coordinate point is located within 120 pixels from the x value of the right coordinate point, below its y value and to the right of the left coordinate point, it is stored as part of the right needle edge to be analysed during needle insertion, one of the quality suture metrics, which approximately constitutes a U shape. Finally, if a coordinate point is located within 50 pixels from the x value of the right coordinate point and to the right of the left coordinate point, then it is stored as part of the right needle edge to be analysed in other quality suture metrics.

Toothed Forceps

If a toothed forceps is detected, the bottom coordinate point, associated with the highest x value, and the left coordinate point, associated with the lowest x value, are stored. Then, if a coordinate point is within 200 pixels from the y value of the bottom coordinate point, it is stored as part of the bottom portion of the toothed forceps.

Suture

If a suture is detected, it is stored.

Right Hand

If a right hand is detected, all coordinate points are stored as part of the right hand.

Left Hand

If a left hand is detected, the box width, which is the value associated with the distance between the x values of left coordinate point and of the right coordinate point, and the left coordinate point, associated with the lowest x value, are stored. All coordinate points are stored as part of the left hand.

Correct placement of needle within the needle holder metric

To implement the *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder* metric, a laceration, a needle holder and a needle must be detected by the model. When the needle holder is at most 150 pixels away from the laceration, each side of the needle holder is analysed and a best fit line, also known as a linear regression line, is applied to the coordinates of each edge, calculating the slope, a , and the y -intercept, b , as represented in Equation 4.1:

$$y = a \times x + b \tag{4.1}$$

The following figures enable the visualisation of this metric. Figure 4.24 shows the image of a correct needle placement. In Figure 4.25, the orange dots represent the left edge of the needle holder, with a red line representing the linear regression line associated with them, whereas the blue dots represent the right edge of the needle holder, with the green line representing the linear regression line associated with them. The graphic corresponds to the right and left edges of the needle holder.

Figure 4.24: *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder Metric by the SUGAR Tool*

Figure 4.25: The Needle Holder's Right and Left Edges And Associated Linear Regression Lines

It is noted that the y value in the pixels appears visually upside down due to the fact that, in image, the pixel $[0,0]$ is located at the top left corner. As such, the y value increases when a point is located further down.

If the right edge happens to consist of coordinate points that share the same x value, the values for the linear regression line are not possible to calculate, given that the slope, a , would be infinite. In this case, the total length of the needle is calculated by

the sum of the distance between each right edge coordinate point and, to establish whether the needle is being grabbed at $2/3$ of the needle point, the distance between each right edge coordinate point is calculated, up until the needle holder's right edge.

In contrast, if the right edge does not consist solely of coordinate points with the same x value, the values for the linear regression line are calculated. By averaging the needle holder's edges slopes and y -intercepts, the resulting linear regression line represents the approximate middle of the needle holder, depicted in purple in Figure 4.26.

Figure 4.26: Representation of the Middle of the Needle Holder

Then, the intersection between the middle linear regression line and the needle is calculated. If this intersection contains several coordinate points, the total needle length is calculated similarly to the previous method. The length of the needle's right edge is calculated up until the left intersection coordinate point, associated with the lowest x value.

In Figure 4.27, it is demonstrated the left and right needle holder edges, represented by the orange and the blue dots, respectively, and their respective linear regression lines, represented by the purple and the red lines, respectively. In addition, the middle linear regression line is represented by the brown line and the needle is represented in green, with their intersection marked in yellow.

Figure 4.27: Graphic of the *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder* Metric by the SUGAR Tool

By calculating the ratio between the total needle length and the length of the needle up until the relevant coordinate point of the needle holder, a value between 0 and 1 is obtained that represents the approximate point at which the needle is being held. This ratio is calculated throughout 15 frames (half a second of video), and averaged to obtain the mean of the point at which the needle is grasped by the needle holder. This average is only calculated at the 15th frame and, if this average is between the values 0.30 and 0.91, the placement of the needle within the needle holder is considered correct, otherwise it is considered incorrect.

If the number of frames with respect to the *Insertion of needle at the right angle to skin* metric reaches its limit before the number of frames with respect to the *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder* metric reaches its limit, then the placement is considered incorrect. This is because there are too few intersections detected, which translate to the participant grasping the needle too close to its end point. When this happens, the needle becomes harder to detect from the point where the needle holder is grasping it. Without producing frames with the necessary calculations, an intersection is not detected.

Once the suturing task concludes, the SUGAR tool returns the values for the *Correct placement of needle within needle holder* metric calculated at the 15th frame and indicates if the metric was performed correctly (average between the values of 0.30 and 0.91) with a *Done* result. If the placement of the needle in needle holder is not

deemed correct, the metric is considered *Not Done*.

Insertion of needle at the right angle to skin metric

This metric is subjected to two analyses. The first concerning whether it is being correctly performed in each particular suture, while the latter focuses on the overall performance throughout the suturing task.

To implement the *Insertion of needle at the right angle to skin* metric, a toothed forceps, a laceration, a needle holder and a needle must be detected. If the needle's right coordinate point is within 40 pixels from the x value of the laceration's left coordinate point, the top coordinate points' x values and the bottom coordinate points' x values of the needle's right edge are stored. The top coordinate points correspond to all coordinate points that belong to the needle's right edge and own the lowest y value. Similarly, the bottom coordinate points correspond to all coordinate points that belong to the needle's right edge and own the highest y value.

Then, the top coordinate points' maximum x value and the bottom coordinate points' maximum x value are associated with the lowest y value and highest y value, respectively. Hence, it is possible to obtain the top right and the bottom right corners of the needle, as can be observed in Figure 4.28.

Figure 4.28: Graphic of the *Insertion of needle at the right angle to skin* Metric by the SUGAR Tool

The needle's right edge coordinate points are represented in blue, with the top right and bottom right corners represented in green and orange, respectively. Finally,

the difference between the x values of the two corners is calculated for 30 frames (1 second of video). When a new suture is detected, the distances calculated are averaged and, if the mean is a value below 16, then the insertion for the suture is considered correct, otherwise it is considered incorrect. A new suture is only detected with more than 15 frames (half a second of video), thus avoiding possible misdetection moments of new sutures throughout the video analysis.

It is noted that the values collected to analyse whether the insertion was performed at the correct angle with respect to the skin are not deleted when a new suture is detected. Indeed, this method was compared with the method of deleting the prior collected values and restarting the analysis: when the values were not restarted, the performance of the SUGAR tool regarding this particular metric increased by 40.00% in accuracy, 43.75% in precision and 25.00% in recall.

Once the suturing task concludes and the two-stage video analysis assessment is complete, the SUGAR tool returns the values for the *Insertion of needle at the right angle to skin* metric, presenting the ratio between the number of correct insertions and the total number of insertions. If this ratio is over 0.5, then the tool displays the metric as *Done*, otherwise the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

Needle inserted and removed using supination metric

To implement the *Needle inserted and removed using supination* metric, two different analyses are performed: one is focused on whether the insertion of the needle was performed using supination, while the other dedicated to whether the removal of the needle was performed using supination.

For the insertion analysis, a needle holder must be detected and the number of frames in which the insertion distance has been calculated needs to be at least 11, since the participants usually puncture the suturing pad approximately after 12 frames of calculating the insertion distances. Whenever this is true, a new frame for the insertion using supination is identified. For the first 10 frames, the difference between the x values of the needle holder's right coordinate point and left coordinate point is stored as the initial approximate width value for the needle holder. Between the 50th and 60th frames (2 seconds of video), the difference between the x values of the needle holder's right coordinate point and left coordinate point is also stored as the final approximate width value for the needle holder. If the number of frames reaches 110, these final values are discarded and recalculated and stored until the 120th frame (4 seconds of video). Similarly, the process is repeated on the 170th frame up until the 180th frame (6 seconds of video), on the 230th frame up until the

240th frame (8 seconds of video), and on the 270th frame up until the 280th frame (over 9 seconds of video).

Before reaching the 280th frame, if the needle is detected and its top coordinate point is over 75 pixels away from the needle holder's bottom coordinate point, no more frames are analysed, and the latest values are used for the supination analysis. In addition, if a laceration is detected and the needle holder's bottom coordinate point is located to the right of the laceration's right coordinate point, no more frames are analysed, with the latest values being used for the supination analysis.

With the latest values collected, the start and final values are each averaged and, if the difference between the start mean and the final mean is below the value of 35 pixels in the x axis, it is considered that the insertion of the needle was performed using supination and, thus it is performed correctly, otherwise it is performed incorrectly.

For the removal analysis, the insertion analysis must be conducted and a toothed forceps, a laceration, a needle holder and a needle must be detected. Also, the needle holder's bottom coordinate point and the needle's right coordinate point must both be located to the right of the laceration's right coordinate point. When this is true, the intersection between the needle holder's bottom coordinate points and the needle's coordinate points is calculated. If there is an intersection, then the needle's removal process has started. Similarly, if there is an intersection between the forceps's bottom coordinate points and the needle's coordinate points, the needle's removal process has started. This addresses both participants who remove the needle using the needle holder or using the toothed forceps.

Once the needle removal process starts, 60 consecutive frames are analysed. For the first 10 frames, the difference between the x values of the needle holder's right and left coordinate points is calculated and stored as the initial approximate width value for the needle holder. Between the 20th and 30th frames (1 second of video), the difference between the x values of the needle holder's right coordinate point and left coordinate point is also stored as the final approximate width value for the needle holder. If the number of frames reaches 50, these final values are discarded and recalculated and stored until the 60th frame (2 seconds of video).

Before reaching the 60th frame, if the needle holder is no longer detected or if its left coordinate point's y value is below 100 pixels, no more frames are analysed, with the latest values being used for the supination analysis. This ensures that, once the participant has fully removed the needle in less than 2 seconds of video, these values are no longer calculated.

With the latest values collected, the start and final values are each averaged and, if the difference between the start mean and the final mean is below the value of 35, it is considered that the removal of the needle was performed using supination and, therefore, it is correctly performed, otherwise it is performed incorrectly.

If the analyses determine the use of supination, then the final output for the *Needle inserted and removed using supination* metric is *Done*, otherwise it is *Not Done*.

When a new suture is detected, all supination variables and values are restarted to be analysed anew for the new suture.

Once the suturing task concludes, the final analysis of this metric occurs and the *Needle insertion and removal using supination* metric calculates the ratio between the number of correct movements using supination, regardless of whether it concerns insertion or removal, and the total number of supination analyses executed. If this ratio is at least 0.5, then the tool exhibits the metric as *Done*, otherwise the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges metric

This metric is subjected to two analyses. The first concerning whether it is being correctly performed in each particular suture, while the latter focuses on the overall performance throughout the suturing task.

To implement the *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges* metric, two different analyses are conducted: one refers to the needle's insertion, while the other deals with the needle's removal, taking advantage of the code created for analysing the use of supination on both the needle's insertion and removal.

For the needle's insertion analysis, the difference between the x values of the needle's right coordinate point and the laceration's left coordinate point is calculated and stored, whenever a needle and a laceration are detected during the first 10 frames (one third of a second). In Figure 4.30, the needle is represented in blue, with its right coordinate point marked in orange, and a green dot represents the laceration's left coordinate point. In this case, the relevant difference is approximately 30 pixels.

Figure 4.29: *Insertion and exit of needle approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges Metric by the SUGAR Tool*

Figure 4.30: *Graphic of the Insertion and exit of needle approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges Metric*

If frame 50 is reached, these values are discarded and recalculated for the next 10 frames as long as both a needle and a laceration are detected. The process is repeated: from the 110th frame up to the 120th frame (4 seconds of video), from the 170th frame up to the 180th frame (6 seconds of video), from the 230th frame up to the

240th frame (8 seconds of video), and from the 270th frame up to the 280th frame (over 9 seconds of video).

Before reaching the 280th frame, if the needle is detected and its top coordinate point is over 75 pixels away from the needle holder's bottom coordinate point, no more frames are analysed, with the latest values being used for the needle's insertion analysis. In addition, if a laceration is detected and the needle holder's bottom coordinate point is located to the right of the laceration's right coordinate point, no more frames are analysed, with the latest values being used for the needle's insertion distance.

With the latest needle insertion distance values calculated, their average is extracted and, if the mean is above 30 and below 50 pixels in the x axis, then the insertion is deemed to have been performed at the correct distance, otherwise it is considered to be performed at an incorrect distance.

For the removal, once the needle removal process has started, 60 consecutive frames are analysed. For the first 10 frames, the difference between the x values of the laceration's right coordinate point and needle's left coordinate point is calculated and stored. If the 20th frame is reached and no values have been stored yet, then it calculates those values for the next 10 frames. Similarly, if the 50th frame is reached and no values have been stored yet, then they are calculated and stored for the next 10 frames. This ensures that, if no needle is detected at first, these values are calculated as soon as it is detected.

Before reaching the 60th frame, if the needle holder is no longer detected or its left coordinate point's y value is below 100 pixels, no more frames are analysed, with the latest values being used for the needle's removal analysis. This ensures that, once the participant has fully removed the needle in less than 2 seconds of video, these values are no longer calculated.

With the distance values collected, the average is calculated and, if it is below 15 and above 80 pixels in the x axis, then the removal is considered to have been performed at the correct distance from the laceration and, therefore, it is correct for the particular suture, otherwise it is incorrect.

When a new suture is detected, all distance variables and values are restarted to be analysed anew for the new suture.

Once the suturing task concludes and the final two-stage video analysis assessment is complete, the SUGAR tool returns the values for the *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges* metric, calculating the ratio between

the number of movements executed at a correct distance, regardless of whether it concerns the needle's insertion or removal, and the total number of executed movements. If this ratio is at least 0.25, then the SUGAR tool displays the metric as *Done*, otherwise the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

One pass of needle per suture insertion metric

To implement the *One pass of needle per suture insertion* metric, two different analyses are employed: one addresses whether the participant hesitates before puncturing the needle through the suturing pad, while the other focuses on whether the participant removes the needle backwards after having punctured the suturing pad.

For the first case, a toothed forceps, the laceration, a needle holder and a needle must be detected. Also, the number of frames in which the insertion distance is calculated needs to be lower than 11, for participants usually puncture the suturing pad approximately after 12 frames of calculating the insertion distances.

If the needle's right coordinate point is over 200 pixels away from the x value of the laceration's left coordinate point for over 10 consecutive frames, then it is considered that the participant hesitated before puncturing the suturing pad. This conclusion restarts all the insertion, supination and distance variables in order to analyse these values only when the participant performs the needle's insertion and removal for the particular suture.

For the second case, a needle holder, a laceration and a needle must be detected. Also, the number of frames in which the insertion distance has been calculated needs to be at least 11 and the number of frames in which the width value for the needle holder during the needle's removal phase has been calculated needs to be lower than 61. This ensures that, if the participant already inserted the needle and removes it to start the suture again, the additional pass is detected.

Similarly to the first case, if the needle's right coordinate point is over 200 pixels away from the x value of the laceration's left coordinate point for over 10 consecutive frames, then it is considered that the participant removed the needle backwards, which restarts the insertion, supination and distance variables, in order to analyse these values only when the participant performs the needle's insertion and removal for the particular suture.

It is noted that some participants insert and remove the needle out of the first wound edge to then insert it at depth on the other wound edge and remove it. This is deemed to be correct, despite presenting 2 insertions and 2 removals in total. In

order to duly consider this situation, if (1) there are a laceration and a needle, (2) no locking of suture has been performed, (3) the needle's right coordinate point is to the left of the laceration's left coordinate point and (4) the use of supination during removal has been analysed, then the results related to the use of supination during removal are removed and the values for the use of supination during insertion and removal are restarted to be analysed again.

When a new suture is detected, if there is at least one identification of an additional pass performed, then the metric is considered to have been performed incorrectly, otherwise it is correct. Then, the variables and values regarding the identification of additional passes are restarted to be analysed anew for the next suture.

Once the suturing task concludes and the final two-stage video analysis assessment is complete, the SUGAR tool returns the values for the *One pass of needle per suture insertion* metric, estimating the ratio between the number of sutures executed with one pass and the total number of sutures performed. If this ratio is at least 0.75, then the SUGAR tool displays the metric as *Done*, otherwise the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot metric

To implement the *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot* metric, the use of supination during insertion must have been analysed and a left hand must be detected. If the x value of the left hand's left coordinate point is a value below 600 pixels and the width of the left hand's bounding box is over 1300 pixels, then the locking of suture is deemed to have been demonstrated. In Figure 4.31, the locking of a suture is demonstrated.

Figure 4.31: Demonstrated Locking of Suture When Performing the Surgeons Knot

When a new suture is detected, if the locking of suture has already been demonstrated, the metric is deemed to be correctly performed for the particular suture, otherwise it is considered to have been performed incorrectly. Then, the variables and values concerning the locking of suture are restarted to analyse anew the next suture.

Once the suturing task concludes and the final two-stage video analysis assessment is complete, the SUGAR tool returns the values for the *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot* metric, computing the ratio between the number of successful suture locks and the total number of sutures performed. If this ratio is over 0.4, then the metric is displayed as *Done*, otherwise the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

Handled needle with forceps, not fingers metric

To implement the *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers* metric, two different analyses are executed. For one of the analyses, a needle, a right hand, a toothed forceps and a laceration must be detected. If there is an intersection between the needle and the right hand for more than 5 consecutive frames, then it is concluded that the needle has been handled by the right hand. Similarly, for the other analysis, a needle, a left hand, a toothed forceps and a laceration must be detected. If there is an intersection between the needle and the left hand for more than 5 consecutive frames, then it is concluded that the needle has been handled by the left hand.

Figure 4.32: Demonstrated Handling of Needle With Fingers

Once the suturing task concludes and the final two-stage video analysis assessment is complete, the SUGAR tool returns the values for the *Handled needle with forceps*,

not fingers metric, examining the number of frames in which the needle has been handled by a hand. If this number is below 15 frames, then the metric is displayed as *Done*, otherwise the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suture End-Product Images

Completed the design and implementation of the one suture quality metric associated with input analysis, conducted before the suturing task starts, and of the seven suture quality metrics applicable to the assessment of the suturing videos, the novel SUGAR suturing skills assessment and grading tool was also designed and developed to include the five suture quality metrics applicable to the assessment of suture end-product imagery.

It is noted that all suture quality assessment metrics applied to the suture end-product images undergo a two-stage analysis. With the exception of the *Suture tension appropriate* metric, the first analysis determines whether the metric was performed correctly in each pair of sutures, and the latter focuses on whether the metric was performed correctly for the overall suture. Indeed, the *Suture tension appropriate* metric analyses firstly whether too much tension is applied, while the latter analysis determines whether too little tension is present.

In the two-stage analysis, and to ensure a more precise calculation of these outputs, the rationale for each of the metrics is fine-tuned and refined as the CV model is tested in different validation runs. Specific thresholds are therefore defined and implemented in the code, based on the interpretation of the surgical experts' assessment reviews, to deliver superior assessment capability.

For the assessment analysis, the first step is to store all the relevant coordinate points of the detected objects' segmentations.

Suture

If a suture is detected, two different sets of coordinate points are stored: the first set comprises the normalised right and left extremities' x and y values, whereas the second set encompasses the original right and left extremities' pixel x and y values.

For the first set, the right coordinate point, associated with the highest normalised x value, and the left coordinate point, associated with the lowest normalised x value, are stored. Then, all coordinate points' normalised x values are averaged for all coordinate points with the highest normalised x value and with the lowest normalised

x value. This allows to obtain approximately the right and left extremities of each suture.

Similarly, for the second set, the right coordinate point, associated with the highest x value, and the left coordinate point, associated with the lowest x value, are stored. Then, all coordinate points' x values are averaged for all coordinate points with the highest x value and with the lowest x value. This allows to obtain approximately the right and left extremities of each suture.

Figure 4.33a shows the image of a final result of a suturing process (i.e., suture end-product). In Figure 4.33b, the sutures are represented in purple, with the averaged left extremities highlighted in red and the right extremities highlighted in green for the original pixel x and y values.

(a) Suture End-Product

(b) Representation of a Suture by the SUGAR Tool

Figure 4.33: Suture End-Product and its Representation by the SUGAR Tool

Following the storing of all relevant suture coordinates, the SUGAR tool reorganises both sets of coordinates in ascending order of the y values, resulting in the reordering of the suture extremities from top to bottom suture.

All sutures parallel to each other metric

To implement the *All sutures parallel to each other* metric, each pair of consecutive sutures is analysed separately. For each pair, the suture orientation is calculated for each suture and compared. The suture orientation refers to the angle of the line formed by the suture's right and left extremities in relation to a horizontal line. This metric is achieved with the normalised suture coordinate points (between 0 and 1).

Figure 4.34: *All sutures parallel to each other* Metric by the SUGAR Tool

In Figure 4.34, the suture's right and left extremities are represented in blue, as well as the line formed by them, and the horizontal line is represented in red. The angle formed by both lines is calculated for each and compared with the next suture. In this case, four comparisons are made, where the absolute difference between the angles is calculated and, if it corresponds to a value below 5° , then the next sutures are considered parallel to each other, and considered unparallel otherwise. Finally, when all comparisons are completed, the percentage of the amount of parallel suture

comparisons over the total amount of comparisons is calculated and, if the value is at least 50%, the metric is displayed as *Done* and displayed *Not Done* otherwise.

All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound metric

To implement the *All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound* metric, two different analyses are performed: the first analysis focuses on the left suture coordinate points placement, while the second analysis is centred on the right suture coordinate points placement. This metric is achieved with normalised suture coordinate points.

In Figure 4.35, the left suture coordinate points are represented in red, with a line representing the average of their x values in blue. Similarly, the right suture coordinate points are represented in green, with a line representing the average of their x values in orange.

Figure 4.35: *All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound* Metric by the SUGAR Tool

For the first analysis, the left suture coordinate points' x values are averaged. Then, the absolute difference between each x value and the mean is calculated, with the suture's extremity deemed to be placed equidistantly from the wound when the value is below 0.017. However, if there is at least one calculated value above 0.03, the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

For the second analysis, the right suture coordinate points' x values are averaged. Then, the absolute difference between each x value and the mean is calculated, with the suture's extremity deemed to be placed equidistantly from the wound when the value is below or equal to 0.01. However, if there is at least one calculated value above 0.03, the metric is displayed as *Not Done*.

Lastly, the percentage of equidistant suture extremities with respect to the total number of suture extremities is calculated and, if the value is at least 90%, then the metric is displayed as *Done* and displayed *Not Done* otherwise.

It is noted that this implementation has been compared with SUGAR Lite's bite sizes method. This new implementation is the selected one, as it increases the overall model's accuracy by 13.60% and recall by 50.00%, whereas the precision decreases by 16.70%.

Distance between sutures appropriate metric

To implement the *Distance between sutures appropriate* metric, each pair of consecutive sutures is analysed separately. For each pair, the distance between the left coordinate points and the distance between the right coordinate points are obtained and averaged. If this mean is a value between 0.055 and 0.095, the distance between the pair of sutures is considered appropriate, and considered non-appropriate otherwise. This metric is achieved using the normalised suture coordinate points (between 0 and 1).

Once all suture pairs have been analysed, the percentage of appropriate distance between sutures and the number of suture pairs is calculated. If this ratio is at least 50%, then the metric is displayed as *Done* and displayed as *Not Done* otherwise.

Distance between sutures equal metric

To implement the *Distance between sutures equal* metric, the code used for the *Distance between sutures appropriate* metric is leveraged. The distances between each suture pair are averaged and each suture pair is analysed separately. This metric is

obtained using the normalised suture coordinate points (between 0 and 1).

For each suture pair, the absolute difference between the calculated mean and the distance between the particular sutures is extracted and, if this value is below 0.025, the distance is considered equal. Once all suture pairs have been analysed, the percentage of equal distances with respect to the number of suture pairs is calculated and, if this value is at least 50%, then the metric is displayed as *Done* and displayed as *Not Done* otherwise.

Suture tension appropriate metric

Lastly, to address the *Suture tension appropriate* metric, the pixels' Red, Green and Blue (RGB) values are extracted. This metric is acquired with the original suture coordinate points. In order to analyse whether there is inappropriate tension applied, two different analyses are applied. The first analysis reveals whether there is too much tension applied resulting in an elevated bump throughout the suture and around the laceration, whereas the second analysis discloses whether not enough tension is applied, causing a gap between sutures.

To implement the analysis of the application of too much tension, each pair of consecutive sutures is analysed separately. For each pair, 15 pixels are identified as relevant, as observed in Figure 4.36. The suture's extremities are represented in blue and there are 9 pixels belonging to the space between the sutures represented in red and 6 pixels belonging to the space not affected by the suture in the suturing pad represented in green. The inside pixels are obtained by marking $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{3}{4}$ of the distance between the y values of the left suture coordinate points and $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{3}{4}$ of the distance between the x values of the extremities of the pair's top suture. Similarly, the outside pixels, are obtained by marking $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{3}{4}$ of the distance between the i values of the left suture coordinate points and adding $\frac{1}{2}$ of the distance between the x values of the extremities of the pair's top suture to each extremity.

Figure 4.36: *Suture tension appropriate* Metric for Excessive Tension Analysis by the SUGAR Tool

With the relevant pixels identified, their intensity is calculated using the standard NTSC (National Television System Committee) conversion formula [123] used for calculating the effective luminance of a pixel being represented by the following equation:

$$Intensity = 0.299 \times R + 0.587 \times G + 0.114 \times B \quad (4.2)$$

with the R, G, B representing the pixel values pertaining to the red, green and blue matrices, respectively. The intensities of the inside pixels and the outside pixels are averaged. If the absolute difference between these means is a value above 2, then the metric is displayed as *Not Done*. This metric assesses whether the inside pixels appear brighter, which correlates with an increased tension applied in the suture.

To implement the analysis of the application of too little tension, the inside pixels located at $\frac{1}{2}$ of the distance between the x values of the pair's top suture extremities are considered placed approximately on top of the laceration. In Figure 4.37, the gap pixels are represented in red, with the other inside pixels represented in green and the suture extremities represented in blue. Similarly, the intensities of the gap pixels and the other inside pixels are averaged each. If the absolute difference between these means is a value above 2, then the metric is displayed as *Not Done*. This metric assesses whether the gap pixels appear darker, which correlates with an absence of tension applied in the suture, causing gaps between the sutures.

Figure 4.37: *Suture tension appropriate* Metric for Insufficient Tension Analysis by the SUGAR Tool

When both analyses are concluded for all suture pairs, if there are no absolute differences above the value 2, then the metric is displayed as *Done* and displayed as *Not Done* otherwise.

Chapter 5

Experimental Results

This chapter presents the results of the novel SUGAR surgical suturing grader tool. These results represent the outcomes and data obtained from real-world evidence grounded in actual observation and measurements, offering a concrete basis for analyses. The chapter describes the experimental results obtained from the analysis of suture quality metrics and the results ensuing from the validation of the system using a comparative analysis of the suture quality metrics between the novel SUGAR automated surgical suturing grader and the traditional human-based suturing skills assessment and grading system, also considering the application of the *Inter-Rater Reliability* indicator. It is important to note that the SUGAR experimental results aim to foster reproducibility and significance.

5.1 Suture Quality Analysis Through Metrics

The novel CV-based suturing skills assessment and grading tool assesses the suturing skills of the participants by analysing the human input and the suturing videos and imagery based on the implemented suture quality metrics, hard-coded in the SUGAR tool using traditional CV techniques.

For the suture quality analysis, it is noted that the suturing videos performed by left-handed participants were not considered, for the Proof-of-Concept of the SUGAR tool is designed to detect and identify suturing movements performed by right-handed participants. As a result, from the captured 51 videos, a total of 45 suturing videos were analysed. Also, the *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure)* metric was not assessed by the tool, for it is based on console inputs and not in CV-based video analysis. Further, the assessment

of image 757345 only identified one suture, compromising all end-product assessment metrics and resulting on the exclusion of this image from the validation. Overall, a total of 50 suture end-product images were analysed.

5.1.1 Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Human-based Input

The *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure) metric* analyses whether the participant chooses the correct suture, on size, absorbability and structure, for a forearm laceration. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Results Obtained for the *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure) Metric*

Video Number	Size	Absorbability	Structure	Final Score
114576	2-0	Absorbable	Monofilament	Not Done
124269	4-0	Absorbable	Monofilament	Not Done
136793	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
179892	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
208773	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
210072	4-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
237435	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
248992	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
249076	4-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
263779	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
269939	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
276273	4-0	Absorbable	Monofilament	Not Done
291008	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
307232	4-0	Absorbable	Monofilament	Not Done
312377	4-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
318727	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
366649	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
389990	4-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
393574	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
432109	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
455439	4-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
460500	4-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
479135	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done

509697	3-0	Absorbable	Monofilament	Not Done
515825	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
539815	4-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
541143	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
565344	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
575148	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
610107	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
624255	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
651651	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
655144	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
708712	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
713882	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
719664	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
731434	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
746814	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
757345	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
765830	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
786683	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
793150	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
818274	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
901007	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
904417	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
923130	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
947474	3-0	Absorbable	Monofilament	Not Done
965216	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
973149	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done
974039	2-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Not Done
978699	3-0	Non-absorbable	Monofilament	Done

The results presented in Table 5.1 indicate that 43 participants (86.00%) answered all the questions associated with this metric correctly, demonstrating that the participants possess basic knowledge related with simple interrupted sutures for wound closure in forearm lacerations. Of the seven participants that did not answer correctly, none answered the incorrect suture structure, two selected size 2-0, which is considered too large for a forearm laceration, and six chose an absorbable suture, usually used for subcuticular sutures (as these sutures are performed within the body, removing the suture by cutting is impossible, and removable sutures should be used). In addition, only one participant answered incorrectly to both the suture's

size and absorbability.

5.1.2 Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suturing Videos

The *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder* metric analyses whether the needle is being grasped approximately at $2/3$ from the needle point by the needle holder. It is analysed the ratio between the needle length until the needle holder grasp and the total needle length, providing the final score. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder* Metric

Video Number	Ratio	Final Score
114576	0.9255	Not Done
124269	0.7927	Done
136793	0.9611	Not Done
179892	0.7108	Done
208773	0.4196	Done
210072	0.7976	Done
248992	0.8397	Not Done
249076	0.7352	Done
263779	0.5581	Done
269939	0.4851	Done
276273	0.7355	Done
291008	0.4942	Done
312377	0.2623	Not Done
318727	0.6482	Done
366649	0.6747	Done
389990	0.5527	Done
393574	0.6794	Done
432109	0.6326	Done
455439	1.0000	Not Done
460500	0.7028	Done
479135	0.8990	Not Done
509697	0.7899	Done
515825	0.9021	Done
539815	0.8025	Done

541143	0.7098	Not Done
565344	0.7664	Done
575148	0.7173	Done
610107	0.6894	Not Done
624255	0.6107	Done
651651	0.1985	Not Done
655144	0.0000	Not Done
713882	0.0000	Not Done
719664	0.8669	Done
731434	0.9051	Done
746814	0.4221	Done
757345	0.8286	Done
765830	0.1073	Not Done
793150	0.7305	Done
818274	0.5183	Done
901007	0.3993	Done
904417	0.3333	Done
923130	0.6902	Done
973149	0.0000	Not Done
974039	1.0000	Not Done
978699	0.7618	Not Done

For this metric, the mode, the mean and the median correspond to 0.0000, 0.6300 and 0.7028 values, respectively, and the overall ratio values vary between 0.0000 and 1.0000, with a standard deviation of 0.2630. This reveals that, since the mean and median are values near $2/3$, the SUGAR tool often identifies as correct the placement of the needle within the needle holder. Indeed, 66.67% of the participants performed this metric correctly (*Done*). However, there are particular cases in which the metric is considered *Not Done*, even when the values belong to the interval set as correct. This is due to the detection of a too low number of intersections between the needle and the needle holder. In addition, the standard deviation value reveals that the calculated ratio for this particular metric varies moderately from the mean, explained by the fact that, even when grasping the needle incorrectly, the participants tend to grasp it between the needle's middle point and end point.

The *Insertion of needle at right angle to the skin metric* analyses whether the needle is being inserted at an approximate right angle for each suture, based on the ratio between the number of insertions at a right angle and the total number of

insertions, providing the final score. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Insertion of needle at right angle to the skin* Metric

Video Number	Insert success	Insertion
114576	0.7727	Done
124269	0.9167	Done
136793	0.0000	Not Done
179892	0.6000	Done
208773	0.0000	Not Done
210072	1.0000	Done
248992	0.1250	Not Done
249076	0.4000	Done
263779	0.1818	Done
269939	0.2667	Done
276273	0.0000	Not Done
291008	0.4348	Done
312377	0.0000	Not Done
318727	1.0000	Done
366649	0.5000	Done
389990	1.0000	Done
393574	0.3077	Done
432109	0.0000	Not Done
455439	0.0000	Not Done
460500	0.0000	Not Done
479135	0.0000	Not Done
509697	0.7692	Done
515825	0.1667	Done
539815	0.6364	Done
541143	1.0000	Done
565344	0.0000	Not Done
575148	0.0000	Not Done
610107	0.0000	Not Done
624255	0.1667	Done
651651	0.0000	Not Done
655144	0.1579	Done
713882	1.0000	Done

719664	0.0000	Not Done
731434	0.1500	Not Done
746814	0.0000	Not Done
757345	0.1818	Done
765830	0.8333	Done
793150	0.1538	Done
818274	1.0000	Done
901007	0.9444	Done
904417	0.0000	Not Done
923130	0.3846	Done
973149	0.9231	Done
974039	0.0000	Not Done
978699	1.0000	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 0.0000, 0.3800 and 0.1818, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.0000 and 1.0000, with a standard deviation of 0.3930. This reveals that, since the mean and median are low values, the SUGAR tool often detects an incorrect angle of needle insertion. However, since the threshold for the metric's correctness is 0.15, 60.00% of participants are deemed to have inserted the needle at a right angle throughout the suture's performance (*Done*). In addition, the high standard deviation value reveals that the ratio values obtained vary greatly, highlighting that the tool measures distinct ratios and values for this particular metric.

The *Needle inserted and removed using supination metric* analyses whether the participant inserts and removes the needle using supination for each suture. This analysis is based on the ratio between insertions and removals that use supination and the total number of insertions and removals, providing the final score. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Needle inserted and removed using supination* Metric

Video Number	Ratio	Final Score
114576	0.6667	Done
124269	1.0000	Done
136793	1.0000	Done
179892	0.0000	Not Done
208773	1.0000	Done

210072	1.0000	Done
248992	0.0000	Not Done
249076	1.0000	Done
263779	0.8571	Done
269939	1.0000	Done
276273	1.0000	Done
291008	1.0000	Done
312377	1.0000	Done
318727	1.0000	Done
366649	1.0000	Done
389990	0.8333	Done
393574	1.0000	Done
432109	1.0000	Done
455439	1.0000	Done
460500	1.0000	Done
479135	0.5000	Done
509697	0.6667	Done
515825	1.0000	Done
539815	1.0000	Done
541143	0.8571	Done
565344	1.0000	Done
575148	1.0000	Done
610107	1.0000	Done
624255	0.7500	Done
651651	1.0000	Done
655144	0.8750	Done
713882	0.0000	Done
719664	1.0000	Done
731434	1.0000	Done
746814	1.0000	Done
757345	1.0000	Done
765830	0.8000	Done
793150	0.8571	Done
818274	1.0000	Done
901007	0.8571	Done
904417	1.0000	Done
923130	1.0000	Done
973149	0.8333	Done

974039	0.8571	Done
978699	1.0000	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 1.0000, 0.8700 and 1.0000, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.0000 and 1.0000, with a standard deviation of 0.2583. The mode, mean and median present high values, indicating that the SUGAR tool often detects the correct use of supination for the needle's insertion and removal. In addition, the standard deviation value reveals that there is only a moderate deviation from the mean, leading to the conclusion that most identified ratios in this metric's analysis are relatively high. As such, 95.56% of the participants have this metric assessed as *Done*.

The *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges metric* analyses whether the participant inserts and removes the needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges, using the ratio between the number of correct insertions and removals and the total number of insertions and removals, providing the final score. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges Metric*

Video Number	Ratio	Final Score
114576	0.3333	Done
124269	0.6250	Done
136793	0.5000	Done
179892	0.5000	Done
208773	0.8571	Done
210072	0.4167	Done
248992	0.5000	Done
249076	0.8333	Done
263779	0.7778	Done
269939	0.4000	Done
276273	0.3333	Done
291008	0.2308	Done
312377	0.6667	Done
318727	0.1667	Done
366649	0.3333	Done
389990	0.7143	Done

393574	0.2727	Done
432109	0.6923	Done
455439	0.3333	Done
460500	0.0000	Not Done
479135	0.7500	Done
509697	1.0000	Done
515825	0.8571	Done
539815	0.2500	Done
541143	0.3333	Done
565344	0.7500	Done
575148	0.7273	Done
610107	0.0000	Not Done
624255	0.6000	Done
651651	0.6250	Done
655144	0.2000	Done
713882	0.5000	Done
719664	0.5455	Done
731434	0.0000	Not Done
746814	0.3333	Done
757345	0.3750	Done
765830	0.5000	Done
793150	0.3571	Done
818274	0.5455	Done
901007	0.4444	Done
904417	0.5000	Done
923130	0.3333	Done
973149	0.6000	Done
974039	0.6429	Done
978699	0.4000	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 0.3300, 0.4800 and 0.5000, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.0000 and 1.0000, with a standard deviation of 0.2320. This reveals that, because the mean and median are moderate values, the SUGAR tool detects the correct distance between the incision edges and the needle's insertion and removal performed for half of the suture in 46.67% of the tool's calculated values (these values are approximately 0.5, that is, values higher than $1/3$ and lower than $2/3$). However, since the threshold for the metric to be considered correct is 0.15, 93.33% of the participants are deemed to

have successfully performed this metric throughout the suture's performance (*Done*). In addition, the standard deviation value demonstrates that there is a moderate deviation from the mean, leading to the conclusion that this metric's analysis does not exhibit disparate ratio values.

The *One pass of needle per suture insertion metric* analyses whether the participant hesitates before inserting the needle into the suturing pad or whether, after insertion, the participant removes it backwards to repeat the suture from the start. As such, this metric analyses the ratio between the number of sutures in which more than one pass is detected and the total number of sutures, providing the final score. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.6.

Table 5.6: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *One pass of needle per suture insertion* Metric

Video Number	Ratio	Final Score
114576	0.6667	Not Done
124269	0.8333	Done
136793	0.7273	Not Done
179892	0.7500	Done
208773	1.0000	Done
210072	0.8000	Done
248992	0.7500	Done
249076	1.0000	Done
263779	0.8333	Done
269939	1.0000	Done
276273	1.0000	Done
291008	0.8571	Done
312377	0.9091	Done
318727	0.7692	Done
366649	0.6667	Not Done
389990	1.0000	Done
393574	0.8571	Done
432109	0.9091	Done
455439	1.0000	Done
460500	0.7500	Done
479135	0.7778	Done
509697	0.7500	Done
515825	0.8750	Done

539815	1.0000	Done
541143	1.0000	Done
565344	0.7143	Not Done
575148	1.0000	Done
610107	1.0000	Done
624255	0.8182	Done
651651	1.0000	Done
655144	0.6364	Not Done
713882	0.6923	Not Done
719664	1.0000	Done
731434	0.7692	Done
746814	0.8889	Done
757345	1.0000	Done
765830	1.0000	Done
793150	0.6667	Not Done
818274	1.0000	Done
901007	0.9167	Done
904417	1.0000	Done
923130	0.8889	Done
973149	0.8750	Done
974039	0.7692	Done
978699	1.0000	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 1.0000, 0.8700 and 0.8750, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.6360 and 1.0000, with a standard deviation of 0.1200. This reveals that, since the minimum, mean and median display high values, the SUGAR tool detects that only one pass is performed in each suture in 100.00% of the tool's calculated values. This makes sense, for it is extremely unlikely for a surgical trainee to perform more than one pass per suture. However, since the threshold for the metric to be considered correct is 0.75, not all participants (15.56%) achieve success in this particular metric. This is due to the fact that, if the participant performs additional passes (at least two passes), the metric is considered *Not Done*. In addition, the standard deviation value reveals a low deviation from the mean, further establishing the homogeneity of the ratios obtained in this metric's analysis.

The *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeons knot* metric analyses whether the participant demonstrates locking of suture for each suture. As

such, this metric analyses the ratio between the number of sutures with locking demonstrations and the total number of sutures, providing the final score. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.7.

Table 5.7: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeons knot Metric*

Video Number	Ratio	Final Score
114576	0.6250	Done
124269	0.0000	Not Done
136793	0.3750	Not Done
179892	0.6667	Done
208773	0.7500	Done
210072	0.6667	Done
248992	1.0000	Done
249076	0.5714	Done
263779	1.0000	Done
269939	0.8889	Done
276273	0.7500	Done
291008	0.6667	Done
312377	0.7000	Done
318727	0.0000	Not Done
366649	0.7500	Done
389990	0.3636	Not Done
393574	0.8333	Done
432109	0.8000	Done
455439	0.7500	Done
460500	1.0000	Done
479135	0.5714	Done
509697	0.5000	Done
515825	0.5714	Done
539815	0.6250	Done
541143	0.8750	Done
565344	0.5000	Done
575148	0.7143	Done
610107	0.3750	Not Done
624255	0.5556	Done
651651	0.6667	Done
655144	0.8571	Done

713882	0.3333	Not Done
719664	0.5385	Done
731434	0.7000	Done
746814	0.6250	Done
757345	0.5714	Done
765830	0.1429	Not Done
793150	0.8333	Done
818274	0.8333	Done
901007	0.8182	Done
904417	1.0000	Done
923130	0.6250	Done
973149	0.2857	Not Done
974039	0.7000	Done
978699	0.4286	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 0.6250, 0.6300 and 0.6600, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.0000 and 1.0000, with a standard deviation of 0.2370. This reveals that, since the mean and median are moderately high values, the SUGAR tool reveals the capability to detect a demonstration of suture locking performed during at least half of the suture in 82.22% of the tool's calculated values. Indeed, since the threshold for this metric to be considered correct is 0.4, most participants are deemed to achieve success in performing the activity associated with this metric throughout the suture's performance. In addition, the standard deviation value reveals that there is a modest deviation from the mean, concluding that the ratio values are tendentially moderate in this metric's analysis.

The *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers metric* analyses whether the participant holds the needle at any point with their hands, rather than using the forceps to manipulate it, by examining the number of frames in which needle handling is detected, and providing the final score. The analysis of this metric produced the following results presented in Table 5.8.

Table 5.8: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers* Metric

Video Number	Number of Frames	Final Score
114576	213	Not Done

124269	0	Done
136793	21	Done
179892	0	Done
208773	0	Done
210072	12	Done
248992	28	Done
249076	20	Done
263779	6	Done
269939	11	Done
276273	0	Done
291008	29	Done
312377	10	Done
318727	1	Done
366649	0	Done
389990	1	Done
393574	7	Done
432109	2	Done
455439	2	Done
460500	0	Done
479135	0	Done
509697	13	Done
515825	0	Done
539815	0	Done
541143	0	Done
565344	18	Done
575148	0	Done
610107	0	Done
624255	18	Done
651651	31	Not Done
655144	14	Done
713882	0	Done
719664	3	Done
731434	8	Done
746814	3	Done
757345	0	Done
765830	0	Done
793150	64	Not Done
818274	1	Done

901007	57	Not Done
904417	0	Done
923130	0	Done
973149	0	Done
974039	0	Done
978699	0	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 0, 13.18 and 1, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0 and 213, with a standard deviation of 33.29. This reveals that, since the minimum, mode and median comprise low values, the SUGAR tool detects that only the forceps is used to handle the needle throughout the suture in 91.11% of the tool's calculated values. This makes sense, since most of the suture's performance consists of handling the needle with the needle holder, without the necessity of readjusting this grasp. As such, most participants are deemed to achieve success in this particular metric. In addition, the standard deviation value of this metric reveals a high deviation from the mean, establishing that it is possible for the SUGAR tool to distinguish a participant who has likely handled a needle with their hands from one who has not.

5.1.3 Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suture End-Product Images

The *All sutures parallel to each other metric* analyses whether consecutive sutures are parallel to each other, considering the percentage of parallel suture pairs out of the total number of suture pairs. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.9.

Table 5.9: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *All sutures parallel to each other Metric*

Image Number	Percentage	Final Score
114576	37.50	Not Done
124269	33.33	Not Done
136793	100.00	Done
179892	75.00	Done
208773	75.00	Done
210072	33.33	Done

237435	100.00	Done
248992	50.00	Done
249076	60.00	Done
263779	0.00	Not Done
269939	71.43	Done
276273	100.00	Done
291008	85.71	Done
307232	75.00	Done
312377	77.78	Done
318727	75.00	Done
366649	50.00	Done
389990	63.64	Done
393574	75.00	Done
432109	0.00	Not Done
455439	100.00	Done
460500	0.00	Not Done
479135	40.00	Not Done
509697	80.00	Done
515825	16.67	Not Done
539815	33.33	Not Done
541143	57.14	Done
565344	85.71	Done
575148	0.00	Not Done
610107	100.00	Done
624255	33.33	Not Done
651651	0.00	Not Done
655144	60.00	Done
708712	42.86	Not Done
713882	33.33	Not Done
719664	40.00	Not Done
731434	66.67	Done
746814	14.29	Not Done
765830	50.00	Done
786683	50.00	Done
793150	75.00	Done
818274	50.00	Done
901007	62.50	Done
904417	0.00	Not Done

923130	0.00	Not Done
947474	100.00	Done
965216	0.00	Not Done
973149	0.00	Not Done
974039	71.43	Done
978699	83.33	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 0.00, 51.67 and 53.57, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.00 and 100.00, with a standard deviation of 32.37. This reveals that, since the minimum, mode and median are moderate values, the SUGAR tool is capable of assessing the suture pairs as being parallel in 60.00% of the tool's calculated values. However, the standard deviation presents a high value, demonstrating that the tool does not continuously detect the same values throughout the images. This is also noticed through the value range of 0.00 to 100.00, which are the minimum and maximum values possible to be obtained for a percentage value, respectively.

The *All suture placement equidistant from the edge of the wound metric* analyses whether the suture extremities are placed at an equal distance from the incision edges. This metric assesses the percentage of suture extremities approximately at the same distance from the incision edges out of the total number of suture extremities. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.10.

Table 5.10: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *All suture placement equidistant from the edge of the wound Metric*

Image Number	Percentage	Final Score
114576	0.00	Not Done
124269	87.50	Not Done
136793	83.33	Not Done
179892	70.00	Not Done
208773	80.00	Not Done
210072	0.00	Not Done
237435	100.00	Done
248992	33.33	Not Done
249076	83.33	Not Done
263779	100.00	Done
269939	75.00	Not Done
276273	100.00	Done

291008	0.00	Not Done
307232	70.00	Not Done
312377	95.00	Done
318727	70.00	Not Done
366649	80.00	Not Done
389990	95.83	Done
393574	100.00	Done
432109	50.00	Not Done
455439	0.00	Not Done
460500	100.00	Done
479135	58.33	Not Done
509697	0.00	Not Done
515825	0.00	Not Done
539815	0.00	Not Done
541143	81.25	Not Done
565344	87.50	Not Done
575148	100.00	Done
610107	100.00	Done
624255	75.00	Not Done
651651	100.00	Done
655144	91.67	Done
708712	75.00	Not Done
713882	90.00	Done
719664	0.00	Not Done
731434	78.57	Not Done
746814	75.00	Not Done
765830	90.00	Done
786683	0.00	Not Done
793150	80.00	Not Done
818274	0.00	Not Done
901007	0.00	Not Done
904417	0.00	Not Done
923130	100.00	Done
947474	66.67	Not Done
965216	75.00	Not Done
973149	0.00	Not Done
974039	81.25	Not Done
978699	100.00	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 0.00, 61.57 and 76.78, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.00 and 100.00, with a standard deviation of 38.81. This reveals that, since the mean and median display mid-to-high values, the SUGAR tool is capable of detecting whether the suture extremities are placed at an approximately equal distance from the incision edges in 72.00% of the tool's calculated values. However, it is also observed that the standard deviation value is high, indicating that there are participants exhibiting less suturing experience, in what refers to the scope of this metric. Since the threshold is 0.9, due to the fact that surgical experts assessing the suturing performance are particularly rigid with this metric, most participants have seen this metric be assessed as *Not Done*.

The *Distance between sutures appropriate metric* analyses whether consecutive sutures are not placed too close together nor too far apart. As such, this metric analyses the percentage of suture pairs with an appropriate distance between them out of the total number of suture pairs. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.11.

Table 5.11: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Distance between sutures appropriate* Metric

Image Number	Percentage	Final Score
114576	87.50	Done
124269	0.00	Not Done
136793	87.50	Done
179892	50.00	Not Done
208773	100.00	Done
210072	50.00	Not Done
237435	100.00	Done
248992	50.00	Not Done
249076	100.00	Done
263779	100.00	Done
269939	85.71	Done
276273	0.00	Done
291008	57.14	Not Done
307232	100.00	Done
312377	66.67	Done
318727	50.00	Not Done
366649	25.00	Not Done

389990	45.45	Not Done
393574	100.00	Done
432109	50.00	Not Done
455439	100.00	Done
460500	100.00	Done
479135	100.00	Done
509697	60.00	Not Done
515825	50.00	Not Done
539815	66.67	Done
541143	100.00	Done
565344	85.71	Done
575148	0.00	Not Done
610107	75.00	Done
624255	100.00	Done
651651	75.00	Done
655144	100.00	Done
708712	71.43	Done
713882	88.89	Done
719664	40.00	Not Done
731434	33.33	Not Done
746814	85.71	Done
765830	50.00	Not Done
786683	25.00	Not Done
793150	100.00	Done
818274	100.00	Done
901007	50.00	Not Done
904417	0.00	Not Done
923130	0.00	Not Done
947474	50.00	Not Done
965216	33.33	Not Done
973149	0.00	Not Done
974039	85.71	Done
978699	100.00	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 100.00, 64.62 and 69.04, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.00 and 100.00, with a standard deviation of 33.34. This reveals that, since the mean and median are mid-to-high values, the SUGAR tool tends to detect appropriate distances between a

pair of sutures in 56.00% of the tool's calculated values (*Done*). However, since the standard deviation displays a high value, there are also participants with significantly less suturing experience assessed in the scope of this metric.

The *Distance between sutures equal metric* analyses whether each suture pair is placed approximately at an equal distance, considering the percentage of suture pairs with an equal distance between them out of the total number of suture pairs. The analysis of this metric produced the following results presented in Table 5.12.

Table 5.12: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Distance between sutures equal Metric*

Image Number	Percentage	Final Score
114576	100.00	Done
124269	33.33	Not Done
136793	100.00	Done
179892	100.00	Done
208773	100.00	Done
210072	50.00	Done
237435	100.00	Done
248992	100.00	Done
249076	100.00	Done
263779	100.00	Done
269939	100.00	Done
276273	100.00	Done
291008	0.00	Not Done
307232	100.00	Done
312377	100.00	Done
318727	50.00	Done
366649	100.00	Done
389990	100.00	Done
393574	100.00	Done
432109	100.00	Done
455439	100.00	Done
460500	100.00	Done
479135	100.00	Done
509697	60.00	Done
515825	83.33	Done
539815	83.33	Done

541143	100.00	Done
565344	100.00	Done
575148	100.00	Done
610107	75.00	Not Done
624255	100.00	Done
651651	100.00	Done
655144	100.00	Done
708712	71.43	Done
713882	100.00	Done
719664	20.00	Not Done
731434	83.33	Done
746814	100.00	Done
765830	50.00	Done
786683	50.00	Done
793150	100.00	Done
818274	100.00	Done
901007	50.00	Done
904417	100.00	Done
923130	100.00	Done
947474	100.00	Done
965216	100.00	Done
973149	100.00	Done
974039	100.00	Done
978699	100.00	Done

For this metric, the mode, mean and median correspond to the values 100.00, 87.20 and 100.00, respectively. The ratio values vary between 0.00 and 100.00, with a standard deviation of 24.09. This reveals that, since the mode, mean and median exhibit high scores, the SUGAR tool often detects equal distances between suture pairs throughout the suture in 92.00% of the tool's calculated values. This makes sense, since even inexperienced volunteers tend to space out the sutures approximately at the same distance. However, there are false negatives due to the fact that the CV model does not possess a 100.00% accuracy and, therefore, does not always detect all sutures present in the image. This limitation compromises the assessment of this metric, since the distance seems larger due to a misdetected suture. In addition, the standard deviation value reveals that there is a moderate deviation from the mean, establishing that most volunteers achieve a high percentage in this metric.

The *Suture tension appropriate metric* analyses whether there are changes in pixel intensity which correlate with too little or too much tension in the suture. The metric is assessed as *Not Done* when there is at least one relatively abrupt change in pixel intensity present in the entire suture. The analysis of this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.13.

Table 5.13: Results Obtained by the SUGAR Tool for the *Suture tension appropriate Metric*

Image Number	Final Score
114576	Not Done
124269	Done
136793	Not Done
179892	Not Done
208773	Not Done
210072	Not Done
237435	Done
248992	Done
249076	Not Done
263779	Not Done
269939	Not Done
276273	Done
291008	Not Done
307232	Not Done
312377	Not Done
318727	Not Done
366649	Not Done
389990	Not Done
393574	Not Done
432109	Done
455439	Not Done
460500	Done
479135	Not Done
509697	Not Done
515825	Done
539815	Not Done
541143	Not Done
565344	Not Done
575148	Not Done

610107	Done
624255	Not Done
651651	Not Done
655144	Not Done
708712	Done
713882	Not Done
719664	Not Done
731434	Not Done
746814	Not Done
765830	Not Done
786683	Not Done
793150	Not Done
818274	Not Done
901007	Not Done
904417	Done
923130	Done
947474	Done
965216	Done
973149	Not Done
974039	Not Done
978699	Not Done

This metric analyses if there is an abrupt change of pixel intensity present in relevant identified pixels. As such, it does not calculate ratios or percentages. For this metric, the SUGAR tool detected 13 (26.00%) successful outcomes for this specific metric, demonstrating that the CV-based tool tends to detect changes in pixel intensity and, therefore, concludes that the suture tension applied is not appropriate for most cases.

5.2 System Validation

In order to validate whether the novel CV-based SUGAR suturing skills assessment and grading tool is correctly identifying if the participant is performing the suturing task in accordance to the reference suture quality metrics, it is implemented a comparative analysis between the results produced by the automated suturing skills assessment tool and the results of the suturing skills assessments performed by the surgical experts, assumed as the ground truth for this Thesis's work.

In total, the surgical experts performed 102 reviews, with two expert reviews per suturing video and suture end-product image, using the traditional human-based suturing skills assessment and grading system. In case of disagreement between the two surgical experts with respect to the assessment of a given metric, the novel automated CV-based SUGAR tool is deemed to have successfully assessed the metric, representing thus the tiebreaker.

The following sections present the validation results for each of the suture quality metrics. In section 5.2.5, those validation results are explained, allowing to determine the alignment between the results of the automated CV-based SUGAR tool with the results of the surgical experts' assessment reviews (ground truth).

5.2.1 Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Human-based Input

The surgical experts' reviews were performed based on the collected suturing videos and suture end-product images. The *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure) metric* is analysed based on the human-based input and is not part of the video or image analyses. Also, the surgical experts were not present during the suturing task activities and did not receive the human input for this metric. As a result, their reviews did not include this specific metric.

5.2.2 Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suturing Videos

The *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder metric* analyses whether the needle is being grasped approximately at $\frac{2}{3}$ from the needle point by the needle holder. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.14.

Table 5.14: Validation Results for the *Correct placement of needle within the needle holder Metric*

Video Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Conflict	Not Done
124269	Done	Done
136793	Conflict	Not Done
179892	Conflict	Done
208773	Done	Done

210072	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Not Done
249076	Done	Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Done	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Done	Done
312377	Done	Not Done
318727	Done	Done
366649	Done	Done
389990	Done	Done
393574	Conflict	Done
432109	Not Done	Done
455439	Conflict	Not Done
460500	Done	Done
479135	Done	Not Done
509697	Done	Done
515825	Done	Done
539815	Conflict	Done
541143	Not Done	Not Done
565344	Done	Done
575148	Conflict	Done
610107	Done	Not Done
624255	Conflict	Done
651651	Conflict	Not Done
655144	Done	Not Done
713882	Done	Not Done
719664	Done	Done
731434	Done	Done
746814	Conflict	Done
757345	Not Done	Done
765830	Conflict	Not Done
793150	Done	Done
818274	Done	Done
901007	Done	Done
904417	Done	Done
923130	Done	Done
973149	Done	Not Done

974039	Done	Not Done
978699	Done	Not Done

The *Insertion of needle at right angle to the skin metric* analyses whether the needle is being inserted at an approximate right angle for each suture. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.15.

Table 5.15: Validation Results for the *Insertion of needle at right angle to the skin Metric*

Video Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Done	Done
124269	Done	Done
136793	Not Done	Not Done
179892	Conflict	Done
208773	Not Done	Not Done
210072	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Not Done
249076	Done	Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Conflict	Done
276273	Done	Not Done
291008	Conflict	Done
312377	Done	Not Done
318727	Done	Done
366649	Done	Done
389990	Done	Done
393574	Conflict	Done
432109	Not Done	Not Done
455439	Conflict	Not Done
460500	Done	Not Done
479135	Not Done	Not Done
509697	Conflict	Done
515825	Conflict	Done
539815	Not Done	Done
541143	Conflict	Done
565344	Done	Not Done
575148	Not Done	Not Done
610107	Not Done	Not Done

624255	Not Done	Done
651651	Conflict	Not Done
655144	Conflict	Done
713882	Not Done	Done
719664	Done	Not Done
731434	Done	Not Done
746814	Conflict	Not Done
757345	Done	Done
765830	Done	Done
793150	Done	Done
818274	Done	Done
901007	Done	Done
904417	Conflict	Not Done
923130	Conflict	Done
973149	Done	Done
974039	Done	Not Done
978699	Done	Done

The *Needle inserted and removed using supination metric* analyses whether the participant inserts and removes the needle using supination for each suture. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.16.

Table 5.16: Validation Results for the *Needle inserted and removed using supination Metric*

Video Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Conflict	Done
124269	Conflict	Done
136793	Conflict	Done
179892	Not Done	Not Done
208773	Conflict	Done
210072	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Not Done
249076	Done	Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Not Done	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Done	Done

312377	Conflict	Done
318727	Conflict	Done
366649	Conflict	Done
389990	Done	Done
393574	Not Done	Done
432109	Not Done	Done
455439	Conflict	Done
460500	Done	Done
479135	Conflict	Done
509697	Done	Done
515825	Done	Done
539815	Not Done	Done
541143	Conflict	Done
565344	Conflict	Done
575148	Not Done	Done
610107	Conflict	Done
624255	Conflict	Done
651651	Not Done	Done
655144	Done	Done
713882	Not Done	Done
719664	Conflict	Done
731434	Conflict	Done
746814	Not Done	Done
757345	Not Done	Done
765830	Conflict	Done
793150	Conflict	Done
818274	Conflict	Done
901007	Not Done	Done
904417	Conflict	Done
923130	Conflict	Done
973149	Not Done	Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Done	Done

The *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges metric* analyses whether the participant inserts and removes the needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.17.

Table 5.17: Validation Results for the *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges* Metric

Video Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Conflict	Done
124269	Done	Done
136793	Done	Done
179892	Conflict	Done
208773	Done	Done
210072	Done	Done
248992	Conflict	Done
249076	Conflict	Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Done	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Done	Done
312377	Done	Done
318727	Done	Done
366649	Done	Done
389990	Conflict	Done
393574	Conflict	Done
432109	Conflict	Done
455439	Done	Done
460500	Done	Not Done
479135	Done	Done
509697	Done	Done
515825	Done	Done
539815	Not Done	Done
541143	Done	Done
565344	Done	Done
575148	Conflict	Done
610107	Conflict	Not Done
624255	Conflict	Done
651651	Conflict	Done
655144	Done	Done
713882	Done	Done
719664	Conflict	Done
731434	Done	Not Done

746814	Done	Done
757345	Done	Done
765830	Done	Done
793150	Done	Done
818274	Done	Done
901007	Done	Done
904417	Done	Done
923130	Conflict	Done
973149	Conflict	Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Done	Done

The *One pass of needle per suture insertion metric* analyses whether the participant hesitates before inserting the needle into the suturing pad or whether, after insertion, the participant removes it backwards to repeat the suture from the start. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.18.

Table 5.18: Validation Results for the *One pass of needle per suture insertion Metric*

Video Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Conflict	Not Done
124269	Done	Done
136793	Not Done	Not Done
179892	Done	Done
208773	Not Done	Done
210072	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Done
249076	Done	Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Done	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Conflict	Done
312377	Done	Done
318727	Done	Done
366649	Conflict	Not Done
389990	Conflict	Done
393574	Not Done	Done
432109	Conflict	Done

455439	Conflict	Done
460500	Done	Done
479135	Done	Done
509697	Done	Done
515825	Done	Done
539815	Done	Done
541143	Not Done	Done
565344	Done	Not Done
575148	Conflict	Done
610107	Conflict	Done
624255	Not Done	Done
651651	Conflict	Done
655144	Done	Not Done
713882	Done	Not Done
719664	Done	Done
731434	Conflict	Done
746814	Conflict	Done
757345	Done	Done
765830	Conflict	Done
793150	Not Done	Not Done
818274	Conflict	Done
901007	Conflict	Done
904417	Conflict	Done
923130	Done	Done
973149	Conflict	Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Done	Done

The *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeons knot metric* analyses whether the participant demonstrates locking of suture for each suture. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.19.

Table 5.19: Validation Results for the *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeons knot Metric*

Video Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Done	Done
124269	Not Done	Not Done

136793	Conflict	Not Done
179892	Done	Done
208773	Conflict	Done
210072	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Done
249076	Conflict	Done
263779	Conflict	Done
269939	Done	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Done	Done
312377	Conflict	Done
318727	Conflict	Not Done
366649	Conflict	Done
389990	Conflict	Not Done
393574	Not Done	Done
432109	Conflict	Done
455439	Conflict	Done
460500	Not Done	Done
479135	Done	Done
509697	Conflict	Done
515825	Done	Done
539815	Conflict	Done
541143	Conflict	Done
565344	Conflict	Done
575148	Conflict	Done
610107	Conflict	Not Done
624255	Done	Done
651651	Done	Done
655144	Done	Done
713882	Conflict	Not Done
719664	Conflict	Done
731434	Done	Done
746814	Done	Done
757345	Conflict	Done
765830	Conflict	Not Done
793150	Conflict	Done
818274	Conflict	Done
901007	Conflict	Done

904417	Not Done	Done
923130	Done	Done
973149	Conflict	Not Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Conflict	Done

The *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers metric* analyses whether the participant holds the needle at any point with their hands, rather than using the forceps to manipulate it. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.20.

Table 5.20: Validation Results for the *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers Metric*

Video Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Done	Not Done
124269	Conflict	Done
136793	Done	Done
179892	Conflict	Done
208773	Conflict	Done
210072	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Done
249076	Not Done	Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Done	Done
276273	Conflict	Done
291008	Done	Done
312377	Not Done	Done
318727	Not Done	Done
366649	Done	Done
389990	Conflict	Done
393574	Conflict	Done
432109	Conflict	Done
455439	Conflict	Done
460500	Done	Done
479135	Done	Done
509697	Done	Done
515825	Not Done	Done
539815	Conflict	Done

541143	Conflict	Done
565344	Conflict	Done
575148	Not Done	Done
610107	Done	Done
624255	Conflict	Done
651651	Not Done	Not Done
655144	Done	Done
713882	Not Done	Done
719664	Done	Done
731434	Conflict	Done
746814	Not Done	Done
757345	Not Done	Done
765830	Conflict	Done
793150	Done	Not Done
818274	Done	Done
901007	Done	Not Done
904417	Conflict	Done
923130	Done	Done
973149	Done	Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Conflict	Done

5.2.3 Suture Quality Metrics Applied to Suture End-Product Images

The *All sutures parallel to each other* metric analyses whether consecutive sutures are parallel to each other, considering the percentage of parallel suture pairs out of the total number of suture pairs. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.21.

Table 5.21: Validation Results for the *All sutures parallel to each other* Metric

Image Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Conflict	Not Done
124269	Conflict	Not Done
136793	Conflict	Done
179892	Done	Done

208773	Done	Done
210072	Done	Done
237435	Done	Done
248992	Conflict	Done
249076	Conflict	Done
263779	Done	Not Done
269939	Done	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Conflict	Done
307232	Conflict	Done
312377	Done	Done
318727	Done	Done
366649	Done	Done
389990	Done	Done
393574	Not Done	Done
432109	Done	Not Done
455439	Done	Done
460500	Done	Not Done
479135	Done	Not Done
509697	Conflict	Done
515825	Conflict	Not Done
539815	Conflict	Not Done
541143	Done	Done
565344	Done	Done
575148	Not Done	Not Done
610107	Done	Done
624255	Not Done	Not Done
651651	Conflict	Not Done
655144	Done	Done
708712	Conflict	Not Done
713882	Conflict	Not Done
719664	Conflict	Not Done
731434	Done	Done
746814	Conflict	Not Done
765830	Conflict	Done
786683	Not Done	Done
793150	Conflict	Done
818274	Done	Done

901007	Conflict	Done
904417	Done	Not Done
923130	Conflict	Not Done
947474	Done	Done
965216	Conflict	Not Done
973149	Conflict	Not Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Done	Done

The *All suture placement equidistant from the edge of the wound metric* analyses whether the suture extremities are placed at an equal distance from the incision edges. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.22.

Table 5.22: Validation Results for the *All suture placement equidistant from the edge of the wound Metric*

Image Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Not Done	Not Done
124269	Not Done	Not Done
136793	Conflict	Not Done
179892	Done	Not Done
208773	Done	Not Done
210072	Done	Not Done
237435	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Not Done
249076	Not Done	Not Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Done	Not Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Not Done	Not Done
307232	Conflict	Not Done
312377	Done	Done
318727	Conflict	Not Done
366649	Not Done	Not Done
389990	Conflict	Done
393574	Not Done	Done
432109	Not Done	Not Done

455439	Conflict	Not Done
460500	Done	Done
479135	Not Done	Not Done
509697	Not Done	Not Done
515825	Conflict	Not Done
539815	Not Done	Not Done
541143	Conflict	Not Done
565344	Not Done	Not Done
575148	Not Done	Done
610107	Not Done	Done
624255	Not Done	Not Done
651651	Not Done	Done
655144	Conflict	Done
708712	Not Done	Not Done
713882	Not Done	Done
719664	Conflict	Not Done
731434	Done	Not Done
746814	Not Done	Not Done
765830	Not Done	Done
786683	Not Done	Not Done
793150	Not Done	Not Done
818274	Conflict	Not Done
901007	Conflict	Not Done
904417	Done	Not Done
923130	Not Done	Done
947474	Conflict	Not Done
965216	Not Done	Not Done
973149	Conflict	Not Done
974039	Done	Not Done
978699	Done	Done

The *Distance between sutures appropriate metric* analyses whether consecutive sutures are not placed too close together nor too far apart. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.23.

Table 5.23: Validation Results for the *Distance between sutures appropriate* Metric

Image Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Conflict	Done
124269	Done	Not Done
136793	Done	Done
179892	Conflict	Not Done
208773	Done	Done
210072	Done	Not Done
237435	Done	Done
248992	Conflict	Not Done
249076	Done	Done
263779	Done	Done
269939	Done	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Done	Not Done
307232	Done	Done
312377	Conflict	Done
318727	Done	Not Done
366649	Not Done	Not Done
389990	Not Done	Not Done
393574	Conflict	Done
432109	Conflict	Not Done
455439	Done	Done
460500	Conflict	Done
479135	Done	Done
509697	Conflict	Not Done
515825	Done	Not Done
539815	Not Done	Done
541143	Done	Done
565344	Done	Done
575148	Done	Not Done
610107	Done	Done
624255	Done	Done
651651	Not Done	Done
655144	Done	Done
708712	Done	Done
713882	Conflict	Done

719664	Conflict	Not Done
731434	Done	Not Done
746814	Conflict	Done
765830	Conflict	Not Done
786683	Conflict	Not Done
793150	Conflict	Done
818274	Done	Done
901007	Done	Not Done
904417	Done	Not Done
923130	Conflict	Not Done
947474	Conflict	Not Done
965216	Conflict	Not Done
973149	Conflict	Not Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Done	Done

The *Distance between sutures equal metric* analyses whether each suture pair is placed approximately at an equal distance, considering the percentage of suture pairs with an equal distance between them out of the total number of suture pairs. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.24.

Table 5.24: Validation Results for the *Distance between sutures equal Metric*

Image Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Not Done	Done
124269	Done	Not Done
136793	Not Done	Done
179892	Conflict	Done
208773	Done	Done
210072	Done	Done
237435	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Done
249076	Conflict	Done
263779	Conflict	Done
269939	Conflict	Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Not Done	Not Done
307232	Conflict	Done

312377	Conflict	Done
318727	Conflict	Done
366649	Not Done	Done
389990	Done	Done
393574	Not Done	Done
432109	Not Done	Done
455439	Conflict	Done
460500	Done	Done
479135	Conflict	Done
509697	Not Done	Done
515825	Done	Done
539815	Not Done	Done
541143	Conflict	Done
565344	Not Done	Done
575148	Not Done	Done
610107	Not Done	Not Done
624255	Done	Done
651651	Not Done	Done
655144	Conflict	Done
708712	Not Done	Done
713882	Not Done	Done
719664	Not Done	Not Done
731434	Done	Done
746814	Not Done	Done
765830	Not Done	Done
786683	Not Done	Done
793150	Conflict	Done
818274	Done	Done
901007	Done	Done
904417	Done	Done
923130	Not Done	Done
947474	Not Done	Done
965216	Conflict	Done
973149	Conflict	Done
974039	Done	Done
978699	Done	Done

The *Suture tension appropriate metric* analyses whether there are changes in

pixel intensity which correlate with too little or too much tension in the suture. The validation for this metric produced the results presented in Table 5.25.

Table 5.25: Validation Results for the *Suture tension appropriate* Metric

Image Number	Review Score	SUGAR Score
114576	Conflict	Not Done
124269	Conflict	Done
136793	Not Done	Not Done
179892	Conflict	Not Done
208773	Conflict	Not Done
210072	Conflict	Not Done
237435	Done	Done
248992	Not Done	Done
249076	Conflict	Not Done
263779	Done	Not Done
269939	Conflict	Not Done
276273	Done	Done
291008	Conflict	Not Done
307232	Conflict	Not Done
312377	Not Done	Not Done
318727	Not Done	Not Done
366649	Not Done	Not Done
389990	Not Done	Not Done
393574	Not Done	Not Done
432109	Not Done	Done
455439	Conflict	Not Done
460500	Conflict	Done
479135	Not Done	Not Done
509697	Done	Not Done
515825	Done	Done
539815	Not Done	Not Done
541143	Conflict	Not Done
565344	Conflict	Not Done
575148	Not Done	Not Done
610107	Conflict	Done
624255	Conflict	Not Done
651651	Not Done	Not Done
655144	Done	Not Done

708712	Conflict	Done
713882	Conflict	Not Done
719664	Conflict	Not Done
731434	Conflict	Not Done
746814	Not Done	Not Done
765830	Conflict	Not Done
786683	Not Done	Not Done
793150	Done	Not Done
818274	Conflict	Not Done
901007	Conflict	Not Done
904417	Conflict	Done
923130	Conflict	Done
947474	Conflict	Done
965216	Not Done	Done
973149	Conflict	Not Done
974039	Done	Not Done
978699	Conflict	Not Done

5.2.4 The Value of Inter-Rater Reliability

Inter-Rater Reliability (IRR) indicates the degree of agreement among independent evaluators who assess or grade the same object, signaling consistency and objectivity in their evaluations.

A high *IRR* indicates a highly consistent, robust and valid evaluation result (the evaluators apply the same criteria consistently), while a low *IRR* suggest a potential bias, subjectivity or unclear criteria, in which valid conclusions cannot be derived from the available evaluation data. As a result, when assigning a ground-truth value to the evaluators' assessment, it is important that this assessment exhibits a high *IRR*.

IRR is here applied using a simplified formula that calculates the percentage of agreement among evaluators as follows:

$$IRR(\%) = \frac{\text{Total Agreements}}{\text{Total Evaluations}} \times 100 \quad (5.1)$$

In this Thesis, it is decided to observe the RCSI surgical experts' reviews of the

suturing videos and suture end-product images as the ground-truth to validate the automated CV-based SUGAR tool. Consequently, it is relevant to understand which is the degree of agreement among the RCSI surgical experts in their assessment of the suturing skills displayed in the suturing videos and suture end-product images. The IRR is able to demonstrate that degree of agreement.

Results are presented in Table 5.26.

Table 5.26: Inter-Rater Reliability (IRR) Among RCSI Surgical Experts' Assessments

Suture Quality Metric	IRR (%)
Correct placement of needle within needle holder	75.56
Insertion of needle at the right angle to the skin	71.11
Needle inserted and removed using supination	55.56
Insertion and exit of needle at app. 2-4 mm from the incision edges	68.89
One pass of needle per suture insertion	64.44
Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot	44.44
Handled needle with forceps, not fingers	64.44
All sutures parallel to each other	58.00
All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound	74.00
Distance between sutures appropriate	64.00
Distance between sutures equal	72.00
Suture tension appropriate	46.00

Overall, it can be observed that all *IRR* values are below 80.00%, confirming that the assessment of suturing skills and competences is an inherently subjective process, and may incorporate potential bias in its evaluation. It also indicates that additional discussion between the surgical experts on the objective application of specific suture quality metrics would be beneficial towards achieving higher levels of agreement concerning their assessment, eventually identifying possible misunderstandings or lack of clarity in the definition of the metrics.

On a positive note, it is noted that the *Correct placement of needle within needle holder* (76.00%), the *Insertion of needle at the right angle to the skin metric* (71.00%), the *All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound* (74.00%) and the *Distance between sutures equal* (72.00%) metrics present a good agreement degree among evaluators and, consequently, indicate a good level of consistency, robustness and validity in their assessment.

On a less positive note, it is demonstrated that the *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot* (44.00%) and the *Suture tension appropriate* (46.00%) metrics exhibit the lowest *IRR* scores (below 50%), followed by the *Needle inserted and removed using supination* (56.00%) and the *All sutures parallel to*

each other (58.00%) metrics. These agreement levels indicate the suture quality metrics requiring more attention towards the definition of a more objective and clear evaluation criteria. Overall, the *IRR* values indicate sufficient to weak levels of consistency and validity. When validating the SUGAR tool, the drawing of findings and conclusions about these specific suture quality metrics require additional attention.

5.2.5 Overall SUGAR System Validation

Table 5.27 and Figure 5.1 displays the final validation results for the SUGAR Tool Proof-of-Concept, following the comparative analysis performed and summarised in the tables above. These results reveal, for each suture quality metric, the scores of the SUGAR tool in terms of:

- Accuracy - the number of correct assessments over the total number of assessments; it is calculated through equation 5.2:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{True Positives} + \text{True Negatives}}{\text{Total Samples}} \quad (5.2)$$

- Precision - the number of true positives over the sum of the number of true positives and false negatives; it is calculated through Equation 5.3:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}} \quad (5.3)$$

- Recall - the number of true negatives over the sum of the number of true negatives and the false positives; it is calculated through Equation 5.4:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Negatives}}{\text{True Negatives} + \text{False Positives}} \quad (5.4)$$

- F1 Score – calculated through Equation 5.5:

$$\text{F1 Score} = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{\text{Precision}+1} + \frac{1}{\text{Recall}}} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (5.5)$$

Table 5.27: Validation Results of the SUGAR Tool

Suture Quality Metric	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 Score (%)
Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Correct placement of needle within needle holder	77.78	77.78	77.78	77.78
Insertion of needle at right angle to skin	77.78	77.73	78.57	78.15
Needle inserted and removed using supination	75.56	100.00	15.38	26.66
Insertion and exit of needle at app. 2-4 mm from incision edges	93.33	95.35	50.00	65.60
One pass of needle per suture insertion	82.22	91.67	44.44	59.86
Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeon's knot	91.11	100.00	66.67	80.00
Handled needle with forceps, not fingers	73.33	91.43	10.00	18.03
All sutures parallel to each other	86.00	85.29	87.50	86.38
All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound	72.00	57.14	80.00	66.66
Distance between sutures appropriate	78.00	74.29	86.67	80.00
Distance between sutures equal	62.00	96.55	14.29	24.90
Suture tension appropriate	84.00	66.67	91.43	77.11
SUGAR Tool Proof-of-Concept	81.01	85.68	61.75	71.77

Figure 5.1: Validation Results of the SUGAR Tool

The *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure)* metric is calculated based on the participants' input. The final validation score of the SUGAR tool for this metric reveals the maximum possible values for all evaluation variables, thus indicating that this metric will always align with any surgical expert's assessment. Overall, the SUGAR tool always correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the *Correct placement of needle within needle holder* metric, the final

validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with the same high value for all evaluation variables. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***Insertion of needle at the right angle to the skin metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with approximately the same high value for all evaluation variables. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***Needle inserted and removed using supination metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with high values in the precision (100.00%) and accuracy (75.56%) scores, and low values in the recall (15.38%) and F1 score (26.66%) scores. The very low values of the recall and F1 scores is caused by the high difficulty level in assessing this particular metric, directly associated with the required subtlety of wrist movement required for successfully performing this suturing action. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***Insertion and exit of the needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a highly positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with higher values in the precision (95.35%) and accuracy (93.33%) scores. In this particular metric, the recall (50.00%) and F1 score (65.60%) values are relatively low, because there are only two videos (videos 539815 and 136793) for which this metric was considered *Not Done* and, one is correctly assessed by the SUGAR tool, resulting in a recall value of 50.00%. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***One pass of needle per suture insertion metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with high values in the accuracy (82.22%) and precision (91.67%) scores, and low values in the recall (44.44%) and F1 score (59.86%) scores. Both these relatively low values are determined by the five videos for which the SUGAR tool assessed this metric as *Done*, differing from the subjective judgement of the surgical

experts. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*. This metric should be further discussed and reviewed in future work.

For the ***Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a highly positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with higher values in the precision (100.00%) and accuracy (91.11%) scores. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***Handled needle with forceps, not fingers metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with high values in the precision (91.43%) and accuracy (73.33%) scores, and low values in the recall (10.00%) and F1 score (18.03%) scores. The very low recall score value is directly associated with the fact that the camera does not capture 3D information, causing the need to set a threshold to help determine whether the participant grasps the needle with at least one of the hands at any point during the video. Because of this threshold, several videos in which the grasping of the needle with fingers is identified are not correctly assessed, as in most cases once the needle is grasped with fingers, the needle stops being detected, thus compromising the tool's capability to assess whether there has been an intersection between the two objects. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***All sutures parallel to each other metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a highly positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with balanced high score values for all evaluation variables. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with higher values in the recall (80.00%) and accuracy (72.00%) scores. The relatively low precision score (57.14%) is caused by the inherent limitations of the CV model's accuracy for performing the segmentation of each suture, resulting in small errors that affect this metric's rigorous threshold. Overall,

the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***Distance between sutures appropriate metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with balanced high score values for all evaluation variables. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

For the ***Distance between sutures equal metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with higher values in the precision (96.55%) and accuracy (62.00%) scores, and low values in the recall (14.29%) and F1 score (24.90%) scores. The low recall score value is explained by the limitations in the CV model's accuracy in the detection of each suture, which results in individual sutures not being detected and the space between them considered too high to be equal. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

Finally, for the ***Suture tension appropriate metric***, the final validation score of the SUGAR tool displays a positive alignment with the surgical experts' assessment, with higher values in the recall (91.43%), accuracy (84.00%) and F1 score (77.11%) values. The relatively low precision score value (66.67%) is caused by the fact that some pixels deemed relevant might coincide with the suture thread from the leftovers, rather than the suturing pad surface. This leads the CV model to detect a change in pixel intensity, associated with the absence of appropriate suture tension. Overall, the SUGAR tool correctly grades whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*.

Based on the results showcased by Table 5.27, and taking into account the ground-truth for this Master's Thesis, it is demonstrated that the SUGAR Proof-of-Concept correctly grades whether each suture quality metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*, thus exhibiting promising results to the feasibility of developing a CV-based automated tool to assess and grade suturing skills.

Chapter 6

Discussion and Impact

This chapter delivers an analysis of the Master Thesis's results, explaining the observed trends in the experimental results and addressing any limitations of the performed research and of the developed Proof-of-Concept. This chapter concludes with a discussion of the results' significance, demonstrating how the Thesis's work ambitions to advance knowledge and to contribute to solving real-world problems. The articulation of the Thesis's impact is crucial for demonstrating the value of the research and its potential contribution to society, beyond the academic setting.

The SUGAR surgical suturing grader tool is a Proof-of-Concept developed in this Master's Thesis aiming to demonstrate the feasibility of applying CV-based techniques to develop an automated suturing skills assessment and grading system. This Proof-of-Concept was implemented with the active support of the RCSI surgical experts and considers the RCSI's basis for suture quality metrics and suturing skills assessment as the main source of ground truth, relevant to conduct the validation of the SUGAR tool.

The experimental results, exhibiting an overall accuracy of 81.01%, a precision of 85.68%, a recall of 61.75% and a F1 score of 71.77%, allow to demonstrate that the novel SUGAR tool is capable of reliably detecting and tracking the movements of hands and surgical tools and detecting different surgical tools and key suture components in simple interrupted sutures, as well as of assessing and grading suturing performance based on specific suture quality metrics, such as the *Correct placement of needle within needle holder* and the *Insertion of needle at the right angle to the skin* metrics.

In this context, although the importance of the accuracy and precision scores are straightforwardly understandable, the relevance of the values provided by the recall

and F1 scores may be less clear. The obtained accuracy score reveals that the SUGAR tool produces the correct output, namely when compared with the expert reviews' scores established as the ground truth for the Thesis's work. The precision and recall scores function as a weighing scale to the SUGAR tool's performance, as they allow for the analysis of the number of false negatives and false positives produced, respectively. Finally, the F1 score highlights which are the suture quality metrics with the highest deviation between the precision and recall values, clearly indicating if the SUGAR tool presents a tendency to consider a specific suture quality metric as *Done* or *Not Done*. For example, metrics such as the *Needle inserted and removed using supination*, the *Handled needle with forceps, not fingers* and the *Distance between sutures equal* demonstrate a low recall value, revealing such a tendency towards the *Done* assessment. To properly assess the reasons behind this tendency, it would be necessary to have a larger and more diversified dataset so that the number of *Not Done* assessments would be sufficient to improve the model's learning capability.

Indeed, for a better understanding of the achieved results in this Master's Thesis, it is important to explain the reasons behind the assessment results, as well as the inherent limitations of the automated assessment of specific suture quality metrics.

Indeed, it is noted the specific nature of the suture quality metric that is based on the human input. The assessment of the ***Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure) metric*** is not a result of video analysis. Hence, it functions as an add-on to be included in a CV-based suturing skill assessment that judges basic proficiency. The collection of the data to analyse may be thus considered somewhat flawed, as the surgical trainee needs to correctly type the answers, with grammatical errors affecting the answers' correctness, and no possibility to change a prior choice. This metric's assessment by the SUGAR tool indicates that a large majority of participants (approximately 90% of them) have provided correct answers to all questions. It is noted that, since this metric is based on human input, the SUGAR tool's assessment indicates an accuracy of 100.00%. However, the setup used for the data capture process did not follow the exact settings of an exam environment (for example, due to time constraints of the participants to perform the suturing videos, different participants performed the suturing task at the same time), which is likely to have affected the outcome of the metric, particularly for those participants who did not provide the correct answers. As a result, it would be important to consider specific changes for the data collection associated with this metric, in order to allow for more accurate results. Aside from the execution of the suturing task in a private setting, it would

be effective to provide multiple choices for the selection of the answers, with the possibility to change the options until final submission. Aside from facilitating the data collection process, these changes would have a positive effect in the reduction of stress- and anxiety-related mistakes during exams.

Next, the specific characteristics of the suture quality metrics applied to the suturing videos are addressed, based on automated CV-based video analysis. Although applying an objective and reproducible analytical method, it is observed that the SUGAR tool's assessment of these metrics is affected by known limitations of CV models, including the absence of 3D information, which may lead to difficulties in identify overlapping, and the lack of spatial-temporal information, which may cause limitations in distinguishing similar suturing sub-tasks. Further, it is also noted that the need to adjust these metrics through hard-coded thresholds and fine-tuning work based on traditional CV techniques to meet the specific interpretations of the metrics by the surgical experts (the ground truth in this Proof-of-Concept demonstration) may affect a purely objective assessment of the suture quality metrics based on video analysis.

One of the suture quality metrics requiring detailed explanation is the ***Correct placement of needle within the needle holder metric***. Overall, this metric's results indicate an accuracy, precision, recall and F1 scores of 77.78%. Although a positive result, it is acknowledged that this metric's assessment is influenced by the inherent precision limitations of the CV model. Indeed, this metric's analysis requires a highly precise detection and segmentation of the needle and of the needle holder and there are cases where the needle is not detected easily at the beginning of the suture. This is caused by the elevated difficulty of detecting the needle, as it is a small sized object, it has the ability to reflect light and it may have different visual appearances depending on the point of view (for example, it may visually appear to be straight or circular). In addition, this metric requires the detection of an intersection between the needle holder's tip and the needle, which can be affected or not detected at all because of the difficulty in detecting and segmenting the needle. Further, when the needle holder is grasping the needle, the needle's end point might not be detected as part of the needle, as is the case with the video 208773 (while the expert reviewers stated the metric was *Done* in this video, the tool considered it *Not Done*). In this case, since the end point of the needle is not correctly identified, the needle appears to end near the needle holder, with the SUGAR tool not detecting an intersection and, therefore, assessing the metric as *Not Done*. It is noted that, while this negatively affected the suturing performance in video 208773, when the CV model cannot identify the end point of the needle, it usually means that the

placement is done incorrectly, with the needle holder too close to the end point of the needle, thus affecting its detection due to a large obstruction by the needle holder.

The *Insertion of needle at the right angle to the skin metric* displays the same measurement limitation, as its assessment accuracy is also dependent on the needle's correct detection and segmentation. It is noted that, depending on the needle's position, it might overlap with the laceration, occasionally leading to an increased difficulty in detecting and segmenting the needle or the complete absence of the needle's detection and segmentation. It is known that overlapping is still a limitation of CV-based analysis of visual input. In addition, when the needle is held at an inclination, either towards the camera or the participant, the angle is occasionally mistaken for a right angle, resulting in false positives. This metric's assessment displays a positive result, based on an accuracy of 77.78%, a precision of 77.73%, a recall of 78.57% and a F1 score of 78.15%.

The limitations of the CV model also affect the assessment of the *Needle inserted and removed using supination metric*, as this metric depends on the correct detection and segmentation of the needle and on the correct detection of the intersection between the needle and the needle holder or the forceps during the removal process. Indeed, when the removal process begins, the needle is mostly obstructed, which compromises its detection and segmentation and, therefore, the metric's assessment. This can both result in false positives and false negatives. This metric's assessment displays an accuracy of 75.56%, and a precision of 100.00%, a recall of 15.38% and a F1 score of 26.66%. The low recall and F1 score values reveal that the SUGAR tool tends to assess this metric as *Done*, regardless of whether the participant is using supination during the needle's insertion and removal. In addition, the metric analyses whether the needle holder's width is larger at the end of the insertion and removal process than at its start, which means that, when a participant unlatches the needle holder from the needle, its width increases causing the automated tool to produce a false positive.

A similar situation is observed in the assessment of the *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges metric*, for the calculations of the distance between the insertion and incision edges and between the removal site and incision edges are dependent on the correct detection and segmentation of both the needle and the laceration. As such, the metric's assessment produces false positives and false negatives, also dependent of the CV model's precision. For example, during needle removal, the needle might be removed too quickly towards the incision side, affecting the measurement of the distance between the incision edges and the needle's exit site. As a result, incorrect measurements

are extracted concerning the needle's removal, leading to an increased number of false negatives. Indeed, this metric's assessment displays an accuracy of 93.33%, a precision of 95.35%, a recall of 50.00% and a F1 score of 65.50%. While the recall and F1 score values are relatively low, this is due to the fact that there are only two videos in total with this metric considered *Not Done*, with one of them being correctly assessed by the SUGAR tool. As such, the recall value cannot be accurately explained, given the lack of information about the subpar performance of this metric.

A false positive issue may also occur with the assessment of the ***One pass of needle per suture insertion metric***, as it is calculated based on whether the participant moves the needle back towards the insertion side before demonstrating the locking of suture. In this situation, false positives may be identified if the needle happens to be dragged or held to the incision side during the knot tying phase, prior to the locking of suture. Further, if the participant does not perform the locking of suture according to the assessment of the automated tool, then false positives are likely to occur during the knot tying process. This metric's assessment displays an accuracy of 82.22%, a precision of 91.67%, a recall of 44.44% and a F1 score of 59.86%. Since the recall and F1 score values are relatively low, it is concluded that false positives occur more often in this metric due to the SUGAR tool's tendency to assess this metric as *Done* and to the fact that there is a reduced number of videos assessed as *Not Done* for this metric, making the recall value more susceptible to oscillate when the expert reviews' and SUGAR tool's scores differ.

Concerning the ***Demonstrated locking of suture when performing surgeons knot metric***, it calculates whether the left hand crosses over to the right side, possibly obscuring the camera's view of the suture. It is a metric that may present false positives due to the participant's movements to grab an object, such as suturing scissors, on the right side of the suturing pad with the left hand before the end of suture. Further, the metric can also present false negatives for participants who perform the locking of suture more discreetly, performing the correct movement without crossing the hand drastically to the other side. However, in an exam, the individual performing the simple interrupted suture is asked to act when performing the locking of suture, in order to avoid any subjectivity on whether this metric should be considered *Done* or *Not Done*. The metric's assessment displays an accuracy of 91.11%, a precision of 100.00% and a recall of 66.67%.

The ***Handled needle with forceps, not fingers metric***'s assessment displays an accuracy of 73.33%, a precision of 91.43%, a recall of 10.00% and a F1 score of 18.03%. The low recall and F1 score values reveal that the SUGAR tool tends to assess this metric as *Done*, regardless of whether the participant holds the needle

with their hands at any point during the suturing task. This is explained by the fact that this metric's calculation is based on the detection of an intersection between the needle and one of the hands and may present false positives due to the fact that the tool does not have 3D information and, therefore, cannot identify overlapping and differentiate between the hand partly obscuring the needle by hovering above it or the needle being held in front of the hand and the actual grasping of the needle with a hand. Further, this metric may also present false negatives if, when the needle is grasped, the needle stops being detected due to its obscurement by the hand, leading to a null or low number of video frames in which the grasping of the needle with a hand is detected.

The suture quality metrics applied to the CV-based analysis of suturing end-product images bring forth a relevant objective and reproducible assessment of suturing skills by the SUGAR tool. Still, here-in, as in the suture quality metrics applied to the CV-based analysis of suturing videos, also the explanation of identified false positives – the SUGAR tool presents a recall score of 61.75% – highlights the need to further advance prevailing AI-based technologies for object detection, image segmentation and video analysis.

Considering the *All sutures parallel to each other metric*, which displays an accuracy of 86.00%, a precision of 85.29%, a recall of 87.50% and a F1 score of 86.38%, it is still noted that, while the metric states explicitly that the assessment should focus on a comparison between the sutures, some surgical experts use this metric as an implicit assessment of whether the sutures are perpendicular to the laceration. Aside from explaining the presence of subjectivity in the traditional assessment of this particular metric, it also influences this work's results as it considers the surgical experts' understanding and assessment of suturing skills and competences as the ground truth for the work. It cannot be overlooked that a possible reason for the overall subjectivity present in the assessment and grading of suturing skills lies on the fact that some surgical experts focus on what is explicitly stated to be analysed by the particular metric, while other surgical experts analyse what they believe to be implicitly associated with the particular metric, subconsciously or not.

The *All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound metric* displays an accuracy of 72.00%, a precision of 57.14%, a recall of 80.00% and a F1 score of 66.66% in the assessment performed by the SUGAR tool. The relatively lower precision and F1 score values reveal that the tool detects a moderate number of false negatives. Indeed, both the false positives and false negatives identified are associated with the fact that the CV model does not possess a 100.00% accuracy in object detection and image segmentation. As such, false positives occur when the

sutures are not correctly and fully segmented, contouring shorter sutures than the ones in the image, as is observed for Image 208773, in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: False Positives Example for the *All suture placement equidistant from edge of wound* Metric in Image 208773 by the SUGAR Tool

The *Distance between sutures appropriate metric* displays an accuracy of 78.00%, a precision of 74.29%, a recall of 86.67% and a F1 score of 80.00% in the assessment performed by the SUGAR tool. Since these values are high, it is concluded that the SUGAR tool is able to accurately assess this metric.

The *Distance between sutures equal metric* displays an accuracy of 62.00%, a precision of 96.55%, a recall of 14.29% and a F1 score of 24.90% in the assessment performed by the SUGAR tool. The low recall and F1 score values reveal that the SUGAR tool tends to assess this metric as *Done*, regardless of whether the end-product suture image exhibits equal distance between each suture.

Also, false negatives have also been identified in the *Distance between sutures appropriate* metric and in the *Distance between sutures equal* metric. These false negatives are caused by the absence of detection of multiple sutures in the image, due to limitations of the CV model. This situation is observed in Image 210072, displayed in Figure 6.2.

The *Suture tension appropriate metric* displays an accuracy of 84.00%, a

Figure 6.2: False Negatives Example for the *Distance between sutures appropriate* and *Distance between sutures equal* Metrics in Image 210072 by the SUGAR Tool

precision of 66.67%, a recall of 91.43% and a F1 score of 77.11%. The relatively low precision and F1 score values reveal that the SUGAR tool detects more false negatives than false positives. This is explained by the fact that some of the images might not have the correct sRGB profile, which affects the intensity values of the pixels collected and, therefore, the automated assessment of the metric.

Focusing on the false positives, it is observed that there are nuances associated with the tension present: for example, in the case of Image 248992 the lack of tension applied is not detected by the automated SUGAR tool for there are no clear changes in pixel intensity. This situation is captured in Figure 6.3.

Figure 6.3: False Positives Example for the *Suture tension appropriate* Metric in Image 248992 by the SUGAR Tool

Considering the false negatives, it is seen that they result from the identification of a change in pixel intensity by the automated CV model that might be caused by the collection of a pixel containing a leftover of the suture, which assigns to the pixel a much higher intensity than to the other neighbouring pixels, as is the case of Image

263779, represented in Figure 6.4.

Figure 6.4: False Negatives Example for the *Suture tension appropriate* Metric in Image 263779 by the SUGAR Tool

In order to correctly assess each relevant suturing metric, fine-tuning must be applied through the use of ground-truth data. Indeed, a large and diverse dataset is considered ideal to correctly and accurately validate an expert system, such as the one devised for SUGAR. However, it is noted that, based on the expert reviews' scores, particular metrics present a lower number of incorrectly performed suturing tasks than correctly performed ones, which compromises the optimisation applied. These metrics include the *Insertion and exit of needle at approximately 2-4 mm from the incision edges* and the *One pass of needle per suture insertion* metrics.

It is conceded that the expert reviews demonstrate an expected level of subjectivity in the assessment and grading, with certain metrics showcasing a higher number of conflicting scores attributed by the surgical experts: the *Demonstrated locking of suture when performing the surgeons knot*, the *Needle inserted and removed using supination* and the *Suture tension appropriate* metrics present 55.56%, 44.44% and 60.00% of the reviews' scores as conflicting, respectively. It is noted that the *IRR* degree of agreement of the RCSI surgical experts concerning these exact suture quality metrics reinforce the same conclusion. Indeed, these metrics' scope and interpretation are even more difficult to capture and implement into the SUGAR tool's expert rule system, as they embed a degree of human-based tacit knowledge associated with the understanding of the subtleties and nuances required for suturing skills assessment. As such, further discussion is warranted regarding the relevant suture quality metrics for assessing proficient surgical suturing skills, as well as how to correctly grade them.

Overall, the novel CV-based SUGAR surgical suturing assessment and grading tool exhibits promising results as a Proof-of-Concept, demonstrating the design,

development, implementation, testing and validation of core AI-enabled functional capabilities for an automated, objective and reproducible suture quality metrics' assessment and grading system.

From an academic standpoint, the SUGAR Proof-of-Concept sets an encouraging avenue towards the development of more precise and proficient AI CV models for object detection and image segmentation, namely for surgical applications and, particularly in the educational and training field.

While researching the assessment and grading of suturing skills, the SUGAR tool also addresses the inherent limitations or shortcoming of today's state-of-the-art in CV methods and techniques. Leveraging the Thesis's scientific and technical background review, the SUGAR tool explores alternatives, including the traditional approaches, to overcome specific challenges, such as overlapping objects, 3D information and spatial-temporal modelling. The effects of this effort, translated into improved model design, manual labelling of datasets and an expert rule system, have been successful in improving the SUGAR Proof-of-Concept's overall precision and recall scores and establish valuable information towards further development of automated suturing skills assessment and grading systems.

Further, AI-based training tools are reshaping surgical education by improving skill acquisition, providing real-time feedback, and enhancing long-term retention. From an applicational real-world perspective, the Thesis's work echoes the significant benefits offered by automated suturing skills assessment tools, by providing objective and cost-efficient evaluation of surgical performance, leading to improved training, accelerating the learning process and leading to faster proficiency, and potentially better patient outcomes, minimising complications like bleeding and tearing. The need for fully trained surgical trainees and highly competent surgical trainers continues to rise, as the shortage of healthcare professionals worsens. The expectation is there for the SUGAR tool and automated suturing skills assessment tools alike to expedite the training time, facilitate a larger number of surgical trainees to be trained, support objective grading and contribute to a more standardised and evidence-based training design that ultimately delivers highly qualified surgical professionals.

Concerning the Thesis's societal impact, this work is well-aligned with the health- and education-related Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), that is SDGs 3 and 4, created by the United Nations to attain peace and prosperity [124]. Aside from capitalising on relevant investments on digital healthcare technologies, the Thesis's results – a new CV-based grading tool to assess surgical suturing skills and competences – provide tangible benefits that support superior surgical skills and improve

patient safety and health outcomes, as well as promote a novel surgical training assessment tool to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of medical education, contributing to a high-quality education and lifelong training portfolio for surgical trainees.

By improving the quality of surgical training, the SUGAR tool may contribute to a more skilled workforce, potentially leading to better job opportunities and economic growth in the healthcare sector, effectively assisting with the objectives of SDG8 on Decent Work and Economic Growth. Finally, the contribution to technological innovation, namely concerning the development of CV-based assessment tools, is also relevant for attaining SDG9 for Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure. In conclusion, this Thesis's work has the potential to add to the UN SDGs by improving surgical training, enhancing access to quality education, and promoting innovation in the healthcare sector.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Work

This Master's Thesis presents the SUGAR Surgical Suturing Grader tool, a Proof-of-Concept developed to demonstrate the feasibility of applying CV-based techniques to implement an automated suturing skills assessment and grading system. The work results in a novel video-based approach for observing continuous, long sequence of surgical students and experts' hands and surgical tools movements with a camera and then modelling and evaluating the surgical suturing skill demonstrated in the observation through the application of advanced and traditional CV techniques.

Currently, the evaluation of suturing skills and competences has been known to lack precision, quantitative data and reproducibility, while being highly subjective and prone to bias. Therefore, a need for objective methods has motivated the development of technology-based approaches to surgical training. Compared with manual video-based assessment, AI-based methods are faster, potentially less subjective and more reproducible, and require less trainer-hours, being always available for training purposes. Particularly, the YOLOv11 algorithm is designed to excel in speed and accuracy for object detection tasks, while supporting a range of CV tasks.

The foundation of this Master's Thesis is the work conducted in SUGAR Lite [120], which verified the feasibility of a CV-based tool to reliably detect and segment suture components, and assess the suture's quality through relevant metrics. It focused on top view images of simple interrupted sutures, exhibiting promising results regarding the metrics' grading by distinguishing between the quality of sutures performed by a novice and an expert.

For this Thesis, relevant suture quality metrics were necessary to validate the SUGAR tool. RCSI's surgical experts were consulted and a set of thirteen metrics for the tool's overall performance validation was identified, based on three of the four assessment

scales used by the RCSI. This set of metrics is comprised of one to be applied to human-based input collected before the suturing task starts, seven to be applied to the suturing videos and five to be applied to the sutures' end-product images.

Due to the lack of publicly available and adequate datasets for this Thesis, a new dataset is created using the suturing videos captured, through the application of manual labelling techniques. Fifty-one HD videos were obtained during the RCSI CST Bootcamp 2025 with a suturing station purposely designed by RCSI experts, whereas the analysis of images utilises the Noraset *et al.*'s dataset. At the end of the training stage, the CV model chosen for this Thesis displays a precision of 92.0% and recall value of 87.3% for surgical suturing tools detection and segmentation and a precision of 95.6% and a recall value 90.3% for the end-product's suture components detection and segmentation.

The software development work in the Thesis involves the design and implementation of the SUGAR tool's expert system to assess and grade the relevant suture quality metrics. Since these metrics are specified with the help of RCSI surgical experts, the validation approach consists of a comparative analysis between the SUGAR's outputs and the expert reviews' results. The SUGAR's validation results – i.e. an overall accuracy of 81.01%, a precision of 85.68%, a recall of 61.75% and F1 score of 71.77% – demonstrate that the novel SUGAR tool is capable of reliably detecting and tracking the movements of hands and surgical tools, of detecting and segmenting different surgical tools and sutures in interrupted sutures, as well as of assessing and grading suturing performance based on specific suture quality metrics.

Notwithstanding, it is also noted that this work presents limitations that can be addressed in future work. For example, the trained model's capability to correctly detect and segment objects can be further improved. Indeed, the dataset is one of the most prominent influencers, with large and diverse datasets considered important. Obtaining a larger and more diversified dataset would significantly improve the performance of the CV model.

In addition, the metrics are designed for evaluating right-handed individuals. While there were captured videos of left-handed participants (6 videos), these were a minority and, due to the Proof-of-Concept's constricted timeframe, the SUGAR tool is not implemented to assess left-handed individuals.

Further, the Master's Thesis has benefited from the RCSI guidance and expertise. As such, in order to improve the universality of the work the implemented metrics, how they are assessed, and their final thresholds must be revised and changed accordingly for deployment in other organisations. In addition, the SUGAR tool Proof-of-Concept

is currently fitted to work with the videos and data collected in the scope of this Thesis, using the RCSI suturing station setup described in section 3.2.1.

Advancing the maturity of the Proof-of-Concept towards a usable product, an interface should be created for the SUGAR tool, allowing for an intuitive use of the tool developed. For example, the *Appropriate suture choices: 3-0 or 4-0 size, non-absorbable (absorbability), monofilament (structure)* metric would benefit from a multiple-choice format, enabling the surgical trainee to change answers until submitting the answers. Once the surgical trainee chooses to submit, the suturing video recording and analysis would start.

Future work should also address the improvement of the overall *IRR* score in the validation effort, particularly by applying this core for AI benchmarking, with the long-term ambition for the CV-based assessment system to achieve the same (or improved) level of consistency as a human-based assessment system. This work would deliver an effective short-term benefit towards assisting human evaluators in reducing bias and subjectivity, while serving as a valuable indicator of the increased objectivity, consistency and credibility of the suturing skills assessments and grading produced by the SUGAR tool.

Finally, future work may also focus on advancing automated approaches to suturing training, using AI technologies to offer real-time performance tracking, personalised feedback, and enhanced skill retention.

Despite the discussed limitations, this Master's Thesis provides strong foundational work to adopt CV-based techniques for automated suturing skills assessment and grading. The successful achievement of the SUGAR Proof-of-Concept for an automated suturing skills grading tool cements innovative AI-enabled training approaches as a new paradigm in the objective assessment of suturing skills and performance, improving skill acquisition and long-term proficiency.

In summary, the main contributions of this Thesis's work are described as follows:

- Identification of relevant objective suture quality metrics to predict the level of expertise;
- Creation of a novel dataset for detection and segmentation of surgical suturing tools and the surgeon's hands;
- Attainment of a high alignment between the expert reviews' scores and SUGAR's outputs;

- Verification of the feasibility of applying CV-based techniques to suturing skills' quality assessment;
- Development of a novel Proof-of-Concept for a low-cost video-based grading tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.

This Thesis's work also produced a poster (Appendix C) and a video (<https://youtu.be/QKtjJ8VtriU>). These materials aim to reinforce the reach and dissemination of the SUGAR tool's results and its contribution to advance the application of CV-based techniques to develop automated suturing skills assessment and grading systems.

Appendix A

Ethics-Related Documentation

Next, the Thesis's Study Protocol is presented, informing about the goals, methodology, data collection and analysis procedures to ensure the study is conducted ethically and effectively.

SUGAR

Surgical sUturing

GrAdeR

Study Protocol

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

STUDY PROTOCOL	1
INTRODUCTION	3
<i>HYPOTHESIS</i>	5
<i>MAIN OBJECTIVE</i>	5
METHODOLOGY	5
<i>STUDY DESIGN</i>	5
<i>STUDY TIMEFRAME</i>	6
<i>STUDY PARTICIPANTS</i>	6
<i>SELECTION CRITERIA</i>	6
<i>RANDOMISATION PROCESS</i>	7
RECRUITMENT	7
VOLUNTARINESS	8
ACCESSIBILITY	9
RIGHT TO WITHDRAW	10
PRIVACY AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION	10
<i>GENERAL RULES AND PRINCIPLES</i>	10
<i>SPECIFICATIONS</i>	13
INFORMED CONSENT	13

INTRODUCTION

Suturing is a fundamental surgical skill required in a variety of operations and, as such, surgical trainees' skills are meticulously evaluated by surgical educators. Currently, this evaluation is based on subjective rating scales that often lack precision and reproducibility, and has been proven to be resource intensive, time-consuming and expensive. Also, there is the potential for subjectivity and bias. Therefore, a need for objective methods has motivated the development of technology-based approaches, determining precise quantification of metrics that define best surgical practices factors, capable of encapsulating potential value to certification organisations, credentials committees and surgical educators, as well as providing surgeons in training with objective feedback.

The Surgical sUturing GrAdeR (SUGAR) Study aims to deliver an objective, reliable, and cost-effective method to evaluate surgical suturing skills, using computer vision (CV). SUGAR uses object detection algorithms, such as YOLOv10, to detect and track surgical needles and suturing tools, and Deep Learning (DL) models, such as Xception, to assess surgical skills using metrics, such as hesitation and needle placement and orientation. Skill assessment metrics are calculated based on the estimated hands and tools' trajectories, which are then used to predict the surgical trainees' suturing skill levels.

To achieve its goals, the SUGAR Study proposes to involve 12 surgical trainees and 3 expert surgical trainers and collect high-quality videos of their hands performing surgical suturing, to establish valid motion trajectories of both hands and surgical tools and then use those trajectories to predict the surgical trainees' suturing skill levels. Given the need for objective methods for the evaluation of surgical suturing skills, the SUGAR Study aims to develop a novel objective and low-cost video-based tool capable of assessing and grading medical students' surgical suturing skills. This study represents a significant step towards reducing the need for expert review of sutures and enabling medical students to perform self-directed learning in suturing skills.

The SUGAR Study is committed to adhere to the highest European research integrity and ethical and fundamental rights standards, while carrying out its study activities. The SUGAR Study is particularly attentive to the main ethical principles governing human subject research: respect for autonomy, respect for private life, beneficence and non-maleficence. These principles are encapsulated in relevant European and national regulations, including the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Irish data protection law.

Since the SUGAR Study's planned research activities imply interaction with individual surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers, special attention and substantial effort is devoted to ensure that the values and fundamental rights (e.g. dignity, integrity, privacy, protection of personal data, right to equal treatment, freedom of thought) of these stakeholders are fully respected and enforced. The SUGAR Study is committed to satisfy the individual human participants' needs and safeguard their interests.

The following sections detail the objectives and purpose of the SUGAR Study, the methodology applied, and the measures and best practices adopted by the SUGAR Study to ensure that the planned research activities comply with the EU ethical and fundamental rights standards. In particular, they describe the measures and actions that are adopted, respected and enforced by those involved in the development of the SUGAR Study, namely the research activities involving human participants.

DECLARATION

As the Research Student leading the SUGAR Study, Laura Manso is in charge of organising and implementing the human participation research activities in the SUGAR Study to be held at the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland in June 2025.

Laura Manso declares to fully observe and enforce the provisions contained in the present Study Protocol. In particular, Laura Manso will adopt and enforce the following measures and best practices with respect to the organisation and implementation of the human participation research activities in the SUGAR Study to be held at the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland in June 2025.

OBJECTIVES AND PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Hypothesis

The objective, reliable and low-cost video-based tool capable of establishing valid motion trajectories of both hands and surgical tools and then use those trajectories to predict the surgical trainees' suturing skill levels will be feasible to implement and effective in assessing and grading medical students' surgical suturing skills.

Main Objective

To evaluate the feasibility and preliminary effectiveness of the objective and low-cost video-based tool to assess and grade medical students' surgical suturing skills, by analysing 100 high quality videos of hands of surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

The study design of SUGAR encompasses the active involvement of three expert surgical trainer in the identification of the metrics or performance criteria associated with specific highly competent surgical suturing skills, as well as the capture of high-quality videos of their hands performing surgical suturing to establish valid motion trajectories of both hands and tools. Also, twelve surgical trainees will record their hands performing surgical suturing to establish valid motion trajectories of both hands and tools. Then, the developed SUGAR tool will use the YOLOv10 algorithm to reliably detect and track hands and surgical needles' trajectories, based on which skill assessment metrics will be calculated. Deep learning methods, such as Xception, will be applied to distinguish between the surgical suturing skills of novices and experts and the tool will predict a grading level to each video. At the same time, at least one expert surgical trainer will grade the suturing videos and, finally, their grades will be compared with the grading predicted by the SUGAR tool, in order to assess the SUGAR tool's performance.

Study Timeframe

The duration of the SUGAR Study is estimated at 2 months, from June to August 2025, including the time necessary after the recruitment of the last volunteer for creating the video datasets, performing data analysis and preparing the Masters' Thesis report.

Study Participants

The SUGAR Study will actively involve at least 12 surgical trainees and 3 expert surgical trainers from the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland (RCSI). The minimum number of individual human participants in the study will be 100 volunteers.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria for surgical trainees are:

- **Minimum age:** Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme at RCSI with at least 18 years old at the time of the enrolment;
- **Suturing and needlework experience:** Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme with less than 2 years of experience with surgical suturing;
- **Informed Consent:** Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme must provide their signed informed consent to participate in the study.

The inclusion criteria for surgical trainers are:

- **Maximum age:** Expert surgical trainers at RCSI or in RCSI's contact list up to 65 years old at the time of the enrolment;
- **Suturing experience:** Expert surgical trainers with more than 5 years of suturing experience;
- **Suturing practice:** Expert surgical trainers who practiced suturing in the last year;
- **Informed Consent:** Expert surgical trainers must provide their signed informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

The exclusion criteria for surgical trainees are:

- **Age restrictions:** Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme at RCSI who are younger than 18 years or older than 65 years at the time of the enrolment;
- **Suturing and needlework experience:** Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme with more than 2 years of experience with surgical suturing;
- **Consent issues:** Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme who have not signed the informed consent form.

The exclusion criteria for surgical trainers are:

- **Maximum age:** Expert surgical trainers at RCSI or in RCSI's contact list who are older than 65 years old at the time of the enrolment;
- **Suturing experience:** Expert surgical trainers with less than 5 years of suturing experience;
- **Suturing practice:** Expert surgical trainers who have not practiced suturing in the last year;
- **Consent issues:** Expert surgical trainers who have not signed the informed consent form.

Randomisation Process

There will be no randomisation in the SUGAR Study. All participants will provide a video recording of their hands performing suturing.

RECRUITMENT

Given the scope of the SUGAR Study and the planned research activities, all human participants in the SUGAR Study are identified or recruited by the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland (RCSI). An invitation will address the surgical trainees who are Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme enrolled in the suturing skills class and the expert surgical trainers who are RCSI employees or whose contact details are available in the RCSI contacts list.

All the invited human participants agree to take part in the SUGAR Study research activities by accepting the invitation they receive. The invitation is issued in advance of the scheduled date of the concerned SUGAR Study research activities. The invitation is issued in writing and orally. It will consist of specific information on the SUGAR Study and on the scope and goals of the targeted research activity. Together with the invitation, individual human participants receive a Participant

Information Leaflet (PIL) and a Consent Form to be read, understood, - if necessary – further explained, and signed before any such activities occur. The content of the Consent Form to be signed will be read and explained to the participants carefully.

The SUGAR Study research activities include adult human participants only. They are adults fully able and capable to provide explicit, written, freely-given, specific and informed consent to take part in the concerned activities, and who sign the consent form before it occurs. No human participant with potentially impaired capacity to provide a freely-given, specific and informed consent (e.g. minors, mentally-ill, socio-economic disadvantaged groups, prisoners, institutionalised populations) are involved in any SUGAR Study research activities.

The identification, recruitment and participation of individual human participants in the SUGAR Study activities occur in full respect of the EU ethical standards and principles, which are also integrated into the present Study Protocol.

VOLUNTARINESS

Participation in the SUGAR Study research activities is strictly voluntary. Individual human participants agree to participate on the basis of an invitation issued by the RCSI in advance of the scheduled date of the SUGAR Study research activities (*see also the above section on “Recruitment”*). The invitation consists of information on the SUGAR Study, as well as on the scope and aims of the specific SUGAR Study research activities. Individual participants also receive a PIL and a Consent Form to be read, understood, - if necessary – further explained and signed. Participants unable to give free and informed consent (*e.g.* minors, mentally-impaired) are not considered.

Before taking part to the SUGAR Study research activities, invited individual human participants are verbally briefed on the SUGAR Study, as well as on the scope and aims of the specific SUGAR Study research activities, and asked again for confirmation of their consent to take part to it. Briefings and documentation are available in a language in which the human participants are comfortable with and can fully understand. Participants for whom this cannot be assured do not take part in the SUGAR Study research activities. Briefings and documentation is free from jargon and readily accessible also to non-specialists.

Individual participants have access – before, during and after the activities – to the Maynooth University’s research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey, involved in

the organisation and implementation of the SUGAR Study research activities and, if needed, to the representatives of the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland, Professor Oscar Traynor, or to the representatives of the Maynooth University Ethics Committee, who can advise them on any issues, questions, doubts, comments they may have. The MU research student Laura Manso is provided with the mobile number and email address of the MU supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey, and the contacts of the MU Ethics Committee, to be contacted in any moment and advise on demand.

Invited individual human participants are fully briefed as to their right to withdraw (*see also below*) from the SUGAR Study research activities. They are briefed as to the possible risks and benefits of participation.

Invited individual human participants are not placed in any situation in which there is a likelihood of physical, mental or emotional harm. Their dignity is preserved and safeguarded: the MU research student Laura Manso is available to satisfy any reasonable request or need coming from individual human participants; the MU research student Laura Manso pays great attention in identifying early signs of distress or discomfort from human participants, and is ready to stop the research activities as soon as such signs are detected.

Individual human participants are not placed in any environment threatening to their physical or mental integrity. Potential cultural hurdles are identified in advance and *ad hoc* measures taken in order to avoid any incident.

Where invited individual human participants are introduced to the SUGAR Study research activities through their employer, it is ensured that they are under no undue explicit or implicit pressure to take part.

Invited individual human participants are given the names and contact details of the SUGAR Study's research student Laura Manso, organising and implementing the SUGAR Study research activities.

ACCESSIBILITY

Invited participants experiencing disabilities and special needs are guaranteed their right to access, on an equal basis, to the physical environment and facilities where the SUGAR Study research activities take place. The same goes for their right to access relevant information and communications provided during the SUGAR Study research activities. Specific assistance is offered to them in case they need it.

RIGHT TO WITHDRAW

Invited human participants will have – and understand that they retain it at all times – the right to withdraw themselves and their data from the SUGAR Study research activities and, in general, from the SUGAR Study. They may do so for any (or no) reason and without prejudice. They may be asked for a reason, but it will be clear that there is no obligation, and that they are under no pressure whatsoever, to answer. Invited individual human participants are briefed, from the outset, on the procedures for ending their participation to the research activity, i.e. by simply expressing their free choice to withdraw. Withdrawal can be communicated orally or by using special signs (e.g. by raising their hand).

The MU research student Laura Manso pays great attention in identifying early signs of distress or discomfort from human participants, and is ready to stop the research activity as soon as such signs are detected.

PRIVACY AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION

General Rules and Principles

A data minimisation policy is adopted that means no data which is not strictly necessary for developing the SUGAR Study research activities is collected and therefore processed. Whenever participants' personal data are to be collected and processed, these participants will be individually asked for consent and informed about: the entity that is processing their data; the data protection principles applied and enforced; the security measures adopted to protect their data from accidental destruction or loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure or access; data transfer policies; their rights to access, modify and erase their personal data, to object to data processing and how to enforce them. All these information will be detailed to participants in the PIL and Consent Form they are asked to read, understand and sign. Individual human participants will be also briefed orally about the adopted procedure for processing their personal data before taking part to any demonstration activity.

As a general rule, human participants' personal data are stored in secure MU servers and processed only by the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey, that are involved in organising and implementing the SUGAR Study activities. Data will be collected and stored on paper and computer files protected by state-of-the-art physical and logical

security measures. Examples of such measures are: the room and archive containing the paper folder reporting human participants' personal data are locked and accessed only by the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey; the archive is accessed only by the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey; the collected video imagery will be anonymised at the point of collection (RCSI) and stored in secure MU servers.

Individual participants' data are not in any case shared with or disclosed to anyone outside the organisation and implementation of the SUGAR Study and the targeted research activity. In other words, this means that individual personal information is processed only by the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey. Third-parties have access only to anonymised information or non-personal data.

Only if necessary or required, this data will be shared with the authorities. The SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey, may also disclose collected data to the extent that it is required to do so by law, in connection to any legal proceedings or prospective legal proceedings and in order to establish, defend or exercise their rights.

All personal data collected and stored within the by the SUGAR Study and for the purpose of the SUGAR Study research activities will be permanently and irrevocably erased on the study's completion. No personal information is published in the study's master thesis, reports or public documents, or otherwise disclosed outside the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey, involved in organising and implementing the SUGAR Study research activities. Any personal and professional views or comments that might be voluntarily provided by participants during the SUGAR Study research activities will be processed in a way that inhibits tracing those opinions back to participant (anonymised information).

The SUGAR Study will collect the individual human participants' age range, gender, years of suturing experience (expert surgical trainers), years of needlework experience (surgical trainees) and a video of their hands performing surgical suturing. No further sensitive data (concerning sexual habits and orientation, religious, political and philosophical beliefs) will be – either directly or indirectly – collected or in any way retained. In the unforeseen and accidental event of collection, this data are immediately destroyed.

Individual participants' data will not be mined or used for any purpose other than those explicitly and clearly needed for the running of the SUGAR Study research activities.

The competent Ethics Committee of Maynooth University is notified of the SUGAR Study research activities and associated procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction, complying with the national and EU legislation. Their opinion or comments are enforced by the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey. The Ethics Committee of Maynooth University is kept informed of any issue concerning the protection of participants' personal information that may arise.

Specifications

Source of data

The data to be processed in the SUGAR Study research activities are:

1. Age range and gender information. The age range will be provided by the participants as the following:

18-25; 26-35; 36-50; 51-60; over 60.

The gender information will be provided by the participants as the following:

Male; Female; Non-binary.

2. Years of suturing and/or needlework experience;

3. Video recordings of the hands of individual human participants performing surgical suturing.

Data of all the four categories will be provided by the individual human participants themselves.

With regard to the video recordings of the hands of individual human participants to the SUGAR Study research activity, these video recordings are collected and processed in a secure ICT environment. Once the SUGAR Study research activity is over, the collected video recordings will be anonymised at the point of collection (RCSI) and then stored only for the SUGAR Study research purposes. They are also irrevocably deleted upon the SUGAR Study's completion. The MU Ethics Committee will advise the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey, on the issue of and monitor the full data collection, processing, storage, and deletion process.

INFORMED CONSENT

The SUGAR Study PIL and Consent Form will be jargon-free, written by using language and terms understandable to the individual human participants. The Participants Information Leaflet will detail all relevant information that shall be known by the human participant in order to give informed consent; and the Consent Form to be signed in case invited individuals choose to participate in the SUGAR Study research activities. The PIL is tailored to the research activities that participants are required to carry out. It reflects the scope of the research activity, detailing the actions taken by the SUGAR Study research student, Laura Manso, and supervisor, Professor

Gerard Lacey, and what it is expected from participants. In particular, it will be evident that individual human participants in the SUGAR Study research activities have the right:

- To know that participation is voluntary;
- To ask questions and receive understandable answers before making a decision;
- To know the degree of risk and burden involved in participation;
- To know who will benefit from participation;
- To withdraw themselves and their data from the SUGAR Study at any time;
- To know how their data will be collected, protected, shared as anonymised data during the SUGAR Study and destroyed at the end;
- To know how to enforce their right to access, modification, erasure and object.

Invited individual human participants' understanding will be double-checked on-site before the SUGAR Study research activities start.

Examples of question to be asked orally in order to elucidate understanding of the above: *If you decide not to take part in this research study, do you know what your options are? Do you know that you do not have to take part in this research study, if you do not wish to? Do you have any questions? Do you have specific requests or special needs? Do you need further assistance? Do you know that you can ask me questions later, if you wish to? Do you know that I have given the contact details of the person who can give you more information about the study? Do you know that you have the rights to access, modify and erase your personal data? Do you know how to enforce these rights? Can you tell me if you have understood correctly the benefits that you will have if you take part in the study? Do you know if the research will pay for your travel costs and time lost? Do you have any other questions?*

Next, the Thesis's Data Protection Impact Assessment is presented, identifying how the research will comply with data protection obligations and meet participants' expectations of privacy.

ROYAL COLLEGE OF SURGEONS

Health Research- Data Protection Impact Assessment

Relevant Information

Title	Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI
Author	Principal Investigator Laura Manso
Publication Date	
Superseded Documents	n/a
Related Documents	Data Protection Policy
Version	1.4
Data Protection Officer	DONALL KING Phone : E-Mail: dataprotection@rcsi.ie

This policy may be updated at any time (without notice) to ensure changes to RCSI organisation structure and/or business practices are properly reflected in the policy. Please ensure that you check for the most up to date version of this policy.

Table Of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	3
2	THE PROJECT – BRIEF DESCRIPTION.....	3
3	PRIVACY RISKS	3
3.1	PATIENT / RESEARCH PARTICIPANT /STAFF / SERVICE USER PERSPECTIVE	3
4	DPIA - HEALTH RESEARCH – ENSURING PARTICIPANTS’ RIGHTS	7
	<i>Data Flows</i>	<i>10</i>
	<i>AI Software Development</i>	<i>10</i>
	<i>AI Explainability.....</i>	<i>10</i>
	<i>Profiling.....</i>	<i>11</i>
	<i>Security Measures.....</i>	<i>11</i>
	<i>Conclusions and Agreed Actions</i>	<i>11</i>
5	PRIVACY IMPACT ASSESSMENT	12
5.1	SECTION 3 – PRIVACY ISSUES IDENTIFIED AND RISK ANALYSIS	23
5.1.1	<i>Identify the privacy risks</i>	<i>23</i>
5.1.2	<i>Identify the privacy solutions</i>	<i>23</i>
5.1.3	<i>Integrate the PIA outcomes back into the project plan</i>	<i>26</i>
6	APPENDIX 1: STUDY ETHICS APPROVAL BY MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY	27
7	APPENDIX 2: RISK ASSESSMENT FORM BY MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY	28

1 Introduction

This DPIA is part of the Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI (SUGAR) Study's research activities and has been conducted before the study's personal data gathering starts. The DPIA also includes the risk assessment form as an annex. The DPIA provides an assessment whether the processing of personal data will be performed correctly from the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) point of view and it also includes the assessment of health and safety risks. Through this DPIA, it can be assessed that the SUGAR Study has adopted and implemented all the applicable ethical requirements to ensure data protection and privacy, as well as safety guidelines. This DPIA was prepared by Laura Manso, research student at Maynooth University (MU), under the supervision of Professor Gerard Lacey.

2 The Project – Brief Description

The Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI (SUGAR) Project aims to deliver an objective, reproducible, and cost-effective method to evaluate surgical suturing skills, using computer vision (CV). SUGAR uses object detection algorithms, such as YOLOv10m, to detect and track surgical needles and suturing tools, and Deep Learning (DL) models, such as Xception, to assess surgical skills using metrics, such as hesitation and needle placement and orientation. Several datasets, namely AIsuture and surgical-needle from Roboflow, will be used to train and evaluate the system based on objective metrics, such as the models' accuracy, F1 scores, precision, recall and computational time. The improvement and validation of the AI-based models will then proceed, with field tests, conducted at the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland (RCSI), allowing the collection of high-quality videos of the hands of surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers performing surgical suturing to establish valid motion trajectories of both hands and tools. Those trajectories will be used to discriminate between surgical trainees and experts suturing skills and predict suturing skill levels. A minimum of 15 participants, 12 surgical trainees and 3 expert surgical trainers, will be volunteers in this project. Finally, the surgical experts will support full system validation and the analysis of data and achieved results will be performed and reported.

3 Privacy Risks

3.1 Patient / Research Participant / Staff / Service User Perspective

The study does not involve patients or service users.

Eligible volunteer research participants to the study are Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme or expert surgical trainers (staff) at RCSI, willing to voluntarily perform a short video that

captures their hand movements while executing surgical suturing. The videos will be used to train and validate a video-based automatic tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.

All potential eligible participants will be provided with information about the study. The information sheets and privacy notices provided will include information on what type of data will be collected, where it will be stored and who will have access to it. Potential participants are in complete control of whether they choose to participate in the project or not. If potential participants would like to participate in the project, they will be asked to sign a consent form and will be informed that they are free to withdraw consent at any time for any reason and that this will not impact them in any way.

The data to be collected in the study – age range, gender, years of suturing and/or needlework experience, and videos of hands performing surgical suturing – are data required for describing the cohort, supporting the technical functionalities of the developed tools and assisting in the analysis of the study's outcome measures. Data minimisation will be employed to ensure that only data required for the study's purposes is captured, abiding to necessity and proportionality purposes. Following the collection of the participants' signed consent forms, the videos of hands performing surgical suturing will be recorded by Laura Manso and stored in secure servers of Maynooth University, behind a firewall, which will be only accessed by Laura Manso (authorised access) to conduct the study's activities. All collected video data will be anonymised at the point of collection (RCSI). All collected data will be permanently destroyed or deleted at the conclusion of the study.

Data collection entails the potential for risks associated with the non-authorised access, disclosure, or use of data, the accidental release of sensitive information and the misuse of data for malicious purposes. In addition, when involving studies of a limited size sample, there is a higher risk of identifiability of research participants.

To mitigate these risks, specific security measures will be adopted, including:

- The signed consent forms (identifiable data) will be collected and securely stored in a locked cabinet at Prof. Gerard Lacey's office at Maynooth University for the entire duration of the study. The captured videos, anonymised at the point of collection, will be stored in secure servers at the Maynooth University.
- Access to the study data will only be provided to authorised researchers: the PI, Laura Manso, and the academic supervisor, Prof. Gerard Lacey.
- The face-to-face contact with the research participants will be constrained to a maximum of 30-minute sessions, fully dedicated to the video capture of the participants' hands performing sutures. During the video capture sessions, the researcher will be monitoring the images at the computers' screens to validate the recordings.
- A tendentially equal, age- and gender-balanced sample will be sought, in order to reduce the identifiability risk by making it harder to pinpoint research participants based on demographic characteristics.

- Rigorous anonymisation practices will be applied, avoiding direct identifiers (addresses and email addresses will not be collected from research participants) and using full anonymisation (a unique code is given to each video that cannot be linked to the research participant) in all captured videos with no sound, so that the data cannot be linked back to research participants.
- The captured video data will be aggregated in a unique dataset for the study, preventing research participants from being identified.
- Special attention will be dedicated on how to inform research participants better and transparently about the use of their data, their rights concerning data protection and any potential risks of re-identification.
- Opportunities will be offered to research participants to discuss any concerns they may have concerning the use of their data and their own anonymity.

With the adoption of the above-mentioned mitigation measures, the likelihood potential for security risks associated with the non-authorized access, disclosure, or use of data, the accidental release of sensitive information, the misuse of data for malicious purposes and the identifiability of research participants is deemed very low or negligible.

In addition, a risk assessment on health and safety was performed for the study and is included as an Annex to this DPIA. All foreseeable health and safety risks were identified, and mitigation actions were presented. The risk assessment form was officially signed by a committee member of the MU Department of Health and Safety.

Detailing appropriate screening questions that are relevant to RCSI project initiatives will highlight specific and individual privacy considerations and assist in ensuring that proposed investment is proportionate to the risks involved:

		Yes	No	Unsure	Comments
1	Will information about individuals raise privacy concerns or expectations e.g. health records, criminal records or other information people would consider particularly private?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Will project initiative involve collection of new information about patients, visitors or staff?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3	Are you using information about individuals for a purpose it is not currently used for, or in a way it is not currently used?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
4	Will project initiative require use of patient data in ways which they may find intrusive ¹ ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
5	Will patient data be disclosed to other organisations or people who have not previously had routine access to such?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
6	Will project initiative involve using new technology which might be perceived as being privacy intrusive or biased e.g. biometrics or facial recognition?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
7	Will project initiative result in the Hospital making decisions or taking actions against individuals in ways which can have a significant negative impact on them?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

¹ Intrusion can come in the form of collection of excessive personal information, disclosure of personal information without consent and misuse of such information. It can include the collection of information through the surveillance or monitoring of how people act in public or private spaces and through the monitoring of communications whether by post, phone or online and extends to monitoring the records of senders and recipients as well as the content of messages

4 DPIA - Health Research – Ensuring Participants’ Rights

How can the rights be used?

Research participants must contact the named contact point for the SUGAR Study provided in the participant information leaflet (PIL), Principal Investigator Laura Manso, and clearly indicate that he/she wants to use his/her rights as a participant. Using of the rights must happen free of charge.

How quickly must the controller react to the requests concerning the participant’s rights?

The requests have to be answered without undue delay, but at the latest within a week. In case the requests are complicated or there are many of them, the period can be lengthened by a maximum of one month.

Right to obtain information on the processing of personal data

It is the controllers’ responsibility in the Study (Principal Investigator Laura Manso and Academic Supervisor Professor Gerard Lacey) to provide the means for a participant to exercise his/her rights. The information that must be provided to a participant under Article 13 or Article 14 GDPR has been covered in the participant information leaflet (PIL) that is given to a participant when requesting his/her consent for the processing.

Right of access

Research participants have the right to obtain information from the controllers as to whether or not their personal data is being processed, and when it is, access to the personal data and:

- the purposes of the processing;
- the categories of personal data concerned;
- the recipients to whom the personal data is or is going to be disclosed;
- the period for which the data is to be stored;
- the right to request from the controllers rectification, erasure or restriction of the processing, or to object such processing;
- the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority;
- the source of the processed personal data when not received from the participant;
- the existence of profiling and information about the logic involved.

As stated in Article 15 GDPR, the controller shall provide a copy of the personal data undergoing processing. Where the participant makes the request by electronic means, and unless otherwise requested by the participant, the information shall be provided in a commonly used electronic form.

Right to rectification

The participant has the right to demand that the controllers rectify any incorrect or inaccurate personal data of him/her, including by means of providing a supplementary statement.

If the controllers find that, despite the views of the participant, the data is not inaccurate with regard to the purposes of processing, it does not have to rectify the data.

Right to erasure (right to be forgotten)

In certain situations, research participant have the right to erasure of their personal data, which is also known as the right to be forgotten. In the context of SUGAR Study, the controllers have to erase the personal data in question when:

- the personal data is no longer needed for the purposes for which it was collected;
- the participant withdraws his/her consent;
- the personal data has been processed illegally;
- the personal data has to be erased following a legal obligation stemming from the EU's or the Republic of Ireland's legislation.

In SUGAR, the right does not apply if the processing of the data is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

Right to withdraw the consent

As the processing will mainly be based on (explicit) consent (Articles 6(1)(a) and 9(2)(a) GDPR), there is no particular need for right to object data processing. Instead, as it is stated in Article 7(3) GDPR, the participant shall have the right to withdraw his or her consent at any time. The withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal. Prior to giving consent, the participant shall be informed of these matters. It shall be as easy to withdraw as to give consent.

Right to restriction of processing

The participant has a right to request a restriction of processing from the data controller. The request can be made when:

- the participant disputes the accuracy of the personal data in question;

- the processing is illegal but the participant objects on erasure and in place of it demands restriction of their use;
- the controllers do not need the personal data anymore, but the participant needs them for establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

When the processing has been restricted, the personal data in question can only be processed:

- with a consent from the participant;
- for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims;
- for protection of another natural or legal person's rights;
- for reasons of important public interests of the EU or a Member State.

Notification obligation regarding rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing

Article 19 of the GDPR states that the controllers shall communicate any rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing carried out to each recipient to whom the personal data have been disclosed, unless this proves impossible or involves disproportionate effort. The controllers shall inform the participants about those recipients if the participants request it.

In the SUGAR Study, the participant will be informed of all the recipients in the information sheet described in the first paragraph of this section.

Right to data portability

The participant has a right of acquiring any personal data given to the controllers in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and have the right to transmit those data to another controller when the processing is based on consent and the processing is carried out by automated means. The right does not apply to data that the controllers have created on the basis of data supplied by the participant (e.g. suturing skills grading) or that has been compiled through the analysis of data generated by observing the participant (such as the video analysis).

Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority

According to Article 77(1) GDPR, a participant has the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority, in particular in the Member State of his or her habitual residence, place of work or of an alleged infringement of the GDPR. The European Data Protection Board maintains the list of the Member States authorities, and it can be viewed in https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb/members_en.

Data Flows

Once a participant is consented to participate in the SUGAR Study, identifiable information (including consent forms, age range, gender, years of suturing and/or needlework experience, and videos of hands performing surgical suturing) will be stored in secure servers of the Maynooth University (MU), behind a firewall. The collected video data will be anonymised at the point of collection (RCSI) and stored at secure MU servers, which will be accessed by Laura Manso (authorised access) to conduct the project's activities in the project's research computer.

AI Software Development

The SUGAR Study uses object detection algorithms, such as YOLOv10m, to detect and track surgical needles and suturing tools, and Deep Learning (DL) models, such as Xception, to assess surgical skills using metrics, such as hesitation and needle placement and orientation.

In general, when fast and accurate detection is required, the one-stage YOLOv10 computer vision algorithm is considered one of the most prominent object detection algorithms, being one of the selected algorithms for this project, of which several models are then compared. The applied CV algorithms track reliable hands and tools' trajectories, and skill assessment metrics are then calculated based on the estimated hands' and tools' trajectories.

These metrics are assessed by various DL techniques, taking the labelled data and dividing it into training and validation sets, which are used to train and test the DL methods, respectively. The Xception model is one of the DL methods to be assessed in the SUGAR Study, together with other models that will be specifically developed for this project.

The AI-based models will support the development of a tool that is able to automate the review of suturing videos, discriminate between the suturing skills of surgical trainees and experts, and grade suturing skills.

AI Explainability

The SUGAR Study entails the development, deployment and use of AI-based systems and techniques, for AI algorithms are used to improve the detection and identification of suturing needles, suturing tools and hand movements in video imagery. These AI-based techniques will be developed considering the seven principles leading to trustworthy AI, promoted by the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence of the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), and will comply with the EU AI Act. AI robustness and trustworthiness of SUGAR will be ensured by building the AI models to follow standard methodologies for algorithm, hyper-parameter, and variable selection and to incorporate different approaches to explainability,

depending on the models used and, where possible, a confidence measurement on the prediction. eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques will be used, based upon explainability by design, model-specific explainers (class activation mapping, layer-wise relevance propagation, attention mechanisms), or more general black-box and model-agnostic (partial dependence plots, Shapley additive explanation, and permutation feature importance) explainers, if necessary. Once validated, models will be monitored to detect possible drifts and outliers. Any AI-generated data will be secured to guarantee its integrity and security, will have the ability to demonstrate how and from where the data has been created and will be validated by a human user.

Profiling

The SUGAR Study will not perform profiling on the collected data.

Security Measures

A folder containing the necessary information for project management, including the signed consent forms, will be retained in a locked cabinet in a locked office in the Electronic Engineering department at Maynooth University. The collected video data will be anonymised at the point of collection (RCSI) and stored in a secure MU server, protected by the University's firewall and security system. Only Laura Manso and Professor Gerard Lacey will have access to the study's data.

Conclusions and Agreed Actions

The SUGAR Study adheres to the highest standards of research integrity and is particularly attentive to the main ethical principles governing human subject research: respect for autonomy, respect for private life, beneficence and non-maleficence, principles that are encapsulated in relevant European and national regulations, including the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Irish data protection law.

All efforts have been taken to inform participants in a straightforward way about the planned data collection and processing, the foreseeable health and safety risks identified and their appropriate mitigation actions. Dedicated attention will also be placed into eXplainable Artificial Intelligence techniques and compliance with the EU AI Act.

Research ethics committee approval have been sought at MU and RCSI for the conduct of the SUGAR Study. The MU approval has been achieved on June 13th 2025 and is presented as Appendix 1.

5 Privacy Impact Assessment

Section 1: Background Information

Project Name	Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI
Organisation/Department	Electronic Engineering – Maynooth University
Assessment Completed By	Laura Manso
Job Title	Principal Investigator
Date completed	16 th June 2023
Phone/Mobile	+351 933 329 394
E-mail	laura.guerramanso.2025@mumail.ie
<p>Project/Change Outline: What is it that is being planned? If you have already produced this as part of the project's Project Initiation Document you may make reference to this, however a brief description of the project/process being assessed is still required.</p> <p>The Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI (SUGAR) Project aims to deliver an objective, reproducible, and cost-effective method to evaluate surgical suturing skills, using computer vision (CV). SUGAR uses object detection algorithms, such as YOLOv10m, to detect and track surgical needles and suturing tools, and Deep Learning (DL) models, such as Xception, to assess surgical skills using metrics, such as hesitation and needle placement and orientation. Several datasets, namely Alsuture and surgical-needle from Roboflow, will be used to train and evaluate the system based on objective metrics, such as the models' accuracy, F1 scores, precision, recall and computational time. The improvement and validation of the AI-based models will then proceed, with field tests, conducted at the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland (RCSI), allowing the collection of high-quality videos of the hands of surgical trainees and expert surgical trainers performing surgical suturing to establish valid motion trajectories of both hands and tools. Those trajectories will be used to discriminate between surgical trainees and experts suturing skills and predict suturing skill levels. A minimum of 15 participants, 12 surgical trainees and 3 expert surgical trainers, will be volunteers in this project. Finally, the surgical experts will support full system validation and the analysis of data and achieved results will be performed and reported.</p>	
<p>Purpose / Objectives: Why is DPIA being undertaken? This could be the objective of the process or the purpose of the system being implemented as part of the project.</p> <p>This DPIA is part of the Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI (SUGAR) Study's research activities and has been conducted before the study's personal data gathering starts. The DPIA provides an assessment whether the processing of personal data in the Study will be performed correctly from the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) point of view and it also includes the assessment of health and safety risks. Through this DPIA, it can be assessed that the SUGAR</p>	

Study has adopted and implemented all the applicable ethical requirements to ensure data protection and privacy, as well as safety guidelines.

What is the purpose of collecting the information within the system? For example patient treatment, patient administration, research, audit, reporting, staff administration etc.

The Study is concerned with the development, testing and validation of a novel low-cost video-based tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills. Videos of hands of surgical trainees and experts executing sutures will be captured and analysed using computer vision (CV) algorithms. Then, the application of advanced and optimised deep learning (DL) techniques will enable the assessment of the suturing skills demonstrated during observation, using metrics, such as the RCSI's Surgical Affairs Department validated checklist.

What are the potential privacy impacts of this proposal?: How will this change impact upon the patient or research participant? Provide a brief summary of what you feel these could be, it could be that specific information is being held that hasn't previously or that the level of information about an individual is increasing.

The Study involves a minimum of 15 volunteer research participants. Eligible participants in the Study are Year 1 surgical trainees in the national surgical training programme and expert surgical trainers at RCSI. These potential research participants will be recruited during the RCSI Surgical Bootcamp 2025 and their participation formalized through the signing of an informed consent form.

The informed consent forms have personal data, including the name, gender, age range and signature of the research participants. The videos of the hands performing surgical suturing will have no sound and no identifiable information. At the time of their collection, they will be anonymised with key numbers.

It is noted that there are privacy risks associated with the data collection and storage. These risks are presented in section 5 - Privacy Impact Assessment, as well as the associated mitigation actions.

At the conclusion of the study in August 2025, all study data will be destroyed or permanently deleted.

Provide details of any previous Privacy Impact Assessment or other form of personal data compliance assessment done on this initiative. If this is a change to an existing system, a PIA may have been undertaken during the project implementation.

The study has also been submitted to the ethics approval of the Maynooth University. This approval was received on June 13th 2025 and is included as Appendix 1. Also a risk assessment has been performed and accepted by the Maynooth University, included here-in as Appendix 2.

Stakeholders: Who is involved in this project/change? Please list stakeholders, including internal, external, organisations (public/private/third) and groups that may be affected by this system/change.

The study is proposed by Laura Manso, a masters' student in the Department Electronic Engineering, Maynooth University, as the Masters' thesis. The research study is performed under the academic supervision of Professor Gerard Lacey, Head of Robotics in the Department Electronic Engineering, Maynooth University. This study is conducted in collaboration with the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, namely Professor Oscar Traynor, the Director of International Surgical Training Programmes, Dr. Dara O'Keefe, Simulation Lead in Postgraduate Surgical Education and Training, and Mr. Donncha Ryan, Lead Technology Officer at Surgical Affairs.

The research participants in the study are all volunteers. Eligible participants are Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme or expert surgical trainers (staff) at RCSI, willing to voluntarily perform a short video that captures their hand movements while executing surgical suturing. The number of research participants will be 15, being 12 the surgical trainees and 3 the expert surgical trainers. The videos will be used to train and validate a video-based automatic tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.

Data Controller

Who is the Data Controller?

Explain how the Data Controller is the person/entity responsible for the purpose and means of the data processing described in the DPIA.

The data controllers are Laura Manso and Professor Gerard Lacey of the Maynooth University. Laura Manso is the study's Principal Investigator and the study is performed under the academic supervision of Professor Gerard Lacey. Laura Manso and Professor Gerard Lacey are the only authorised personnel to access the study's data in order to adequately conduct the study.

The signed consent forms folder will be securely stored in a locked cupboard at the Electronic Engineering Department in Maynooth University and only Professor Gerard Lacey, the academic supervisor of the study, and Laura Manso, the Principal Investigator, will have access to the consent forms folder.

The videos of hands performing surgical suturing will be captured, with no sound and no identifiable information. At the time of their collection, they will be anonymised with key numbers.

All data that is collected about you during the course of the study will be kept confidential. No names will be identified at any time. All hard copy information will be held in a locked cabinet at the researcher's place of work, electronic information will be encrypted and held securely on MU PC or servers and will be accessed only by Laura Manso and Professor Gerard Lacey. No information will be distributed to any other unauthorised individual or third party.

Section 2: The Data Involved

What data is being collected, shared or used? (If there is a chart or diagram to explain attach it as an appendix)			
	Data Type	Justifications – there must be justification for collecting the particular items and these must be specified here – consider which data items you could remove, without compromising the needs of the project?	
Information that identifies the individual and their personal characteristics	Name	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	The study's informed consent form will require the age range of the participants, in order to ascertain that the target audience is Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme (inclusion criteria).
	Address	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Postcode	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Dob	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Age	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Sex	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Gender	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Racial/ethnic origin	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Tel no.	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Physical description	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	IHI no. (or similar)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Mobile/home phone no.	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Email address	<input type="checkbox"/>	

	Yes	N/A	Justification
i. Information relating to the individual's physical or mental health or condition. Information relating to genetic information(biological samples such as chromosomal or DNA samples) and biometric information(such as fingerprints or facial recognition)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
ii. Information relating to the individual's sex life.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
iii. Information relating to the individual's sexual orientation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
iv. Information relating to the family of the individual and the individual's lifestyle and social circumstances	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
v. Information relating to any offences committed or alleged to be committed by the individual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
vi. Information relating to criminal proceedings, outcomes and sentences regarding the individual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
vii. Information which relates to the education and any professional training of the individual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
viii. Employment and career history	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

ix. Information relating to the financial affairs of the individual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
x. Information relating to the individual's religion or other beliefs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
xi. Information relating to the individual's membership of a trade union.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Will the information be	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>The study's informed consent form has the only identifiable data in the study. The consent forms will be secured in a locked filing cabinet in Professor Gerard Lacey's office.</p> <p>The videos have no identifiable data and are anonymised at capture point.</p>
1) Anonymised	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2) Pseudonymised (Please note the term "<i>pseudoanonymised</i>" is meaningless in data protection and should not appear in a DPIA).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3) Identifiable	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Select the appropriate choice. Please note that where possible information should be anonymised			

Section 3: Assessment

	Question	Response	Required Action E.g. Seek Information Governance advice
Legal compliance – is it fair and lawful?	1. What is the legal basis for processing the information? This is your valid legal reason for processing. These reasons are laid out in Article 6 & 9 of GDPR. Any processing of special categories of data such as health, genetic and biometric information will require TWO legal basis for processing- one from Article 6 and one from Article 9. N.B. In general, the most appropriate basis in RCSI is for processing being carried out for the performance of a task in the public interest Art. 6.1(e) and necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research Ar. 9.2(j)	<p>The study's data processing is based on Article 9.2.</p> <p>The study is the Master Thesis of Master Student Laura Manso, under the academic supervision of Professor Gerard Lacey at Maynooth University.</p>	
	2. If the legal basis is Article 6(1)(f) "legitimate interests", please describe the legitimate interests being relied upon and clarify whether the processing is necessary and proportionate.	Not applicable.	
	<p>3. a) - Is the processing of individual's information likely to interfere with the 'right to privacy' under Article 8 of the Human Rights Act?</p> <p>b) - Have you identified the social need and aims of the initiative and are the planned response actions proportionate in response to social need?</p>	<p>The study's processing data will not interfere with the right to privacy under Article 8 of the Human Rights Act.</p> <p>The study's needs and aims are identified, and the planned response is proportionate to them.</p>	

	4. It is important that patients affected by the initiative are informed as to what is happening with their information. Is this covered by fair processing information already provided to individuals or is a new or revised communication needed?	Not applicable.	
	5. If you are relying on consent to process personal data, please clarify (i) How will consent be obtained and recorded (ii) What information will be provided to support the consent process (iii) How will the value and integrity of the study be preserved in the event that consent is later withdrawn?	<p>The informed consent form will be requested to potential research participants prior to the collection of data. The consent forms will be first shared by email to potential research participants and then presented in the paper format during the RCSI Surgical Bootcamp. Interested volunteers will sign the consent forms, which will be securely locked in a private cabinet at Maynooth University, only accessible to Laura Manso and Professor Gerard Lacey.</p> <p>The consent form has all the study information (description and objectives) and the details on the processing of personal data to be performed in the Study, in accordance to the GDPR.</p> <p>The study's analyses are based on aggregated video datasets. As a result, in the event that consent is later withdrawn, the value and integrity of the study be preserved.</p>	
Purpose	6. Does the project involve the use of existing personal data for new purposes?	No.	

	7. Are potential new purposes likely to be identified as the scope of the project expands?	No.	
Adequacy	8. Is the information you are using likely to be of good enough quality for the purposes it is used for?	Yes.	
Accurate and up to date	9. Are you able to amend information when necessary to ensure currency and accuracy?	Yes.	
	10. How are you ensuring that personal data obtained from individuals or other organisations is accurate?	The research participants will sign their own informed consent forms. We only require their name and signature for proper and adequate data processing, as per the GDPR.	
Retention	11. What are the retention periods for the personal data and explain why this duration is necessary? How will this be implemented?	The study's data will be permanently destroyed or deleted at the end of the study (August 2025).	
	12. Are there any exceptional circumstances for retaining certain personal data for longer than is necessary?	No.	
	13. How will personal data be fully anonymised or destroyed after it is no longer necessary or fit for purpose?	The study's consent forms will be destroyed in a paper shredder and the videos will be permanently deleted from the secure servers in Maynooth University.	
Rights of the individual	14. How will you respond to requests from data subjects (or someone acting on their behalf) for access to their personal information once held? Will the information be provided to the data subject on their right to rectification, erasure, portability etc?	Data subjects are able to access their personal data. This access will be provided within a week of request or a month of request for more complicated requests. Information on the participants' rights to access, rectification, erasure, and	

		portability will be provided to the research students.	
Appropriate technical and organisational measures	15. What procedures are in place to ensure that all staff with access to the patient data have received adequate information governance training?	Not applicable.	
	16. If using an electronic system to process subject access requests, what security measures are in place?	Not applicable.	
	17. How will the information be provided, collated and used?	The consent forms will be signed and stored in a locked cabinet at the Maynooth University. The videos will be stored in secure servers at the Maynooth University. The videos will be used to train and validate a video-based automatic tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.	
	18. What security measures will be used to transfer the identifiable information? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Have you identified any potential risk? ii. The potential impact of any such risk on the data subject. iii. The likelihood and severity of any risk. iv. How you intend to deal with it. 	The identifiable information (signed consent forms in paper format) will be securely stored in a locked cabinet owned by Professor Gerard Lacey in the Electronic Engineering department in Maynooth University. The DPIA accounts for applied security measures.	
Transfers both	19. Will individual's personal information be disclosed internally/externally in identifiable form and if so to whom, how and why?	No.	

	20. Will personal data be transferred to a country outside of the European Economic Area? If yes, what arrangements will be in place to safeguard the personal data?	No.	
Consultation	21. Who should be consulted to identify privacy related risks and how will this be achieved? Identify both internal and external stakeholders. <i>Link back to stakeholders on page 3.</i>	Laura Manso, Principal Investigator; Professor Gerard Lacey, Academic Supervisor and Cecily Giles, DPO at Maynooth University.	
	22. Following the consultation – what privacy risks have been raised? E.g. Legal basis for collecting and using the information, security of the information in transit etc. You should also include consultation with the data subject – have their views been sought?	The privacy risks raised are associated with the non-authorized access, disclosure, or use of data, the accidental release of sensitive information and the misuse of data for malicious purposes. In addition, when involving studies of a limited size sample, there is a higher risk of identifiability of research participants. See section 3 in this DPIA.	
Guidance used	23. List any national guidance applicable to the initiative that is referred to.	The Data Protection Act 2018, which gives effect to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Ireland and transposes the Law Enforcement Directive.	

5.1 Privacy issues identified and risk analysis

5.1.1 Identify the privacy risks

Table 1

Ref No.	Privacy issue – element of the initiative that gives rise to the risk	(a) Risk to individuals (complete if appropriate to issue or put not applicable)	(b) Compliance risk (complete if appropriate to issue or put not applicable)	(c) Associated organisation /corporate risk (complete if appropriate to issue or put not applicable)
PR1	<i>Non-authorized access, disclosure or use to personal data, accidental release of sensitive information and misuse of data for malicious purposes</i>	<i>Individuals' personal data will be potentially made public or used for malicious purposes</i>	<i>Non-compliance with Articles 5 and 25 GDPR</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>
PR2	<i>Identifiability of research participants</i>	<i>Individuals are easily identified</i>	<i>Non-compliance with Articles 25 and 32 GDPR</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>

5.1.2 Identify the privacy solutions

Table 2

Ref No.	Risk – taken from column (a), (b) and/or (c) in table 1.	Risk score – see tables at Appendix 2			Proposed solution(s) /mitigating action(s)	Result: is the risk accepted, eliminated, or reduced?	Risk to individuals is now OK? Signed off by?
		Likelihood	Impact	RAG status			
PR1	<i>Non-authorized access, disclosure or use to personal data, accidental release of sensitive information and misuse of data for malicious purposes</i> <i>Individuals' personal data will be potentially</i>	1	2		<i>Personal data is constrained to the signed consent forms. The data captured in the signed consent forms are name, age range, gender and signature.</i>	<i>Reduced to a negligible level (at this stage it is not possible to declare the risk's elimination).</i>	<i>Yes</i> <i>Sign-off tbc</i>

	<p><i>made public or used for malicious purposes</i></p> <p><i>Non-compliance with Articles 5 and 25 GDPR</i></p>				<p><i>Consent forms are in a written paper format. Consent forms are stored for the study's duration in a locked cabinet at Professor Gerard's Lacey office in the Electronic Engineering Department of Maynooth University.</i></p> <p><i>Only Laura Manso and Professor Gerard Lacey have access to the locked cabinet.</i></p> <p><i>The signed consent forms will be permanently destroyed (shredded) at the end of the study (August 2025).</i></p>		
PR2	<p><i>Identifiability of research participants</i></p> <p><i>Individuals are easily identified</i></p> <p><i>Non-compliance with Articles 25 and 32 GDPR</i></p>	2	2		<p><i>The face-to-face contact with research participants will be constrained to a maximum of 30-minute sessions, fully dedicated to the video capture of the participants' hands performing sutures.</i></p> <p><i>During the video capture sessions, the researcher will be monitoring the images at the computers' screens to validate the recordings.</i></p> <p><i>A tendentially equal, age- and gender-balanced sample will be sought, in order to reduce the risk of identifiability based</i></p>	<p><i>Reduced to an acceptable level (at this stage it is not possible to declare the risk's elimination).</i></p>	<p><i>Yes</i></p> <p><i>Sign-off tbc</i></p>

				<p><i>on demographic characteristics.</i></p> <p><i>Rigorous anonymisation will be applied, avoiding direct identifiers (addresses and email addresses will not be collected from research participants) and using full anonymisation (a unique code is given to each video that cannot be linked to the research participant) in all captured videos with no sound, so that the data cannot be linked back to research participants.</i></p> <p><i>Captured video data will be aggregated in a unique dataset for the study, preventing research participants from being identified.</i></p> <p><i>Special attention will be dedicated to inform research participants better and transparently about the use of their data, their data protection rights and any potential risks of re-identification.</i></p> <p><i>Opportunities will be offered to research participants to discuss any concerns they may have concerning the use of their data and their own anonymity.</i></p>		
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5.1.3 Integrate the PIA outcomes back into the project plan

NB. This must include any actions identified in Table 1 and Table 2.

Who is responsible for integrating the PIA outcomes back in to the project plan and updating any project management paperwork? Who is responsible for implementing the solutions that have been approved? Who is the contact for any privacy concerns which may arise in the future?							
Ref No.	Action to be taken	Date for completion of actions	Anticipated risk score following mitigation			Responsibility for action – <i>job title not names</i>	Current status/progress
			Likelihood	Impact	RAG status		
PR1	Create the consent form and participant information leaflet	May 2025	0	0		Principal Investigator	Completed
PR1	Store the signed consent forms in a locked cabinet	June and July 2025	0	0		Academic Supervisor	To be done
PR1	Permanently destroy the signed consent forms	August 2025	0	0		Academic Supervisor	To be done
PR2	Define that video recordings have no sound and only capture the hands' movements	May 2025	0	0		Principal Investigator	Completed
PR2	Seek a tendentially equal, age- and gender-balanced sample to reduce the identifiability risk based on demographic characteristics.	May 2025	0	0		Principal Investigator	Completed
PR2	Set short video recording sessions with research participants	May 2025	0	0		Principal Investigator	Completed
PR2	Conduct dedicated sessions with potential research participants to better explain the study, its use of data, the participants' rights concerning data protection, anonymity and any potential risks of re-identification.	June and July 2025	0	0		Principal Investigator	To be done
PR2	Aggregate the captured video data in a unique dataset for the study, preventing identifiability of individuals.	June and July 2025	0	0		Principal Investigator	To be done

6 Appendix 1: Study Ethics Approval by Maynooth University

MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY,
MAYNOOTH, CO. KILDARE, IRELAND

Dr Rafael De Andrade Moral
Chair of the Biomedical & Life Sciences Research Ethics Subcommittee
Maynooth University Research Ethics Committee

13 June 2025
Prof. Gerard Lacey
Department of Electronic Engineering
Maynooth University

Re: Application for ethical approval for a Project entitled: Educational tool for the analysis of clinical suturing using computer vision.

Dear Professor Lacey,

The above project has been evaluated under Tier 2 process, expedited review and we would like to inform you that ethical approval has been granted.

Any deviations from the project details submitted to the ethics committee will require further evaluation. This ethical approval will expire on 30/08/2025.

Please note: all projects now require an end of project report which is attached. Please complete and upload the end of project report to your RIS ethics record after the project end date.

Kind Regards,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Aileen O'Keefe".

On behalf of
Dr Rafael De Andrade Moral
Chair of the Biomedical & Life Sciences Research Ethics Subcommittee

Reference Number
BSRESC-2025-40752

7 Appendix 2: Risk Assessment Form by Maynooth University

Department of Electronic Engineering, Maynooth University

MSc PROJECT RISK ASSESSMENT FORM Rev. 3

NAME AND STUDENT NUMBER: Laura Manso, 24252940		PROJECT NAME: SUGAR – Surgical sUturing GrAdeR
SUPERVISOR: Professor Gerry Lacey		PROJECT LOCATION: Maynooth University, Royal College of Surgeons of Ireland (RCSI)
BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT The SUGAR Project aims to develop a novel video-based approach for observing continuous, long sequence of surgical students and experts' hands and surgical tools movements with a camera, and then modelling and evaluating the surgical suturing skill demonstrated in the observation through the application of advanced and optimised DL techniques. Since the system is based on the video data analysis of hand and tool movement rather than sensor-based data, it can be extended to provide real-time feedback to surgical interns while doing surgical exercises or even to surgeons while performing an actual surgery.		
Hazards, Risk [High(H) Medium (M) Low (L)], and Control Measures		
HAZARD	Risk	Controls
Working with surgical needles	L	Only handled with needle drivers by medical students.
Working on location at RCSI	L	Follow all RCSI health and safety guidelines.
Identified risks should be discussed with your supervisor and a safe system of work agreed. A more in-depth risk assessment may be required after initial review. Do not proceed until form is signed off.		
Further Controls Required		
SIGNATURE OF STUDENT: <u><i>Laura Manso</i></u> DATE: 13/02/2025 SIGNATURE OF SUPERVISOR: <u><i>Gerry Lacey</i></u> DATE: 05/03/2025 DEPT HEALTH AND SAFETY COMMITTEE MEMBER: <u><i>John Maloney</i></u> DATE: 14/03/25		

Next, the Participant Information Leaflet is presented. This document is provided to potential participants in the research study with the purpose of giving them the necessary information about the study and enabling them to make a fully informed decision about whether to participate.

RCSI

ROYAL
COLLEGE
OF SURGEONS
IN IRELAND

**Maynooth
University**

National University
of Ireland Maynooth

Participant Information Leaflet

Study title: Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI

Principal investigator's name:	Laura Manso
Principal investigator's title:	Research Student
Telephone number of principal investigator:	+351 933 329 394
Consultant/co-investigator's name:	Professor Gerard Lacey
Consultant/co-investigator's title:	Professor of Robotics at Maynooth University
Data Controller's/joint Controller's Identity:	Laura Manso (research student) and Professor Gerard Lacey (academic supervisor)
Data Controller's/joint Controller's Contact Details:	Laura Manso: T. +351 933 329 394; E. laura.guerramanso.2025@mumail.ie Prof. Gerard Lacey: T. (01) 7086767; E. Gerry.Lacey@mu.ie
Data Protection Officer's Identity:	Cecily Giles
Data Protection Officer's Contact Details:	T. (01) 7086184; E. Cecily.Giles@mu.ie

You are being invited to take part in a research study to be carried out at the Maynooth University and the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI) by myself, Laura Manso, and I am a masters' student in the Department Electronic Engineering at Maynooth University.

Before you decide whether or not you wish to take part, you should read the information provided below carefully and, if you wish, discuss it with your family, friends or GP (doctor). Take time to ask questions – don't feel rushed and don't feel under pressure to make a quick decision.

You should clearly understand the risks and benefits of taking part in this study so that you can make a decision that is right for you. This process is known as 'Informed Consent'.

You don't have to take part in this study. If you decide not to take part it won't affect you in any way.

You can change your mind about taking part in the study any time you like. Even if the study has started, you can still opt out. You don't have to give us a reason. If you do opt out, rest assured it won't affect the quality of treatment you get in the future.

Why is this study being done?

The study aims to deliver an objective, reproducible, and cost-effective method to evaluate surgical suturing skills, using a computer vision model and deep learning techniques. Videos of hands executing sutures will be captured and assessed by the tool and by at least one surgical specialist to allow the distinction between surgical trainees and experts' suturing skills and provide a grading score.

The primary goal of this study is the development of a novel low-cost video-based grading tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.

As a result of the adoption of this new tool, it is expected a reduction of the need for expert review of sutures, the acquisition of the capability for medical students to perform self-directed learning in suturing skills and the creation of an objective and reproducible set of suturing skill scores that students can review.

Who is organising and funding this study?

I am Laura Manso, a masters' student in the Department Electronic Engineering, Maynooth University.

As part of the requirements for my MSc. in Robotics and Embedded AI, I am undertaking a research study under the academic supervision of Professor Gerard Lacey. This study is conducted in collaboration with the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland.

The study is concerned with the development, testing and validation of a novel low-cost video-based tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills. Videos of hands of surgical trainees and experts executing sutures will be captured and analysed using computer vision (CV) algorithms. Then, the application of advanced and optimised deep learning (DL) techniques will enable the assessment of the suturing skills demonstrated during observation, using metrics, such as the RCSI's Surgical Affairs Department validated checklist.

The research study is fully funded by the Maynooth University and there is no grant associated with this study. Also know that I am not being paid to recruit research participants for this study.

Why am I being asked to take part?

You have been asked because you represent the surgical community we want to involve in the study. You are Year 1 surgical trainees on the national surgical training programme or expert surgical trainers at RCSI, and we would like to capture videos of your hands while performing surgical sutures to train and validate a video-based tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.

How will the study be carried out?

The study will start on June 23rd 2025 and it will last for 2 months.

For convenience purposes, the capture of the videos will take place at RCSI facilities, after the Surgical Bootcamp 2025, whereas the data analysis, processing and prototype development will take place at Maynooth University.

The number of research participants will be 15.

In the study, all research participants will be asked to perform suturing, while their hands movements are filmed.

What will happen to me if I agree to take part?

If you agree to take part in the study, you will need to fill, sign and return a consent form. This consent form, which you will receive and be able to read, will collect your age range, gender, years of suturing experience (expert surgical trainers), years of needlework experience (surgical trainees).

Please know that the consent forms folder will be securely stored in a locked cupboard at the Electronic Engineering Department in Maynooth University and only Professor Gerard Lacey, the academic supervisor of the study, will have access to the consent forms folder.

After the signing of the consent form and your selection as a research participant, meeting the study's inclusion criteria, you will be asked to perform a surgical suture and the video of your hands performing the surgical suturing will be captured.

The videos will have no sound and no identifiable information. At the time of their collection, they will be anonymised with key numbers.

All data that is collected about you during the course of the study will be kept confidential. No names will be identified at any time. All hard copy information will be held in a locked cabinet at the researcher's place of work, electronic information will be encrypted and held securely on MU PC or servers and will be accessed only by Laura Manso and Professor Gerard Lacey. No information will be distributed to any other unauthorised individual or third party.

At the conclusion of the study in August 2025, all study data will be destroyed or permanently deleted.

Video/and or Audio recordings?

As a research participant, you will be asked to perform a surgical suture and the video of your hands performing the surgical suturing will be captured. No audio will be captured.

The videos will be anonymised upon capture at the point of collection.

It is possible for research participants to review the captured videos, should they wish to do so.

What are the benefits?

You will not receive individual benefits or gains from taking part in the study.

Still, because the study's primary goal is the development of a novel low-cost video-based grading tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills, I envisage that, upon the adoption of this new tool, there will be the capability at RCSI for reducing the need for expert review of sutures, for surgical trainees to perform self-directed learning in suturing skills and for applying an objective and reproducible set of suturing skill scores that students can review.

What are the risks?

As a research participant, you will be asked to perform a surgical suture and the video of your hands performing the surgical suturing will be captured, with no audio. The videos will be anonymised at the point of collection.

I don't envisage any negative consequences for you in taking part in the study, although it is possible that the recording of your suturing may cause some discomfort.

What if something goes wrong when I'm taking part in this study?

If you decide to take part in this study, please know that you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and/or to withdraw your information up until such time as the research findings are analysed. A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, will not affect your relationship with the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland.

At the end of the video capture session, I will discuss with you how you found the experience and how you are feeling. If you experience any discomfort following the recording of the video, you may contact Donncha Ryan (donncharyan@rcsi.ie). You may also contact my supervisor, Professor Gerard Lacey (gerry.lacey@mu.ie), if you feel the research has not been carried out as I have described.

Will it cost me anything to take part?

You will not incur in any costs if you decide to take part in this study.

Is the study confidential?

Yes, all data that is collected about you during the course of the study will be kept confidential.

No names will be identified at any time. All hard copy information will be held in a locked cabinet at the researchers' place of work, electronic information will be encrypted and held securely on Maynooth University's PC or servers and will be accessed only by Laura Manso and

Professor Gerard Lacey. No information will be distributed to any other unauthorised individual or third party. If you so wish, the data that you provide can also be made available to you at your own discretion.

The confidentiality of the collected study data will be attained through (1) the anonymisation of data at the point of collection; (2) the storage and processing of only anonymised data at the Maynooth University servers; and (3) the authenticated and protected access of the research student to the secure Maynooth University servers.

At the conclusion of the study in August 2025, all study data (video recordings and consent forms) will be destroyed or permanently deleted.

Data Protection

The personal data that will be collected from you is your signature in the consent form. Your personal information is necessary to ensure the lawful processing of the data, which will help us in the development of a novel low-cost video-based grading tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.

The processing of your data in the study is carried out for the purposes of the legitimate interests of scientific research by Laura Manso, and it abides to the 2016 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) principles. In this context, observing Article 6 GDPR, the data processing is lawful as it only occurs if you have given your written consent to the processing of data in the study for the specific purpose of the research study. It is noted that no processing of special categories of personal data, as identified in Article 9 GDPR, will take place in the study.

The recipients of the data will be Laura Manso, the research student, and Professor Gerard Lacey, the academic supervisor.

The study data will be stored until the completion of the research study on August 2025. At this time, all study data will be destroyed or permanently deleted.

At this time, it is not foreseen any risk or implications to you that might arise as a result of the data processing. All data processing follows applicable GDPR principles and security mechanisms are in place to ensure data confidentiality.

If you decide to take part in the research study, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and/or to withdraw your information up until such time as the research findings are analysed. A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, will not affect your relationship with the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland. In case you decide to withdraw consent, you need to contact the research student, Laura Manso (T. +351 933329394; E. laura.guerramanso.2025@mumail.ie), to communicate your decision. As a result of this communication, all study data associated with you will be destroyed and deleted permanently.

You have the right to lodge a complaint with the Data Protection Commissioner concerning this study. For that, please go to <https://www.dataprotection.ie/en/contact/how-contact-us>.

You have the right to request access to your data and a copy of it. The data that you provide can be made available to you at your own discretion.

You have the right to restrict or object to the processing of your data, up until such time as the research findings are analysed.

You have the right to have any inaccurate information about you corrected or deleted.

You have the right to have your personal data deleted, up until such time as the research findings are analysed.

You have the right to data portability, in that you may move your data from one controller to another in a readable format.

The study does not involve automated decision-making, including profiling.

You have the right to object to automated processing, including profiling, if you wish.

The personal data collected from you will not be further processed. The personal data collected from you will only be used to meet the specific purposes of the research study, as identified.

Your data will not be transferred to a country outside of the EU or an international organisation.

Where can I get further information?

If you have any further queries about the study or if you want to opt out of the study, you can rest assured it won't affect the quality of treatment you get in the future.

If you need any further information now or at any time in the future concerning this study, please contact:

Laura Manso

T. +351 933 329 394; E. laura.guerramanso.2025@mumail.ie

Next, the Consent Form is presented. This document is an agreement between the researcher and the research participant, signed by both parties, and outlining the roles and responsibilities both are taking towards one another throughout the research project.

Consent Form

I,, agree to participate in Laura Manso's research study titled Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI.

Please tick each statement below:

The purpose and nature of the study has been explained to me verbally & in writing. I've been able to ask questions, which were answered satisfactorily.

I am participating voluntarily.

I give permission for my hands performing suturing to be video-recorded.

I understand that I can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time, whether that is before it starts or while I am participating.

I understand that I can withdraw permission to use the data right up to the analysis of the data.

It has been explained to me how my data will be managed and that I may access it on request.

I understand the limits of confidentiality as described in the participant information leaflet.

I understand that my data, in an anonymous format, may be used in any subsequent publications, if I give permission below:

I agree for my data to be used for subsequent publications

I do not agree for my data to be used for subsequent publications

Signed

Date

Participant Name in block capitals

I the undersigned have taken the time to fully explain to the above participant the nature and purpose of this study in a manner that they could understand. I have explained the risks involved as well as the possible benefits. I have invited them to ask questions on any aspect of the study that concerned them.

Signed.....

Date.....

Researcher Name in block capitals

If during your participation in this study you feel the information and guidelines that you were given have been neglected or disregarded in any way, or if you are unhappy about the process, please contact the Secretary of the Maynooth University Ethics Committee at research.ethics@mu.ie or +353 (0)1 708 6019. Please be assured that your concerns will be dealt with in a sensitive manner.

For your information the Data Controller for this research project is Maynooth University, Maynooth, Co. Kildare. The Data Protection office is located in Room 17/27, Rye Hall Extension, North Campus, Maynooth University, which can be contacted at dataprotection@mu.ie. Maynooth University Data Privacy policies can be found at <https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/data-protection>.

Next, the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland's Ethical Approval is presented.

Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland
The Research Ethics Committee
111 St. Stephens Green, Dublin 2, Ireland
Tel: +353 1 4022205 Email: recadmin@rcsi.ie

Prof Declan Patton (Chair)
Dr Niamh Clarke, Convenor

Private and Confidential

MS Laura Manso
12th June 2025

HREC Reference Number	REC202503016
Project Title	Automatic Evaluation of Suturing Skills with AI
Researcher Name (lead applicant):	Donncha Ryan
Principal Investigator:	Laura Manso
Other Individuals Involved::	Prof. Gerry Lacey

Dear Laura Manso

Thank you for your Research Ethics Committee (REC) application. We are pleased to advise that ethical approval has been granted by the committee for this study.

This letter provides approval for data collection for the time requested in your application and for an additional 6 months. This is to allow for any unexpected delays in proceeding with data collection. Therefore this research ethics approval will expire on 23rd February 2026.

This ethical approval is given on the understanding that:

- All personnel listed in the approved application have read, understand and are thoroughly familiar with all aspects of the study.
- Any significant change which occurs in connection with this study and/or which may alter its ethical consideration must be reported to the REC, and an ethical amendment submitted where appropriate.
- **A final report will be submitted to the REC upon completion of the project.**

Please note it is the responsibility of the Data Controller/Joint Data Controllers/PI and relevant Data Protection Officer to ensure and monitor compliance with relevant data protection legislation and regulation.

Please liaise with relevant data protection officer(s) with regard to progress in relation to your Data Protection Impact Assessment.

Receipt of research ethics committee approval is not, and should not be regarded as evidence of compliance with GDPR 2016 or the Health Research Regulations 2018.

We wish you all the best with your research.

Yours sincerely,

Niamh Clarke

PP Dr Niamh Clarke (Convenor)

Prof Declan Patton (Chair)

Next, the Maynooth University's Ethical Approval is presented.

MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY,
MAYNOOTH, CO. KILDARE, IRELAND

Dr Rafael De Andrade Moral
Chair of the Biomedical & Life Sciences Research Ethics Subcommittee
Maynooth University Research Ethics Committee

13 June 2025

Prof. Gerard Lacey
Department of Electronic Engineering
Maynooth University

Re: Application for ethical approval for a Project entitled: Educational tool for the analysis of clinical suturing using computer vision.

Dear Professor Lacey,

The above project has been evaluated under Tier 2 process, expedited review and we would like to inform you that ethical approval has been granted.

Any deviations from the project details submitted to the ethics committee will require further evaluation. This ethical approval will expire on 30/08/2025.

Please note: all projects now require an end of project report which is attached. Please complete and upload the end of project report to your RIS ethics record after the project end date.

Kind Regards,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Aileen O'Sheahan', written in a cursive style.

On behalf of
Dr Rafael De Andrade Moral
Chair of the Biomedical & Life Sciences Research Ethics Subcommittee

Reference Number BSRESC-2025-40752

Appendix B

SUGAR CV Models Training and Validation

Figures B.1 to B.6 display the results from the remaining YOLOv10 models' training and validation, which highlight, throughout the training time, a reduction tendency in loss values and an augmentation tendency in precision, recall and mean Average Precision 50 values.

Figure B.1: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 1

Figures B.7 to B.18 display the results from the remaining YOLOv11 models' training and validation, which highlight, throughout the training time, a reduction tendency in loss values and an augmentation tendency in precision, recall and mean Average Precision 50 values.

Figure B.2: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 2

Figure B.3: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 3

Figure B.4: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 4

Figure B.5: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 5

Figure B.6: Results Obtained from YOLOv10 Train 7

Figure B.7: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 1

Figure B.8: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 2

Figure B.9: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 5

Figure B.10: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 6

Figure B.11: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 7

Figure B.12: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 8

Figure B.13: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 9

Figure B.14: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 10

Figure B.15: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 11

Figure B.16: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 12

Figure B.17: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 13

Figure B.18: Results Obtained from YOLOv11 Train 15

Appendix C

Poster SUGAR Master's Thesis

Next, the Thesis's poster is presented.

Introduction

Suturing is a fundamental surgical skill that is meticulously evaluated by surgical educators. However, manual evaluation is subjective, imprecise, non-reproducible, resource- and time-consuming.

An automated approach to suturing training facilitates a larger number of surgical trainees to be trained, with the right set of highly qualified skills and competencies that ultimately contribute to greater patient safety, a positive societal impact.

This Master's Thesis aims to develop a proof-of-concept for a novel CV-based tool capable of delivering objective, reproducible and cost-effective suture skills assessments, using CV techniques.

Figure 1 – Setup Image: computer linked to 2 suture stations, each with a camera, set of suturing tools and table lamp.

Figure 2 – Suture station with a HD camera, lamp, suturing pad, needle holder, toothed forceps, suture cutting scissors and needle.

Methodology

- ❖ Data capture: HD suturing videos to validate the SUGAR tool made by surgical trainees and RCSI trainers;
- ❖ Suturing station purposely designed by RCSI experts;
- ❖ Dataset creation involving manual labelling for hands and suturing tools detection and segmentation (8 labels);
- ❖ YOLOv10 and YOLOv11 models to train and compare;
- ❖ Suture Quality Assessment:
 - ❖ Video analysis: during suturing task with 7 metrics (Fig. 3, 4);
 - ❖ Image processing: end-product image with 5 metrics (Fig. 5, 6);
- ❖ Expert system to assess relevant suture quality metrics, while ensuring use of explainable, responsible and transparent AI.

Figure 3 – Original Suturing Image.

Figure 4 – YOLO applied to Suturing Image.

Figure 5 – Original Suture Image.

Figure 6 – YOLO applied to Suture Image.

Results

- ❖ 51 suturing videos and suture end-product images captured, with the assistance of 38 surgical trainees and 13 trainers;
- ❖ For the video analysis, a dataset with 11K+ images is developed, based on manual labelling;
- ❖ For the image analysis, a dataset with 1.7K+ images is created.
- ❖ YOLOv11 model is selected given the results in Table 1;
- ❖ 13 suture quality metrics identified: 1 for human-based input, 7 for video analysis and 5 for image processing;
- ❖ Website deployed to obtain expert reviews for validation;
- ❖ SUGAR achieved the results displayed in Table 2:
 - ❖ Ground-truth: 2 RCSI expert reviews per video and image;
 - ❖ Validation: SUGAR's alignment with the ground-truth.

Table 1 – Selected CV Models Training and Validation.

Dataset and Model	Overall Precision	Overall Recall
Video – YOLOv11L-seg	92.0%	87.3%
Image – YOLOv11L-seg	95.6%	90.3%

Table 2 – SUGAR's Validation Based on the Expert Reviews.

Tool	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
SUGAR	81.01%	85.68%	61.75%	71.77%

Discussion

- ❖ Results demonstrate that SUGAR can reliably detect and track movements, and detect and segment different surgical tools and key suture components with high accuracy.
- ❖ High alignment between the expert reviews' scores and the SUGAR's outputs highlights the SUGAR tool's ability to automatically assess and grade suturing performance, based on specific suture quality metrics.
- ❖ Future work: improve the CV model's accuracy; decrease suture quality metrics' level of subjectivity.
- ❖ SUGAR exhibits a promising potential as an educational tool that will allow surgical students to further develop basic suturing proficiency using self-directed learning.

Key Take-Aways

- ✓ Identification of relevant objective suture quality metrics to predict the level of expertise;
- ✓ Creation of a novel dataset for detection and segmentation of surgical suturing tools and hands;
- ✓ Attainment of a high alignment between the expert reviews' scores and SUGAR's outputs;
- ✓ Verification of the feasibility of applying CV-based techniques to suturing skills' quality assessment;
- ✓ Development of a novel proof-of-concept for a low-cost video-based grading tool capable of assessing and grading students' surgical suturing skills.

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